

**ANALELE
UNIVERSITĂȚII DIN ORADEA**

FASCICULA: PROTECȚIA MEDIULUI

**VOL XLIII
ANUL 29**

**Editura Universității din Oradea
2024**

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ANALELE UNIVERSITĂȚII DIN ORADEA, FASCICULA PROTECȚIA MEDIULUI
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(Ed. română) = I.S.S.N. 2065 – 3476

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ANALYSIS OF FINANCING TRENDS OF YOUNG FARMERS IN ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The work represents an incursion into the development of agriculture through specific European funds. The multitude of approaches regarding European funds with agrarian and rural specifics lead to the clear establishment of the objectives and purpose of this work. The theme presents particular importance in the current global context of increasingly precarious food safety and security. At the level of the European Union (EU), these issues have been recognized since the 1950s, establishing in the following decades the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), designed to support agriculture in particular. The exacerbated development of industry, services and later the quaternary sectors led to the partial neglect of agriculture in the first phase of European economic recovery after the Second World War. The financing of agriculture, both at the European level and at the world level, has been imposed as a measure to eradicate global hunger and malnutrition. Through the adopted policies, especially within the framework of the CAP, the EU has become a leader in the substantial financing of agro-rural development.

The work also develops aspects related to the agro-rural sustainability of Romania, pointing out the importance of farmers, especially young ones, in national agriculture. The Romanian agro-rural entrepreneurial population is older, which is why young farmers represent the chance of a certain future for national agriculture.

Keywords: agricultural funds, financing analysis, young farmers

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INTRODUCTION

The main components of the CAP for the period under discussion are achieved through two complementary stages: - through annual direct payments and market support granted to farmers and - through multi-annual rural development measures. Through direct payments, which are not linked to the amount of production, competitiveness in the agricultural sector is increased and farmers' adaptation to the market is encouraged. Concrete and targeted measures ensure the development of farms and rural settlements, the support of social capital and the protection of natural resources. The 2014-2020 period saw the consolidation (unification) of the two dimensions of the CAP: the first, which finances direct aid and market measures, is made entirely from the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EGF); the second, which

supports the development of rural areas, is co-financed.

A relevant study in this regard, carried out by Zagorova (2023), shows a tendency to reduce the costs of interventions in agricultural markets with funds from the FEAGA before the indicative period 2014-2020, as well as a restriction/decrease in total intervention costs in the EU agricultural sector for the years 2014 and 2015, while for the period 2016-2019 a marked increase is again observed, with some downward fluctuation in 2018. The research data also shows a drastic reduction in financial support for export refunds for agricultural products produced in the EU, the value of which reached EUR 1.1 million in 2019, compared to EUR 146.7 million in 2012, EUR 62.4 million in 2013 and EUR 4.5 million in 2014, after which they decreased suddenly to EUR 0.3 million in 2015, EUR 0.6 million in 2016. The development of the EU CAP after 2021 is based

on the multiannual financial framework, proposed in May 2018, related to its reform for the period 2021-2027. At the heart of the reform is the EU's results-oriented CAP implementation model and the principle of subsidiarity, which gives member states a much greater role in agricultural interventions. The reform in the agricultural sector provides that the Union will initially establish the key parameters, including the CAP objectives, the main requirements and the main types of interventions under the first and second pillars, after which the Member States will draw up the multi-annual Strategic Plans for agricultural development at the national level. (Zagorova, 2023)

The Rural Development Program at the EU level for the period 2014-2020 consisted of 16 measures, most of them being divided into sub-measures. Among the most important 2014-2020 PNDR measures are: Investments in physical assets (measure 4), Development of holdings and enterprises (measure 6), Basic services and renewal of villages in rural areas (measure 7). (Michalcewicz-Kaniowska & Zajdel, 2019)

Current data show that the number of young farmers in several developed countries, such as the United States and European countries, has declined in recent decades as a result of technological, social and economic changes. In Europe, in 2013, around 30% of European farms were managed by a farmer aged over 65, and in some countries the age exceeds this figure, such as countries such as Spain 33%, Italy 40% and Portugal 50%. The low proportion of young farmers is seen as a problem due to the perceived loss of potential in creating efficient, competitive, innovative and therefore more profitable and sustainable agricultural businesses. It is the main reason why, at the level of the European Union, the financing of young farmers is a primary fact. Young farmers are more open to new ideas, ready to take greater risks, and are also more willing to use loan capital to expand their business. The main contribution of young farmers is the growing recognition that they play an important role in addressing food security challenges. (May et al., 2019)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The Support for the Installation of Young Farmers sub-measure aims to support the initial installation process of young farmers as leaders/managers of an agricultural holding.

The purpose of the investments supported under this sub-measure is to facilitate the establishment of young farmers as leaders of an agricultural holding, thus giving them the opportunity to get involved in this activity for the first time. The objectives of this initiative include boosting the number of young farmers starting their first farming activity as farm heads, encouraging them to become competitive, associate and participate in integrated food chains. At the same time, it is proposed to improve management, increase the competitiveness of the agricultural sector, and support the modernization process to comply with the requirements related to environmental protection, hygiene, animal welfare and workplace safety. The initiative also aims to create the opportunity for young resident farmers with minimal knowledge to become farm leaders. At the same time, the aim is to encourage young people and families from the countryside to settle in this area, having a positive impact on the national economy as a whole. (AFIR, 2021)

Beneficiaries eligible for this support include young farmers aged up to 40 who are setting up for the first time as sole heads of an agricultural holding, as well as multi-shareholder legal entities where a young farmer takes effective long-term control regarding management decisions, benefits and financial risks associated with the holding. The minimum conditions for accessing the support include placing the applicant in the category of micro and small enterprises, owning a farm between 12,000 and 50,000 S.O. (standard output) (standard production value), presenting a Business Plan (BP) and demonstrating the necessary skills and abilities. The Business Plan must include the manure management methods. The implementation of the PA must start within six months at most from the date of the decision to grant support, and the applicant undertakes to become an active farmer within a maximum of 18 months from the date of installation. The beneficiary must establish his domicile, registered office and workplace in the Territorial Administrative Unit (UAT) in which the holding is registered or in the bordering area of the UAT, until the start of the implementation of the PA. These conditions ensure the efficient and sustainable implementation of business plans. (AFIR, 2021)

Non-reimbursable support under sub-measure 6.1 Support for setting up young

farmers was 100% non-reimbursable and had a maximum value of 50,000 euros.

The analysis of young Romanian farmers (aged up to 39 years), of the evolution of their livestock, is a necessity for the agricultural financing sector, but especially for the agro-rural development of Romania.

Forecast statistical analysis takes into account:

- Observed data (2016-2018) - all graphs have an observed data section (red) covering the period 2016-2018.
- Forecasts (2019-2024) - the blue extension represents the forecasts for the period 2019-2024.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

At the level of Romania, young farmers represent a group on the verge of extinction. The agricultural sector has a high degree of aging. Farms managed by elderly farmers are thinly capitalized and therefore market oriented. There is a great need to renew generations of farmers in all sectors of Romanian agriculture to improve farm management and increase productivity. The European Union, through the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development, gives a special interest in supporting young farmers by granting installation aid, precisely to revive this segment of the population that is so necessary in community agriculture.

As can be seen in the following figures, analysis based on Eurostat data (2024), the 2016-2020 period - in which several measures from the National Rural Development Program 2014-2020 were applied - shows a revival of the number of young farmers, especially on the basis of their financing.

Figure 1 Effective young farmers in Romania

The histograms of the number of young farmers in Romania and in the administrative regions show an improved situation towards the end of the 2014-2020 programming period.

The frequency analysis of young farmers at the level of Romania and the development regions shows that there is an uneven distribution between the regions. The region with the highest average number of young farmers is Romania, followed by the Northeast and the Center. The Bucharest-Ilfov region has the lowest number of observations and therefore the results for this region are less stable. The coefficient of variation is over 100% for all regions, except Bucharest-Ilfov. This indicates a significant variability of funds allocated between regions.

Figure 2 Number of young farmers in Center

Figure 3 Effective young farmers in North-East

Figure 4 Effective young farmers in Southeast

Figure 5 Effective young farmers in South-Muntenia

Figure 6 Effective young farmers in Bucharest-Ilfov

Figure 7 Effective young farmers in South-W Oltenia

Figure 7 Effective young farmers in West

Histograms are skewed to the right, with longer tails in the direction of large values. This suggests that there may be a small number of regions that have significantly higher numbers of young farmers. The data presented in the histograms suggest an uneven distribution of the number of young farmers in Romania. The

northeastern and central regions of the country seem to benefit from a greater presence than the southern and western regions.

Regarding the forecast for the period 2020-2024, the forecast shows an overview of the future evolution of the number of young farmers in Romania in different sectors and models (figure 8).

Different models - the graph includes several models numbered from 1 to 9, each representing a specific group of young farmers from a certain development region of Romania, as follows:

1. First Model – Romania (Remodel-Model-1): a steady increase from 2016 to 2018 and a significant upward trend with a steady increase in numbers until 2024 is observed.
2. Second Model – Northwest (Innovators-Model-2): has a modest growth trend between 2016 and 2018, as well as similar growth to the first model, but less steep.
3. Third Model – Center (Creators-Model-3): shows similar growth to the previous models and a steady ascent, in line with the first two models.
4. The Fourth Model – North-East (InTech-Model-4): has a slight increase until 2018 and a continuation of the increase, although at a slower pace compared to the first three models.
5. Fifth Model – South-East (Skills-Model-5): a consistent increase is observed between 2016 and 2018 and a significant rise is predicted until 2024.
6. Sixth Model – South-Muntenia (Soundness-Model-6): shows little growth until 2018 and modest and steady rise until 2024.
7. The Seventh Model – Bucharest-Ilfov (Bumper-Model-7): has significant growth between 2016 and 2018, as well as steep growth to 2024, the highest of all models, suggesting rapid and extensive growth in this sector.
8. The Eighth Model – South-West Oltenia (Sonder-Model-8): shows moderate growth until 2018 and a continuous rise, similar to other models.
9. Ninth Model – West (Verdant-Model-9): Shows growth through 2018 and steady ascent at a similar rate to most other models.

The histogram analysis of young farmers from the north-west region of Romania shows that the population mean and standard deviation indicate a significant variability among young farmers, with the maximum frequency being approximately 1.568 (figure 8).

Figure 8 Forecast regarding the number of young farmers in Romania and development regions

This region has the largest population of young farmers.

The histogram shows the distribution of income frequency among young farmers in the

northwestern region of Romania. The information presented in the histogram can be used to perform a specific analysis of this population category.

The histogram is slightly skewed to the left, with a longer tail for lower incomes.

Figure 9 Effective young farmers in North-West

This suggests that most young farmers have relatively low incomes, but there are also a small number of farmers with significantly higher incomes.

CONCLUSIONS

The general trend of all models predicts a steady increase in the number of young farmers in various sectors until the end of 2024. Model 7 Bucharest-Ilfov (Bumper-Model-7) shows the steepest and most significant growth, suggesting a rapid expansion in this sector specific. All graphs show consistent growth, suggesting optimism regarding the future of young farmers in Romania. This analysis suggests a positive outlook for young farmers in Romania, with expansion predicted in all sectors represented in the models. However, for accurate strategic planning, detailed analysis of each model and the specific factors that

contribute to these predictions would be beneficial.

Based on the conclusions presented above, the following recommendations can be formulated specific for the North-West region of Romania:

- the government should implement policies to support young farmers with low incomes, such as subsidy programs or low-interest agricultural loans;

- training and education courses should be organized to help young farmers improve their skills and competences, which could enable them to earn higher incomes;

- markets for local agricultural products should be developed, which would give young farmers more opportunities to sell their products and earn more income.

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YIELD GAINED IN WHEAT CROP DUE TO THE USE OF NITROGEN-FIXING BACTERIA

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REVIEW

Abstract

Organic farming has numerous benefits for both the environment and human health. Here are some of these benefits: No pesticides and chemical fertilizers. Organic farming uses natural methods to control pests and improve soil fertility by eliminating or minimizing the use of pesticides and synthetic chemical fertilizers. Maintaining biodiversity: Through the diversified use of crops and agricultural practices, organic farming encourages biodiversity in the soil and agricultural ecosystems, helping to maintain ecological balance. At the same time, it also has a positive impact on wildlife and biodiversity, which are affected by the excessive use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides. Azotobacter can convert nitrogen gas from the atmosphere into a form that plants can use. This reduces reliance on chemical nitrogen fertilisers, saving costs for farmers and having a reduced impact on the environment. Nitrogen is an essential element for protein synthesis and other vital processes for plant growth. By providing an additional source of nitrogen, Azotobacter contributes to a more vigorous growth of plants, thus improving crop yield. Therefore, the wheat plants that were treated with Azotobacter chroococcum developed better and faster, of course, registering higher and higher quality yields per hectare. For this study, a product with a concentration of Azotobacter Chroococcum of over 1×10^9 CFU/cm³ was used, applied in stages. It is also worth noting that this experiment was carried out on the type of soil belonging to the luvisoil class. The works prior to the sowing period were carried out according to the crop to be sown and tested. In this study we conclude the major impact that Azotobacter chroococcum has on wheat yields in the organic wheat crop, where chemical fertilizers were not used, results were seen both in terms of plant growth and development, but also a resistance that Azotobacter Chroococcum offers to plants to stress factors, but also to pests.

Keywords: Azotobacter Chroococcum, wheat, biodiversity, concentration, yield, controlled temperature, luvisoil.
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INTRODUCTION

Bacteria have a significant impact on agriculture, being involved in various processes that contribute to soil health and plant growth. Here are some ways bacteria are essential in the agricultural context:

Nitrogen fixation: Nitrogen-fixing bacteria, such as Rhizobium, are able to convert nitrogen gas into a usable form for plants. These bacteria establish symbiosis with the roots of leguminous plants, providing them with nitrogen and improving soil fertility.

Promoting plant growth: Certain beneficial bacteria, such as Azotobacter and Bacillus, can secrete growth substances and hormones that stimulate plant development and give them.

Biofertilization: Beneficial bacteria can be used in the production of biofertilizers, which contain beneficial microorganisms to improve nutrient uptake by plants.

Biological pest control: Beneficial bacteria, such as Bacillus thuringiensis (Bt), produce substances that are toxic to certain pests, providing an environmentally friendly way to control them.

Bioremediation: Some bacteria have the ability to degrade chemicals or absorb heavy metals from the soil, contributing to the bioremediation process and cleaning up contaminated soils.

Fermentation: Bacteria are involved in the fermentation process, which can be used in the production of organic fertilizers and other agricultural products.

Nutrient preservation: Bacteria participate in nutrient cycling in the soil, helping to release and transform nutrients for plants.

Disease resistance: Beneficial bacteria can boost plants' immune systems, giving them increased resistance to various diseases and infections.

The conscious and sustainable use of bacteria in agriculture can help improve productivity, reduce dependence on chemical fertilizers and pesticides, as well as promote sustainable agricultural practices. (Tállai et al, 2023)

Nitrogen-fixing bacteria are microorganisms that have the ability to convert atmospheric nitrogen (N_2) into a usable form for plants and other organisms. This ability is essential for the nitrogen cycle and for maintaining soil fertility. Here is some important information about nitrogen-fixing bacteria (Yingying et al, 2022):

Types of bacteria: There are several genera of nitrogen-fixing bacteria, and the best known are *Rhizobium*, *Azotobacter*, *Clostridium* and *Frankia*. Each of these genera has specific adaptations to different environments and can form symbioses with different types of plants.

Rhizobium: These bacteria establish a symbiotic relationship with the roots of leguminous plants (such as beans, peas, clover). By forming nodules on plant roots, *Rhizobium* fixes atmospheric nitrogen and converts it into the form of ammonium, which is usable by plants.

Azotobacter: These bacteria are present in the soil and can fix atmospheric nitrogen independently, without having a symbiotic association with specific plants. *Azotobacter* contributes to improving soil fertility and promoting plant growth.

Clostridium: Certain species of clostridia are nitrogen fixers, but they are typically involved in the processes of putrefaction and decomposition of organic matter. However, under anaerobic conditions, some clostridia can fix nitrogen.

Frankia: These nitrogen-fixing bacteria are involved in symbiosis with certain plants known as actinized plants (e.g., shrubs of the *Elaeagnaceae* and *Myricaceae* family). These plants form root nodules where *Frankia* fixes nitrogen.

Plant benefits: Nitrogen-fixing bacteria provide the plant with an additional source of nitrogen, an essential element for protein

synthesis and overall plant growth. Through this symbiotic association or by fixing nitrogen in the soil, bacteria contribute to maintaining soil fertility.

Sustainable farming practices: Farmers can benefit from nitrogen-fixing bacteria by adopting sustainable farming practices, such as crop rotation with leguminous plants or by using bacterial inoculants in the soil to stimulate nitrogen fixation.

Nitrogen-fixing bacteria are therefore essential for soil health and supporting plant growth, helping to reduce the need for synthetic nitrogen fertilisers in agriculture.

Wheat cultivation worldwide is one of the most important and widespread cereal crops. Here are some key aspects regarding the wheat crop:

Wheat is one of the most produced cereals worldwide, and among the countries that produce the most significant quantities are the United States, Brazil, Argentina, China, etc. This plant, so widespread, has a very wide range of uses. It can be used in livestock farms for animal feed, but also for human consumption.

Another characteristic of wheat is its ability to be grown over a very large area, in different climatic conditions and on different types of soil. Of course, productions can be affected by the characteristics of each area. It is a plant that adapts easily, hence its worldwide spread.

The economic importance of wheat should not be neglected. Cereal cultivation contributes to the food security of many countries and also generates significant profits for farmers. In recent decades, several varieties of wheat have been discovered, and productions have increased worldwide.

The increase in the price of fertilizers and fuels used in agriculture has led farmers to find alternatives to these problems they face more and more often.

Such an alternative is represented by the use of fertilizers and organic stimulators, which intensify or have the ability to eliminate even completely the use of classic fertilizers, which in addition to destroying the humus layer so important for the development of plants by their excessive use, are also harmful to environmental factors, and can lead to the pollution of the groundwater.

Azotobacter Chroococcum can be a solution to this problem that affects thousands of farmers. Biological fertilizers do not only

refer to materials from animal manure and plant residues, but also include all products obtained through the activity of microorganisms and them.

Azotobacter chroococcum It is an aerobic rhizobacterium that can fix atmospheric nitrogen in nitrogen-based compounds such as nitrogen dioxide (Karthikeyan & Sakthivel, 2011).

These bacteria are capable of fixing atmospheric nitrogen by an average of 20 kg per hectare. They are oval or spherical and pleomorphic, form thick-walled cysts and can produce a large amount of mucus.

These bacteria can produce antifungal antibiotics that can inhibit the growth of several pathogenic fungi (Nazmun Ara et al, 2009).

It is a good alternative to increase nitrogen reserves and crop production capacity (Baral & Adhikari, 2014; Kumar et al., 2015). Here are some aspects of the impact of this bacterium on wheat cultivation:

Nitrogen fixation: *Azotobacter chroococcum* is known for its ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen in the soil in the form of nitrogen compounds. It provides an additional source of nitrogen, an essential nutrient for plant growth, including wheat.

Increased productivity: By fixing nitrogen and releasing it into the soil, *Azotobacter chroococcum* can help improve soil fertility. Nitrogen is essential for protein synthesis and other plant metabolic processes, thus influencing the yield and quality of maize production.

Stimulation of seed germination: Applying *Azotobacter chroococcum* to seeds can stimulate their germination. This effect can contribute to a faster and more uniform emergence of maize plants, positively influencing the early stages of development.

Disease control: *Azotobacter chroococcum* can secrete chemicals with antimicrobial potential, helping to control some pathogens that can affect corn crops. This can lead to better plant health and reduced disease risk.

Savings in the use of nitrogen fertilizers: By fixing atmospheric nitrogen, *Azotobacter chroococcum* can reduce dependence on chemical nitrogen fertilizers. It can bring savings for farmers and contribute to more sustainable farming practices.

Interaction with other organisms: Through the production of substances such as phytohormones, *Azotobacter chroococcum* can

influence the interactions between plants and other organisms in the soil, including insects and other microorganisms (Yingying et al, 2022).

This can contribute to the ecological balance of the agricultural system.

It is important to note that the exact impact of *Azotobacter chroococcum* may vary depending on specific soil conditions, agricultural practices, and other local factors. Specific farm-level experiments and observations can provide more detailed information about how this bacterium may benefit or influence the wheat crop.

Biofertilizers mainly include nitrogen-fixing microorganisms, phosphate solubilizers, and microorganisms that promote plant growth. Biofertilizers beneficial for crop production include *Azotobacter*, *Azospirillum*, blue-green algae, *Azolla*, phosphate-solubilizing microorganisms, mycorrhizae, and synorhizobe. (Hardika & Sarvjeet, 2020)

Organic fertilizers help improve the natural mechanisms of nutrient storage in the soil, both physically and biologically, and thus help manage the risk of overfertilization.

Organic fertilizers were the main focus for wheat production and were added to the soil in the form of biofertilizer, improved for nitrogen fixation, and compost to determine the best application of organic fertilizers for a higher harvest and better growth. (Peng et al., 2013)

Despite the high potential of microbial inoculants, their effective use is very low, estimated at about 2 % of their potential. The low adoption among farmers is largely attributed to their unpredictable response, low quality in terms of the total number of viable cells at the time of use, short storage time, and temperature sensitivity (Yadav & Chandra, 2014).

To ensure high viability of bacteria-based products, it is recommended to store them at a controlled temperature, away from the sun's rays and frost. It is important to avoid exposure to extreme temperatures, as this can affect the quality and efficacy of microbial inoculants.

Storage in optimal conditions, with a constant temperature and without large fluctuations, contributes to maintaining a high concentration of viable cells in the product.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The experiment took place in region of Crisana, Bihor County Romania in a village called Sacadat 22 km from Oradea. The soil where the experiment was carried out belongs to the category of luvisols.

Preparatory work before the sowing period we spread a natural fertilizer containing 8 tons of chicken manure per hectare. After that, as soon as possible not to waste in the atmosphere the NH_3 , we plough to a depth of 25 cm and after we closed the ploughing with a cultivator that worked the first 12-15 cm.

Sowing was carried out at the optimal date in 03.10.2023. The dose of Azotobacter was determined according to the sowing norm, the distance between the rows and the number of plants per square meter. The wheat seeds we used was Apilco and we sowed a number of 400 g/square meter. The experiment was conducted over an area of 6 hectares, divided into two types: 3 control hectares and 3 test hectares. On the 3 control hectares, only chicken manure was applied, at a rate of 8 tons per hectare.

On the 3 test hectares, in addition to the 8 tons of chicken manure, applications of the product Azotohelp were made in different quantities and stages:

1. 2.5 liters of Azotohelp was applied to the soil, incorporated before sowing.

2. The wheat seeds were treated with 1.5 liters of Azotohelp per ton of seeds. Since 210 kg of seeds were used per hectare, 0.32 liters of Azotohelp was applied for seed treatment.

3. 2 liters of Azotohelp were applied to the soil before sowing, and 0.5 liters of Azotohelp were applied to the vegetation at the appearance of the tiller.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on the tests conducted, we were able to draw some clear conclusions regarding the experiment we performed. Even in the early stages of wheat development, we noticed significant differences in the root structure between the wheat from the control fields and that from the test fields. In Figure 1, the differences between the roots of the control wheat and those treated with Azotohelp (*Azotobacter Chroococcum*) can be observed.

The roots of the wheat plants treated with *Azotobacter Chroococcum* are more vigorous and retain more soil around them, indicating the activity of microorganisms in the soil. In the control plots, the roots are less developed and retain less organic matter around them.

Figure 1. Difference in roots system

Visible differences in the color of wheat leaves in the test and control plots can be seen in Figure 2. On the right side of the image, where the wheat appears darker, denser and healthier, *Azotobacter Chroococcum* was used both before sowing and during the vegetation phase. On the left side of the image is the test area where only natural chicken manure was used.

Figure 2. Field picture between control and trial

In Figure 3, we observe the differences in wheat yield following the application of nitrogen-fixing

bacteria at different stages of crop development and in varying amounts. While the differences between applying Azotohelp before sowing, post-emergence of the crop, and as a seed treatment are not very large—only a 20 kg difference between

the two application rates—there is still a considerable yield difference when Azotohelp is applied both before sowing, sprayed on the soil, and during the vegetation phase (see Application rate 3).

Figure 3. Results after using *Azotobacter Chroococcum* in different concentrations

CONCLUSIONS

Following the tests carried out, we conclude with data from the field the percentage impact of *Azotobacter Chroococcum* in our wheat crop, the sustainability of its use and the yield it has given to our crop.

The differences in production obtained from the crosses made, we have been a clear picture, given by figures and expressed in percentages in terms of yield obtained from the use of the *Azotobacter* bacterium in the wheat crop in its own soil conditions, using nothing else but live bacteria and natural manure for fertilization.

With our test we wanted to show that good yields can be obtained with only the use of natural

inputs without pouring into the soil huge amounts of chemical fertilizers. Of course, using live bacterias is not an easy task, because of their needs for temperature and good soil conditions.

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RESEARCH ON THE EFFECTS OF DROUGHT ON RED CLOVER IN BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

*This research analyzes the impact of drought on red clover (*Trifolium pratense* L.) in Bihor County, in the context of variable climatic conditions from 2023-2024. Drought is a major threat to agriculture, affecting not only plant development, but also the quality and quantity of hay obtained.*

The study was conducted in several locations in Bihor County, where meteorological conditions, including precipitation, were monitored in correlation with red clover production. The obtained results indicate a significant decrease in yield, which underlines the vulnerability of this crop to water stress.

Keywords: red clover, drought, productivity, climate impact, agriculture, water stress.

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INTRODUCTION

Drought is a complex natural phenomenon characterized by a prolonged absence of precipitation, leading to a significant water deficit in the soil, hydrological resources, and atmosphere. Unlike other natural disasters such as floods or storms, drought develops gradually and progresses slowly, but its long-term effects can be devastating. This phenomenon is influenced by climatic and geographical factors as well as human activities, with its intensity and duration varying across regions.

The impact of drought is felt across multiple dimensions. In agriculture, it leads to a significant decline in production, affecting crops sensitive to water shortages and reducing the availability of animal feed. In ecosystems, drought disrupts the natural balance, diminishing biodiversity, increasing the risk of desertification, and intensifying the frequency of wildfires. On a social and economic level, drought generates financial losses, forces population migration from affected areas, and increases social tensions due to competition for limited water resources.

Drought is one of the most serious threats to agriculture globally, severely affecting

production of essential crops and food security. To soften the impact of drought, integrated measures are essential, such as improving water management infrastructure, adopting sustainable agricultural practices, and implementing policies to conserve natural resources. While drought is inevitable, its effects can be managed through careful planning and constant adaptation to changing conditions.

In Romania, drought has become an increasingly frequent phenomenon, with significant effects on agricultural systems, especially in regions that depend on natural water resources for irrigation. Bihor County, located in the western part of the country, faces pronounced climate variability, and the impact of drought on local agriculture requires special attention.

Bihor County is located within the historical region of Crişana, and borders Hungary to the west. It is an area of significant geographical diversity, cultural richness, and economic potential, serving as a key gateway between Romania and Western Europe. It covers an area of approximately 7,544 square kilometers, making it one of the larger counties in Romania. The landscape is diverse, ranging from the plains of the western part, suitable for agriculture, to the rolling hills and mountains in

the east, including the Apuseni Mountains. The Criș Rivers (Crișul Repede, Crișul Negru, and Crișul Alb) traverse the county, providing water resources and picturesque landscapes.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The aim of this paper is to evaluate the impact of drought on red clover productivity in Bihor county, analyzing both climatic factors and agronomic parameters that influence the development and yield of this crop. Through case studies and data analyses, the paper aims to identify the correlations between environmental conditions and red clover productivity, while also providing recommendations for more efficient management of water resources and improving the adaptability of crops to water stress conditions.

This research not only contributes to understanding the impact of climate change on agriculture in Bihor, but also to the development of viable strategies to ensure a sustainable and resilient agriculture in the face of climate challenges.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In 2024, the red clover crop in Romania was affected by the severe drought that negatively influenced agricultural production. Although red clover (*Trifolium pratense*) is a leguminous plant that can provide significant benefits, including soil improvement through nitrogen fixation, adverse climatic conditions have significantly reduced yields.

In general, red clover grows well in areas with an average annual rainfall of more than 600 mm, and its water requirements are very specific.

In 2024, however, many farmers reported that yields were well below this threshold due to a lack of adequate rainfall and extreme temperatures.

This situation was compounded by the fact that red clover is sensitive to both drought and excess water, making soil selection and water resource management crucial to crop success. Also, very high temperatures affected germination and vegetative growth, thus influencing the final result.

Figure 1 Temperature comparison Bihor county

Figure 2 Rainfall comparison Bihor county

In the summer of 2024, Bihor County was affected by high temperatures and intense drought, which led to significant agricultural damage. Maximum temperatures frequently exceeded 35°C during heatwave periods, and on some days even higher values were recorded, exacerbated by the lack of precipitation.

Comparing the years 2022, 2023 and 2024, Romania faces a very difficult agricultural situation due to severe drought affecting crops, including red clover. The year 2024 was forecast to be one of the driest on record, with a significant drop in production for many crops.

For red clover, severe drought led to a reduction in biomass and affected the overall development of the plant, leading to a decrease in yield. If in 2023 the production of red clover was relatively constant, in 2024 there is a considerable decrease in production due to the absence of precipitation and heat waves, which compromised the harvest potential.

Red clover needs an adequate amount of water to support its development, and drought can lead to the following negative effects:

1. Growth retardation – Water deficit reduces the growth rate of the plant and decreases the total biomass produced.

2. Decreased production of leaves and flowers – Water fluctuations negatively affect the formation of leaves and inflorescences, essential elements for use as fodder and for nitrogen fixation.

3. Reduction of nitrogen fixation – Red clover fixes atmospheric nitrogen through bacteria in the root nodules. In drought conditions, bacterial activity decreases, which affects the plant's ability to obtain nitrogen, thus reducing its nutritional potential.

4. Competition with other plants – Under severe drought conditions, red clover can become more vulnerable to competition from other species, including weeds, which may have a higher tolerance to water deficit.

This is the graph illustrating the production of red clover in Bihor county for the years 2022, 2023 and 2024, comparing production in drought conditions with normal production in 2022. We observe a significant reduction in production due to drought, from 11 t/ha in normal conditions to 5 t/ha in drought conditions, which represents a loss of about 50%.

Figure 3 Production of hay obtained in 3 years of vegetation

Table 1

The area declared at the Agency for Payments and Interventions in Agriculture in the years 2023-2024

Area cultivated with clover in the year 2023	Area cultivated with clover in the year 2024
3092,62 ha	2989,70 ha

CONCLUSIONS

The impact of drought on red clover crops in Romania is significant, affecting both the yield and the quality of the production. Adaptation to these climatic conditions becomes a necessity, and the implementation of

sustainable agricultural practices, together with the development of drought-resistant varieties and investments in agricultural infrastructure, can help reduce the negative effects of drought. Collaboration between researchers, farmers and decision-makers will be essential to develop

efficient and sustainable solutions for the future of Romanian agriculture.

In conclusion, 2024 was a challenging year for red clover growers in Romania, who faced extreme climatic conditions that directly impacted productivity.

The study highlights the need to implement adaptation measures, such as sustainable irrigation and varietal selection of clover, to increase resilience to adverse climatic conditions. This research contributes to the understanding of the impact of drought on agriculture in Bihor and offers practical suggestions for managing water resources in the future, considering the emerging challenges related to climate change. An effective solution to ameliorate the impact of drought on red clover is the development and use of cultivars red clover more resistant to drought conditions. These varieties are adapted to better conserve water and maximize production even under water stress conditions.

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CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE EVALUATION OF THE PRODUCTIVITY OF PERMANENT GRASSLANDS FROM THE MUNICIPALITY AREA OF HIDIȘELUL DE SUS (BIHOR COUNTY)

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This paper presents a case study on the evaluation of the productivity of permanent grasslands in the Hidișelul de Sus commune (Bihor County), based on a floristic survey. This study is important for the economic characterization, improvement, rational use, and enhancement of the nutritional value of these grasslands. The permanent grasslands in Hidișelul de Sus commune are quite varied, and the most representative types were studied, namely *Agrostis capillaris* - *Festuca rubra* and *Agrostis capillaris* - *Agropyron repens*. The meadows dominated by *Agrostis capillaris* and *Agropyron repens* exhibit the highest productivity, with a yield of 23.36 t/ha of green fodder and a stocking rate of 1.94 LU/ha. This is followed by the *Agrostis capillaris* - *Festuca rubra* meadows, with slightly lower yields of 18.87 t/ha of green fodder and a stocking rate of 1.57 LU/ha. The data provided by this study are useful for characterizing the pastoral potential of these grasslands in the context of improving and rationally utilizing the pastoral land.

Keywords: grasslands, green mass production, nutritional value, stocking rate, floristic survey

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INTRODUCTION

Taking into account the difficulty of determining the green mass production of pastures using the classical method, a new approach based on a floristic survey, with a percentage assessment of the species in the grass cover, has been proposed (Marușca, 2019). Currently, livestock farming systems based on the use of grasslands must meet growing feed demands. The forage production from these areas must align with the increasing requirements for meat and milk, as well as with the challenges posed by climate change (Marușca et al., 2014).

The grasslands under study are located in the Hidișelul de Sus commune, Bihor County. The permanent grasslands in the study area are predominantly composed of *Agrostis capillaris*, *Festuca rubra*, and *Agropyron repens*. The study area is part of the larger geomorphological unit: the Western Piedmont, Piatra Craiului district. Geologically, the

territory of Hidișelul de Sus commune lies on formations of Pleistocene age, overlaid by Quaternary deposits. The parent rocks that formed and shaped the soils in the hilly area are non-carbonate clays, carbonate clays, loams, marls, cemented sandstones (very weakly carbonated or non-carbonated), while in the micro-meadow areas, heterogeneous colluvial deposits are present (Berchez & Stanciu, 2021). The general capacity of the grasslands to support plant production is good. Physical characteristics include a high fine sand content of over 70%, and low silt and clay content. The air occupying the non-capillary pores, which are well-represented in relation to the capillary pores (the volume of capillary pores is directly proportional to the sand content), with very low specific heat and thermal conductivity, leads to rapid heating and cooling at the surface, with deeper horizons remaining cool.

The main soil type in the study area is eutricambosol.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the percentage assessment of species in the grass cover (AD – abundance-dominance), the Braun-Blanquet scale was used, which has the following values: +0.5%; 1-5.0%; 2-17.5%; 3-37.5%; 4-62.5%; 5-87.5% (Cristea et al., 2004).

Considering that there are significant differences between the abundance-dominance scores, with up to a 25% difference between scores 4 and 5, 3 and 4, and 20% between scores 2 and 3, a new formula was adopted to transform the AD intervals into percentage participation, taking into account the general frequency (K) of each species, as presented in the works by Marușca, 2019; Marușca et al., 2020; Pășcuț & Marușca, 2020; Marușca & Pășcuț, 2022.

Floristic relevés were carried out at the most representative points, with GPS coordinates, altitude, exposition, slope, landform, herbaceous vegetation cover, and woody vegetation cover provided for each relevé. The species are ordered in the table presenting the floristic composition for each type of pasture, starting with *Poaceae*, *Fabaceae*, and other families. In the study of the floristic composition of these grasslands, relevés with an area of 100 m² were used.

After transforming the phytocoenological scores into percentages, the forage quality index (F) and the useful phytomass index (M) (Păcurar & Rotar, 2014; Marușca, 2019; Marușca, 2021; Marușca et al., 2019; Marușca et al., 2020) are assigned to each species in the floristic relevé. The forage quality index (F) has the following values: F1-F3 (harmful species), F4-F9 (species with forage value). The values for the forage phytomass index (M) range from M1-M9 for species with useful phytomass, and M0 for species with F1-F3 values.

For the grasslands in the Hidișelul de Sus commune area, the grazing season lasts for 185 days. The botanical nomenclature used for the identified species follows the work of Sârbu et al. (2013).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study of permanent grasslands in the area of Hidișelul de Sus commune (Bihor County) highlights two main types of grasslands: *Agrostis capillaris*–*Festuca rubra* and *Agrostis capillaris*–*Agropyron repens*. This study was conducted in 2023, with a total of 15 relevés, 7 in *Agrostis capillaris*–*Festuca rubra* grasslands and 8 in *Agrostis capillaris*–*Agropyron repens* grasslands. The *Agrostis capillaris*–*Festuca rubra* grassland type is found on slopes with varying exposures (N, NE, S, SE, SW, E), at altitudes ranging from 210 to 290 m, and with slopes of 5-18 degrees (Table 1). The herbaceous vegetation corresponding to this type of grassland has a high cover (92-100%) and is dominated by *Agrostis capillaris* (44.64%) and to a lesser extent by *Festuca rubra* (13.93%).

In the *Poaceae* family, species present in these grasslands include *Lolium perenne*, *Phleum pratense*, *Festuca pratensis*, *Dactylis glomerata*, *Festuca arundinacea*, *Arrhenatherum elatius*, *Poa pratensis*, *Cynosurus cristatus*, *Agropyron repens*, *Holcus lanatus*, *Anthoxanthum odoratum*, *Festuca rupicola*, *Festuca valesiaca*, all of which have high forage quality, as well as *Botriochloa ischaemum*, *Calamagrostis epigejos*, and *Setaria pumila*, which have no forage value.

The *Fabaceae* family is represented by *Trifolium repens*, *Trifolium campestre*, *Trifolium pratense*, *Trifolium medium*, *Trifolium arvense*, and *Lotus corniculatus*, which have good forage value but low percentage coverage (2%). Species with good forage quality and consistency in these grasslands include *Achillea millefolium*, *Agrimonia eupatoria*, *Cichorium intybus*, *Fragaria vesca*, *Hieracium pilosella*, *Pimpinella saxifraga*, and *Plantago lanceolata*. However, their coverage in these grasslands is low (3.43%). Toxic and harmful species for livestock are also present in these grasslands, such as *Eryngium campestre*, *Euphorbia cyparissias*, *Carduus acanthoides*, *Tanacetum vulgare*, *Rumex conglomeratus*, and *Sambucus ebulus*.

Table 1

Floristic composition of the *Agrostis capillaris*-*Festuca rubra* grasslands

No. relevées	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	K	Participation P (%)	Indices		
Altitude (m.s.m.)	210	215	290	280	210	220	260					
Exposition	NE	N, NE	NE	SV	E-SE	E	S					
Slope (°)	5-8	15-18	10-12	8-10	8-10	8-10	10-15					
Area (m ²)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100					
GPS coordonates	Lat. N	46.94085	46.92604	46.91787	46.94177	46.94718	46.97797	46.93435				
	Long. E	22.00883	22.05477	22.04120	22.06661	22.03665	22.05922	22.05258				
General coverage (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100					
Grass vegetation cover (%)	94	97	95	92	98	99	100					
Woody vegetation cover (%)	27	25	10	4	3	9	2					
Pastoral value (VP)	Very Good	Good										
Molehills (%)	6	-	5	8	2	1	-			F	M	
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Poaceae												
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	3	4	3	3	3	4	3	V	50	7	5	
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	V	11.3	7	6	
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	+	1	+	1	+	+	+	V	2.8	5	3	
<i>Cynosurus cristatus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	7	4	
<i>Festuca arundinacea</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	8	9	
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	1	+	1	+	+	+	+	V	2.8	9	8	
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	8	6	
<i>Botriochloa ischaemum</i>	·	+	+	+	·	+	2	IV	6.3	3	0	
<i>Festuca valesiaca</i>	·	+	+	1	1	·	+	IV	2	5	3	
<i>Agropyron repens</i>	+	·	+	·	·	+	·	III	0.3	6	7	
<i>Calamagrostis epigejos</i>	+	1	+	·	·	·	·	III	1.4	3	0	
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	+	·	+	·	·	+	+	III	0.3	6	2	
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	·	·	+	·	+	·	·	III	0.3	9	8	
<i>Arrhenatherum elatius</i>	·	·	+	·	+	·	·	II	0.2	8	8	
<i>Brachypodium pinnatum</i>	·	·	+	·	+	·	·	II	0.2	5	7	
<i>Danthonia decumbens</i>	·	·	·	+	+	·	·	II	0.2	4	3	
<i>Festuca rupicola</i>	·	·	·	1	+	·	·	II	0.8	5	5	
<i>Holcus lanatus</i>	·	·	+	·	·	+	·	II	0.2	6	6	
<i>Setaria pumila</i>	·	·	+	+	·	·	·	II	0.2	3	0	
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	·	·	·	·	·	+	·	I	0.1	9	8	
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	·	·	·	·	·	+	·	I	0.1	9	8	
Fabaceae												
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	8	5	
<i>Trifolium campestre</i>	+	+	+	+	·	+	+	V	0.5	7	2	
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	8	6	
<i>Dorycnium pentaphyllum</i>	·	·	+	+	+	+	1	IV	2	3	0	
<i>Ononis spinosa</i>	+	·	+	+	+	+	·	IV	0.4	3	0	
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	+	+	·	+	+	·	·	III	0.3	8	7	
<i>Trifolium medium</i>	+	+	+	·	·	·	·	III	0.3	6	4	
<i>Trifolium arvense</i>	·	·	·	+	·	·	·	I	0.1	4	2	
Other families												
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	6	4	
<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	3	0	
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	5	6	
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	+	+	+	·	+	+	+	V	0.5	5	1	
<i>Hieracium pilosella</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	4	1	
<i>Pimpinella saxifraga</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	5	3	
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	6	1	
<i>Thymus glabrescens</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	3	0	
<i>Bellis perennis</i>	+	+	+	·	·	+	+	IV	0.4	5	1	
<i>Daucus carota</i>	·	+	+	·	+	+	+	IV	0.4	6	5	
<i>Juncus effusus</i>	1	+	·	+	1	1	·	IV	2	3	0	
<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	+	·	+	+	+	·	+	IV	0.4	5	2	
<i>Ranunculus polyanthemos</i>	+	+	·	·	+	+	+	IV	0.4	4	4	
<i>Xeranthemum cylindraceum</i>	·	·	·	1	+	+	+	IV	2	3	0	
<i>Carex hirta</i>	+	+	·	·	·	+	·	III	0.3	3	0	
<i>Carlina vulgaris</i>	·	·	+	+	+	·	+	III	0.3	3	0	
<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	+	+	·	·	·	+	·	III	0.3	3	0	
<i>Galium verum</i>	+	·	+	+	+	·	·	III	0.3	5	4	
<i>Geranium pusillum</i>	·	·	+	·	+	+	·	III	0.3	3	0	
<i>Hypochaeris radicata</i>	+	·	+	·	+	·	·	III	0.3	3	0	
<i>Juncus tenuis</i>	+	·	·	+	+	·	·	III	0.3	3	0	
<i>Leontodon autumnalis</i>	·	·	·	·	+	+	·	III	0.3	5	3	
<i>Urtica dioica</i>	+	·	+	·	·	+	·	III	0.3	5	7	

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
<i>Verbena officinalis</i>	.	.	.	+	+	+	.	III	0.3	4	4
<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	.	.	+	.	.	+	.	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Centaurium erythraea</i>	+	.	.	+	.	.	.	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Dipsacus laciniatus</i>	+	+	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Erigeron canadensis</i>	+	+	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Filago vulgaris</i>	.	.	+	.	+	.	.	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Filipendula vulgaris</i>	.	.	+	.	.	+	.	II	0.2	5	4
<i>Leontodon hispidus</i>	+	+	II	0.2	5	3
<i>Prunella vulgaris</i>	+	.	+	II	0.2	4	2
<i>Teucrium chamedrys</i>	+	.	+	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Centaurea phrygia</i>	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Cruciata glabra</i>	+	.	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Erodium cicutarium</i>	.	.	+	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Juncus inflexus</i>	+	.	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i>	+	.	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Mentha longifolia</i>	+	I	0.1	4	6
<i>Polygala vulgaris</i>	+	.	.	I	0.1	4	1
<i>Sanguisorba minor</i>	.	.	+	I	0.1	6	3
<i>Scabiosa ochroleuca</i>	.	.	+	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Viola tricolor</i>	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	I	0.1	3	0
Shrubs, subshrubs and invasive young trees											
<i>Cornus sanguinea</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	.	V	0.5	3	0
<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	3	0
<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	1	2	1	+	+	1	+	V	9	3	0
<i>Rosa canina</i>	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	2.8	3	0
<i>Rubus sulcatus</i>	1	1	+	+	+	+	+	V	2.8	3	0
<i>Populus tremula</i>	1	1	+	+	.	+	.	IV	2	3	0
<i>Carpinus betulus</i>	1	1	+	+	.	.	.	III	1.4	3	0
<i>Ligustrum vulgare</i>	+	.	+	.	.	+	.	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Pyrus pyraeaster</i>	+	+	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	.	.	+	+	+	+	.	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Cornus mas</i>	+	.	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Euonymus europaeus</i>	.	.	+	I	0.1	3	0
<i>Malus sylvestris</i>	.	+	I	0.1	3	0
Toxic and harmful plants											
<i>Carduus acanthoides</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	2	0
<i>Eryngium campestre</i>	1	1	1	+	1	1	1	V	2.8	3	0
<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i>	1	+	1	+	1	+	1	V	2.8	1	0
<i>Tanacetum vulgare</i>	.	.	+	.	.	+	.	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Rumex conglomeratus</i>	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	I	0.1	2	0
<i>Sambucus ebulus</i>	.	.	+	I	0.1	3	0

The localities and date where the relevées were carried out: 1, 5 - Hidişelul de Jos (15.08.2023); 2, 7 - Hidişelul de Sus (17.08.2023); 3 - Mierlău (20.08.2023); 4,6 - Sintelec (18.08.2023);
Where: F – fodder quality indices; M – production indices; K – constancy; AD values (Abundance-Dominance): +0.5%; 1-5.0%; 2-17.5%; 3-37.5%; 4-62.5%; 5-87.5%.

In these grasslands, some woody species, including shrubs, saplings, and invasive tree seedlings (13.13%), also penetrate, with the most representative being *Prunus. spinosa*,

Rubus sulcatus, *Rosa canina*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Cornus sanguinea*, *Populus tremula*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Pyrus pyraeaster*, *Robinia pseudoacacia*. (figure 1).

a.

b.

Figure 1 *Agrostis capillaris-Festuca rubra* grasslands, with woody shrubby vegetation (a – Hidişelul de Jos, relevée No. 1, b – Hidişelul de Sus, relevée No. 2)

The *Agrostis capillaris* and *Agropyron repens* grasslands were identified in the area of Hidişelul de Sus commune on slopes with different exposures (N, NE, S, SW), at altitudes ranging from 155 to 225 m on gently sloping terrain (0-8 degrees) (Table 2). The herbaceous vegetation has high cover (97-100%), with the dominant species being *Agrostis capillaris* (46.86%), followed by *Agropyron repens* (25%).

Among the species from the Poaceae family with good nutritional value found in this type of grassland, we mention *Festuca pratensis*, *Holcus lanatus*, *Phleum pratense*, *Anthoxanthum odoratum*, *Poa pratensis*, *Arrhenatherum elatius*, *Cynosurus cristatus*, *Festuca arundinacea*, *Lolium perenne*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Dactylis glomerata*, and *Festuca rubra*, which have a low participation percentage (9.93%).

From the Fabaceae family, the following species are present: *Trifolium repens*, *Trifolium campestre*, *Trifolium pratense*, *Lotus corniculatus*, *Ononis spinosa*, *Trifolium arvense*, *Galega officinalis*, *Vicia cracca*, and *Medicago lupulina*, with a total participation percentage of 3%, which is insignificant for improving the forage quality of these grasslands. Among the species from other families that have high presence and quality indices, *Achillea millefolium*, *Cichorium intybus*, *Plantago lanceolata*, *Potentilla erecta*, *Pimpinella saxifraga*, and *Daucus carota* stand out.

The woody shrubs and invasive tree saplings that penetrate this type of grassland are represented by *Prunus spinosa*, *Rosa canina*, *Rubus sulcatus*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Rubus caesius*, *Cornus sanguinea*, *Populus tremula*, *Carpinus betulus*, and *Robinia pseudoacacia*.

Table 2

Floristic composition of the *Agrostis capillaris*-*Agropyron repens* grasslands

No. relevées	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	K	Participati		Indices	
										on P (%)		F	M
Altitude (m.s.m.)	170	185	180	225	210	180	175	155					
Exposition	-	N-NE	-	S-SV	S	-	-	-					
Slope (°)	-	3-5	-	5-8	3-5	-	-	-					
Area (m ²)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100					
GPS Lat. N	46.95031	46.93861	46.97600	46.93228	46.93143	46.90728	46.89725	46.87119					
GPS Long. E	22.01465	22.03069	22.06395	22.05180	22.04869	21.98953	21.98760	21.95356					
General coverage (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100					
Grass vegetation cover (%)	99	98	99	99	98	97	97	100					
Woody vegetation cover (%)	2	7	2	1	7	3	3	8					
Pastoral value (VP)	Very Good												
Molehills (%)	1	2	1	1	2	3	3	-					
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Poaceae													
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	3	3	3	4	4	3	3	4	V	50	7	5	
<i>Agropyron repens</i>	2	3	2	2	2	3	3	2	V	27.5	6	7	
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	2.8	5	3	
<i>Cynosurus cristatus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	7	4	
<i>Festuca arundinacea</i>	1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	2.8	8	9	
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	1	+	1	+	+	1	+	+	V	2.8	9	8	
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	+	+	+	.	+	+	1	.	IV	2	9	8	
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	.	+	1	+	+	.	.	+	IV	2	9	8	
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	.	+	1	.	+	+	+	.	IV	2	9	8	
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	.	+	+	+	+	.	.	+	IV	0.4	8	6	
<i>Arrhenatherum elatius</i>	.	+	1	.	.	+	+	.	III	0.3	8	8	
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	1	.	.	+	+	.	.	+	III	1.4	6	2	
<i>Holcus lanatus</i>	+	.	.	.	+	.	+	+	III	0.3	6	6	
<i>Botriochloa ischaemum</i>	.	.	.	+	+	.	.	+	II	0.2	3	0	
<i>Calamagrostis epigejos</i>	.	+	.	.	.	+	+	.	II	0.2	3	0	
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	+	+	.	+	II	0.2	7	6	
<i>Setaria pumila</i>	.	+	+	II	0.2	3	0	
Fabaceae													
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	8	6	
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	+	+	+	+	.	+	+	+	V	0.5	8	7	
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	V	2.8	8	5	
<i>Galega officinalis</i>	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	.	II	0.2	3	0	
<i>Medicago lupulina</i>	+	+	.	.	II	0.2	8	3	
<i>Ononis spinosa</i>	.	.	+	+	.	.	.	+	II	0.2	3	0	
<i>Trifolium arvense</i>	.	+	+	.	+	.	.	.	II	0.2	4	2	

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
<i>Trifolium campestre</i>	+	.	.	+	.	.	.	+	II	0.2	7	2
<i>Vicia cracca</i>	.	.	.	+	.	+	+	.	II	0.2	7	6
Other families												
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	6	4
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	+	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	V	2.8	5	6
<i>Daucus carota</i>	.	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	6	5
<i>Pimpinella saxifraga</i>	+	+	+	+	.	+	+	+	V	0.5	5	3
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	+	.	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	6	1
<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	+	.	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	5	2
<i>Ranunculus polyanthemos</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	4	4
<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>	.	.	+	+	.	+	+	+	IV	0.4	3	0
<i>Bellis perennis</i>	+	.	+	+	+	.	.	+	IV	0.4	5	1
<i>Carex hirta</i>	1	.	.	+	+	+	+	+	IV	2	3	0
<i>Centaurea phrygia</i>	+	+	.	.	.	+	+	.	IV	0.4	3	0
<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	+	+	.	+	.	+	.	+	IV	0.4	3	0
<i>Filipendula vulgaris</i>	.	+	+	+	.	+	+	+	IV	0.4	5	4
<i>Galium verum</i>	+	+	+	.	+	+	+	.	IV	0.4	5	4
<i>Urtica dioica</i>	+	+	.	+	+	.	+	+	IV	0.4	5	7
<i>Xeranthemum cylindraceum</i>	.	+	.	+	+	.	+	+	IV	0.4	3	0
<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	.	+	.	+	+	.	.	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Cruciata glabra</i>	+	+	.	.	.	+	+	.	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Dipsacus laciniatus</i>	+	+	.	.	+	+	.	.	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Leontodon hispidus</i>	.	.	+	+	+	.	.	+	III	0.3	5	3
<i>Prunella vulgaris</i>	+	.	.	+	.	.	+	+	III	0.3	4	2
<i>Erigeron canadensis</i>	+	+	.	.	.	+	.	.	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	.	.	+	+	.	.	.	+	II	0.2	5	1
<i>Campanula glomerata</i>	.	+	+	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Carlina vulgaris</i>	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	+	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Verbena officinalis</i>	.	.	.	+	+	.	.	+	II	0.2	4	4
<i>Carum carvi</i>	.	+	I	0.1	6	3
<i>Cirsium canum</i>	.	1	I	0.5	3	0
<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i>	.	+	I	0.1	5	5
<i>Mentha longifolia</i>	.	+	I	0.1	4	6
Shrubs, subshrubs and invasive young trees												
<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	3	0
<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	+	1	+	+	+	+	+	1	V	2.8	3	0
<i>Rosa canina</i>	.	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	3	0
<i>Rubus sulcatus</i>	+	.	+	.	+	+	+	.	IV	0.4	3	0
<i>Populus tremula</i>	.	+	.	.	.	+	+	+	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Carpinus betulus</i>	.	+	+	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	.	+	.	+	1	.	.	.	II	0.8	3	0
<i>Rubus caesius</i>	.	+	+	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Cornus sanguinea</i>	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	+	II	0.2	3	0
Toxic and harmful plants												
<i>Carduus acanthoides</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	.	+	V	0.5	2	0
<i>Eryngium campestre</i>	1	.	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	2.8	3	0
<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i>	+	.	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5	1	0
<i>Artemisia absinthium</i>	.	+	.	.	+	+	+	.	III	0.3	3	0
<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	+	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Tanacetum vulgare</i>	.	+	.	.	+	.	+	.	II	0.2	3	0
<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	.	+	.	.	+	.	.	.	II	0.2	2	0

The localities and date where the relevées were carried out: 1 - Hidişelul de Jos (15.08.2023); 2, 4, 5 – Hidişelul de Sus (17.08.2023); 3 - Sintelec (18.08.2023); 6, 7, 8 - Mierlău (20.08.2023).

Where: F – fodder quality indices; M – production indices; K – constancy; AD values (Abundance-Dominance): +0.5%; 1-5.0%; 2-17.5%; 3-37.5%; 4-62.5%; 5-87.5%.

In these grasslands, a few toxic and harmful species for livestock are also present, namely: *Eryngium campestre* and *Euphorbia*

cyparissias., *Carduus acanthoides*, *Xanthium strumarium*, *Cirsium arvense*, *Artemisia absinthium*, *Tanacetum vulgare* (figure 2).

a.

b.

Figure 2 *Agrostis capillaris*-*Agropyron repens* grasslands with *Eryngium campestre* and *Euphorbia cyparissias* (a. - Hidişelul de Jos, relevée No. 1; b. - Sîntelec, relevée No. 3)

As a result of the calculations performed at the pasture type level, for the most widespread grasslands in the Hidişelul de Sus commune area, it was found that the *Agrostis capillaris* and *Festuca rubra* grasslands have a pastoral value (PV) of 86.64 (very good), with a green fodder biomass (GFB) production of 18.87 t/ha, supporting a

stocking rate of 1.57 LU/ha (Table 3). The most productive grasslands in the studied area are those of *Agrostis capillaris* and *Agropyron repens*, with an excellent pastoral value (PV) of 80.33, a very good green fodder biomass (GFB) production of 23.36 t/ha, and a stocking rate of 1.94 LU/ha.

Table 3

Productivity of grasslands identified in the Municipality area of Hidişelul de Sus

Grassland type	Pastoral value (VP)	Useful phytomass index (IM)	Green mass production (MV) (t/ha)	Cargo with animals (UVM/ha)
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i> - <i>Festuca rubra</i>	86.64 (Very Good)	6.29	18.87 (Good-Very Good)	1.57
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i> - <i>Agropyron repens</i>	80.33 (Very Good)	7.30	23.36 (Very Good)	1.94

CONCLUSIONS

The permanent grasslands in the area of Hidişelul de Sus commune have low agro-productive variability, with a mesophilous, micro-mesothermal, and acid-neutrophilous vegetation.

The most productive grasslands are those of *Agrostis capillaris* and *Agropyron repens*, with a very good pastoral value (PV), very good green biomass production per hectare, and an optimal stocking rate of 1.94 LU/ha for 185 grazing days. Also, the *Agrostis capillaris* and *Festuca rubra* grasslands have very good productivity, very good pastoral value (PV), and very good green biomass (GB) production, which allow a stocking rate of 1.57 LU/ha.

To maintain the high productivity of these grasslands in the future, it is necessary to apply mandatory improvement works, such as clearing shrub vegetation and invasive tree saplings, destroying and leveling ant hills, controlling harmful and toxic plants, and

fertilizing with organic and chemical fertilizers.

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THE CLIMATIC ASPECTS IN THE NORTH OF THE CRAIULUI FOREST MOUNTAINS AND THE ASSESSMENT OF THEIR CONSEQUENCES ON SOIL CHARACTERISTICS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

The Pădurea Craiului Mountains are a distinct branch of the Apuseni Mountains, being located in the northwestern part of this mountain massif. They are bordered by the Beiușului Depression, the Vad-Borod Depression and the Western Hills, which separate them from the main body of the Apuseni. The Pădurea Craiului Mountains represent the west part of the Western Carpathians and reach the maximum altitude of 1024 m at the top of Hodrâncușa, while the highest peak of the Apuseni is represented by the peak of Bihor, which reaches 1849 m.

The thermal changes and the level of precipitation have a particularly important role in influencing soil characteristics. During the years 2019, 2020 and 2021 we carried out a detailed analysis of the evolution of the temperature and the level of precipitation in The Pădurea Craiului Mountains area. The processed data were provided by the Banat-Crișana Regional Meteorological Center in Timișoara, the main source being the meteorological station in Borod, the closest to the studied area.

The change of temperatures and amounts of precipitation in a short period of time, in a certain region, and their impact on the basic characteristics of the soil are the subjects addressed in this study. We will not neglect the tourism-climatic potential of the area, including the underground with remarkable properties caused by climatic conditions, which transform The Pădurea Craiului Mountains into a significant tourist destination.

Keywords: The Pădurea Craiului Mountains, climate, forest, soil, rainfall

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INTRODUCTION

The Pădurea Craiului Mountains range is a distinct branch of the Apuseni Mountains, located in the northwestern part of this mountain massif. Surrounded by the Beiușului Depression, the Vad-Borod Depression and the Western Hills, being separated from the main body of the Apuseni. Characterized as the western part of the Western Carpathians, these mountains reach the maximum altitude of 1024 m at the top of Hodrâncușa, while the highest height of the Apuseni is the peak of Bihor, which reaches 1849 m. From an administrative point of view, this area is located in Bihor County, covering approximately 1150 square km, which represents approximately 15% of the total area of the county.

The Pădurea Craiului Mountains, together with the Plopiș, Meseș, Zărand and Codru-Moma Mountains, represent the western ends of the Apuseni Mountains, proposed by T. Rusu to be included in the so-called Peninsular Apuseni group (Ionel Novac, 2006), due to their genesis and evolution similar. The Apuseni

Mountains, in turn, are a branch of the Western Carpathians. The name Carpathians comes from the Illyrian-Thracian word "karpate", which refers to the rocky features of the mountain regions. Also, this toponym is related to the population of free Dacians - the Carpi, who lived outside the territories conquered by the Romans. The term "Carpathians" was first recorded by Ptolemy, and in the 16th century it was taken over by Mercator under the name Carpathus Mons. The Pădurea Craiului mountains are delimited by the Crișul Repede and Crișul Negru rivers, being surrounded by the Vlădeasa and Bihor massifs, and extend in the north to the Oradea-Bratca depression area, and in the south they are bordered by the Beiuș Depression. To the west, it comes into contact with the Tășadului Hills. This mountain unit is characterized by a pronounced relief, mostly composed of Mesozoic limestones, with peaks rarely exceeding 1000 meters, the highest being Hodrângușa (1027 m), descending to the west and south to approximately 400 meters.

The boundaries of The Pădurea Craiului Mountains are clearly defined, with certain

geographical elements associated with each other, with the northern limit being marked by the Vad-Borod Depression, and to the south they extend to the Tășadului, Holodului and Beiuș Depressions. In the eastern part, they overlap tectonically with Valea Iadei through the Remeți graben. These delimitations were established by Teodor Rusu and were accepted by B. Onac in 2002 and I. Novac in 2006.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The unique character of these mountains in the Western Carpathian region is due to the great diversity of geological formations: crystalline rocks such as schists with granite, limestones from the Mesozoic, conglomerates and sandstones from the Triassic and Permian, andesites and pyroclastites from the Neogene, and at their edges there are even layers sedimentation from the Miocene. This peculiarity of the relief led to the appearance of the karst phenomenon, which is a distinctive feature of this region. The sinking process of the Badenian period led to the formation of some high relief forms, mainly due to the depressions in the Crișului Repede area. Sharp fragmentation and vertical erosion have resulted in average elevations of about 700-800 meters, giving them the appearance of higher hills, with higher elevations only in certain places (1027 m). The transition to the lower areas is made through Piedmont glaciations and Piedmont terraces according to the studies of Grigor P. Pop from 2000. The region is presented in the form of a horst, with 83% of the surface covered by Mesozoic limestones, the rest being made up of crystalline schists, subhercynian magmatites, Permian sandstones and conglomerates. Exokarst features include sinkholes and depressions, as well as karst plateaus and outcrops. The climate and the composition of the rocks contributed to the formation of deposits of bauxite, refractory clay and raw materials for the production of binders. The relief is characterized by fragmented platforms in peaks and isolated massifs in the form of apples. In the western part of the region, Valea Iadului is distinguished by a narrow and high summit, with peaks such as Măgura Beiușele (1004 m), Hodrângușa (1027 m) and Dealul Boții (968 m). In the center of the massif there is an extensive, strongly fragmented surface with smaller hills and peaks, such as Culmea Ponorășului (858 – 825 m), Rujet Hills (844 m), Cărmăzan (851 m), Roșiorului (750 m) and Crucii Hill (722 m).

Below these formations is the Zece Hotare plateau, located at an altitude of 600-700 meters, with interfluves that descend to Bucuroaia, Vârciorog, Crișul Repede and Crișul Negru, up to approximately 500-400 meters. On the calcareous rocks of the karst plateaus Damiș, Zece Hotare, Vârciorog, a complex karst relief was formed, with uvaes, sinkholes, karst depressions, caves and avens. In this region, 680 caves have been identified, with a total length of over 105 km, among which the following caves stand out: Vântului, Vadu Crișului and Meziad.

The present study stops with the analysis in the north of the Pădurea Craiului Mountains, it starts from the area of the Zece Hotare plateau, continues with Roșiorului hills, Dâmbul Nuchii and Oarzăna hills up to the area of the village of Călățea, an area where the climate and the composition of the rocks contributed to the formation of clay deposits (Dealul Cărmăzan) and of bauxite in the area of the villages of Zece Hotare, Tomnatic and Călățea.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Regarding the climatic aspects, the montan area of the Pădurea Craiului falls under the moderate climate conditions of Romania, with a variety of natural landscapes that change during the seasons, favorably influencing the tourism industry. The combination of the country's temperate-oceanic and continental climates helps moderate the negative aspects associated with these two types of climate (such as dense fog and heavy rains for the oceanic climate, and wide temperature variations and cold waves for the continental climate). Also, the specific climate of these lower mountains, having altitudes below 1000 meters, does not allow a clear differentiation of climatic zones as in the case of higher mountains.

The climate in the Pădurea Craiului Mountains region is influenced by geographical factors such as relief and latitude, causing significant variations in temperature and precipitation. The average annual temperature is between 9 and 11°C, falling within the average annual temperatures of Romania, which vary from 8.5-9°C in the south to 11°C in the northern part of our country, and each increase of 1000 meters in altitude brings a decrease of about 6 degrees Celsius. The average temperature of the three years (2019, 2020 and 2021), in the studied area, is 10.63°C. The average annual rainfall decreases

progressively from west to east, reflecting the diminishing oceanic and Mediterranean influences. The average annual rainfall in Romania is 637 mm, with higher values in the mountainous areas (1,000 - 1,400 mm/year) and lower in the east, below 500 mm/year in Bărăgan and below 400 mm/year in Dobrogea and the Danube Delta. In the studied area located in the Pădurea Craiului Mountains, the average precipitation during the analyzed period (2019, 2020 and 2021) was 709.3

mm/year. The meteorological data for the years 2019, 2020 and 2021, in the area of interest, come from the Banat-Crișana Regional Meteorological Center in Timișoara, which uses the information collected from the Meteorological Station in Borod, the closest to the analyzed area, because the weather station in Zece Hotare is no longer operational.

Figure 1. **Temperature evolution, annual averages (2019, 2020, 2021), The Pădurea Craiului Mountains** (source: Banat-Crișana Regional Meteorological Center)

Figure 2. **Precipitation evolution, annual averages (2019, 2020, 2021), The Pădurea Craiului Mountains** (source: Banat-Crișana Regional Meteorological Center)

During the three years analyzed, there was a decrease in the average annual temperature by 1.1 degrees Celsius. Thus, in 2019, the average annual temperature was 11.4 degrees Celsius, in 2020 it dropped to 10.6 degrees Celsius, and in 2021 it reached the value of 9.9 degrees Celsius. This represents a 15% decrease in temperature over the three years.

Regarding the amount of precipitation, it is noted that in 2019 it was 725.7 liters/m², in 2020 it decreased to 688.2 liters/m², and in 2021 there was an increase to 714 liters/m². The analysis shows that both temperature and precipitation fall within the annual averages, with no significant differences. This situation, together with the favorable soil factors and the

absence of pollution in the studied area, contributes to a harmonious growth of plants from the spontaneous flora, which is reflected in the superior quality of the products compared to other regions.

The analyzes carried out on the soil at OSPA Bihor, in three different points both in terms of altitude and area, revealed the fact that the soil has a fine texture, having in its composition both medium clay, loamy clay and clay-dusty soil. For soil analyses, three agro-chemical samples were collected, at a depth of 5-25 cm. The first point for soil analysis was installed at the foot of Roșiorului Hill, in the area called Bradea by the locals, the second point for analysis was established at the point called Drumul Aștilenilor located at the foot of Oarzăna Hill and the third point was installed at

Pancului bridge at the confluence Cornetu hill with Mniera stream.

Table 1

The synthetic situation of the agrochemical samples (analyses carried out by OSPA Bihor)

The studied territory: village TOMNATIC and village CĂLĂȚEA

Crt.no.	Name parcel of fertilization	Samples agrochemical on the plan		pH (H ₂ O)	Al	Ah	SB	V%	H%	IN	Azote total %	P _{Al}	K _{Al}	Fixed rezidue	Other assays								
		Agroc hemical samples	Depth cm.												ml. la 100 g. sol			Nitrates		Texture			
															N-NO ₃	N-NH ₄	Ng	Nfin	Praf	Arg.			
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21			
1	Bradea	1	5 – 25	5,25	0,6	8,8	6,0	40,5	9,57	3,9	0,479	29	200	0,017	50,8	5	29,6	24,1	24,2	22,1			
	The Aștîlenilor Road	2	5 – 25	8,15	-	-	-	-	2,49	-	0,125	6	130	0,044	14,6	8,5	10,3	10,0	39,5	40,2			
	The Pancului Bridge	3	5 – 25	7,9	-	-	-	-	6,88	-	0,344	9	360	20,030	14,1	14,1	5,7	18,2	21,0	55,1			

Schița structurală a Munților Pădurea Craiului (după harta geologică 1:200.000, foaia Șimleul Silvaniei, cu completări după date inedite ale lui D. PATRULIUS, din V. IANOVICI et al., 1976).
 Autohtonul de Bihor:
 1- formațiuni sedimentare permo-mezozoice;
 2- formațiuni cristaline.
 Sistemul Pânzelor de Codru:
 3- Pânza de Văleni;
 4- Pânza de Finiș;
 5- Pânza de Arieșeni.
 Formațiuni post-tectonice:
 6- depozite neocretacee (facies de Gosau);
 7- magmatite subhercinice și laramice;
 8- depozite neogene;
 9- limita unităților din cadrul Autohtonului.

Fig. 3 Structural sketch of the Pădurea Craiului Mountains (Source: I Orășanu, 2016)

CONCLUSIONS

We have four soil categories in the studied area, primarily due to pedogenetic conditions. The first category of soils is intrazonal or lithomorph soils. The second category of soils is represented by luvisols, usually superimposed on a layer of limestone and dolomites, from the Middle and Upper Jurassic, together with Cretaceous formations (limestone, bauxite) belonging to the Bihor Unit. The third category of soils is represented by cambisols. The last category of soils is represented by undeveloped soils, lithosols. The mining operations continued by the massive deforestation led to the change of the structure of the relief, through the appearance of anthropic forms of relief. The traces left by the older bauxite mining and the new clay mining are known (the latter led to the change of the structure of an important part of the Carmăzan hill). Through the washing of the soil left by the

Following the soil analyses, we have the following results: Bradea: medium texture - medium clay (LL); Aștîlenilor Road: fine texture - clay-dusty loam (TP); Pancului bridge: fine texture: - loamy clay (AL). According to Iancu Orăseanu, in the Karst Hydrogeology of the Apuseni Mountains, the researched area is one with Permo-Mesozoic sedimentary formations, bordered by the Mniera valley fault and the Carmăzan horst.

exploitations by the meteoric waters, a landscape is created with flats, even desert, and the penetration of the infiltration water is blocked underground (NOVAC, I, 2006). We can conclude that in the analyzed area the soil is the result of the synergistic evolution of the rocks in the substrate, of the vegetation, of the water but also of the superficial deposits under the particular influence of the topoclimates and the climate in general. These are a geographical symbiosis of the links between the autrophic components with the biotic and abiotic.

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MATHEMATICAL MODELS IN OPTIMIZING AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This paper refers to the application of the simplex method in agriculture, specifically in optimizing agricultural resources. In the context of a farm, there are several resources (budget, water, land, time) available that need to be managed to maximize profit. The goal is to use the simplex method to allocate resources optimally to maximize profit. Mathematics provides essential tools for optimizing agricultural processes. The correct application of models can help farmers make informed decisions, saving resources and maximizing profits.

Keywords: (max. 5) simplex method, agriculture, optimization

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Table 1

INTRODUCTION

The importance of mathematics in agriculture in this paper is:

1. Use of models for production forecasting,
2. Cost-benefit analysis for crops,
3. Irrigation planning and resource management.

The case study is optimizing crop rotation. We analyze the problem: a farmer has 10 hectares of land on which he wants to grow wheat, corn and soybeans. The available resources are:

- Budget: 20000 RON,
- Water for irrigation: 50000 liters,
- Available working time: 1000 hours,

We have four types of resources that are used to grow two types of agricultural products: corn and wheat. Each crop requires a specific amount of resources (budget, water, land, and time), and the objective is to maximize the farmer's profit.

The problem statement is presented above and follows the Table 1 table containing the required resources and profit per hectare.

Required resources and profit per hectare

Crop	Cost per hectare (RON)	Water required per hectare (liters)	Working time per hectare (hours)	Profit per hectare (RON)
Grow	2000	4000	120	3000
Corn	2500	5000	150	4000
Soybeans	1800	3000	100	2500

Solving the problem leads to the use of the simplex method or dedicated software (ex. Excel Solver, MATLAB, Python). The simplex method is a technique used in linear optimization to solve maximization or minimization problems, under linear constraints. In the case presented, we want to maximize profit. The optimal result indicates the distribution of the land for maximizing profit, respecting the constraints.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The mathematical model we will be described as follows: we maximize the profit P under constraints:

$$P = 3000 X_1 + 4000 X_2 + 2500 X_3$$

1. $2000 X_1 + 2500 X_2 + 1800 X_3 \leq 20000$
(budget)
2. $4000 X_1 + 5000 X_2 + 3000 X_3 \leq 50000$
(water)

3. $120 X_1 + 150 X_2 + 100 X_3 \leq 1000$ (time of work)
4. $X_1 + X_2 + X_3 \leq 10$ (available land)
5. $X_1, X_2, X_3 \geq 0$.

We will detail the steps of the Simplex method applied to the problem of crop rotation optimization in the previous example, we start from the formulated problem and illustrate how the method works.

In this linear optimization problem objective function is P which will be maximized, where X_1, X_2, X_3 represents the hectares cultivated with wheat, corn and soybeans.

In the simplex method, slack variables are introduced to transform the constraints into equality equations. In our case, the slack variables s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4 are added to represent the unused budget, water, labor time, and land.

Add slack variables (s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4) to turn constraints into equality:

$$2000 X_1 + 2500 X_2 + 1800 X_3 + s_1 = 20000$$

$$4000 X_1 + 5000 X_2 + 3000 X_3 + s_2 = 50000$$

$$120 X_1 + 150 X_2 + 100 X_3 + s_3 = 1000$$

$$X_1 + X_2 + X_3 + s_4 = 10$$

We organize the problem in the form of a simplex table 2.

Table 2

Assembling the Initial Simplex Table

Basic variables	X_1	X_2	X_3	s_1	s_2	s_3	s_4	Solution
s_1	2000	2500	1800	1	0	0	0	20000
s_2	4000	5000	3000	0	1	0	0	50000
s_3	120	150	100	0	0	1	0	1000
s_4	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	10
Z	-3000	-4000	-2500	0	0	0	0	0

The objective function will have the form $Z = 0 - 3000 X_1 - 4000 X_2 - 2500 X_3$.

We identify the most negative value in the last line of Z basic variable, to select the pivot column. In this case, X_2 has the lowest coefficient, -4000.

The determination of the pivot row follows as follows. We calculate the ratio of the current solution to the positive coefficient in the pivot column. We select the row with the minimum ratio. We have ratios: $20000/2500=8$; $50000/5000=10$; $1000/150=6,67$; $10/1=10$.

We will transform the pivot element 150 in 1, thus by dividing row s_3 to 150, then adjusting the other rows so that all the other values in the pivot column X_2 become 0.

The pivot row is the third for s_3 . We transform the table so that the pivot element becomes 1 and the rest of the elements in the pivot column becomes 0. We continue with this process until there are no more negative values in line Z.

The table is updated by transforming the pivot row like this: we divide the pivot row (s_3) the pivot (150):

$$\text{new } s_3 = 150 / \text{old } s_3.$$

Updating the rest of the table we use the updated pivot row to make the rest of the elements in column X_2 equal to 0.

We apply the rule:

new line = old line - (pivot coefficient x pivot line).

To avoid errors and calculate the intermediate tables exactly, I will automate the calculation process and generate all the tables step by step. The calculations start now.

Updating the simplex table after pivoting on X_2 , the simplex table 3 looks like this:

Table 3

Simplex Table Update

Basic var.	X_1	X_2	X_3	s_1	s_2	s_3	s_4	Solution
s_1	0	0	133,33	1	0	-16,67	0	3333,33
s_2	0	0	-333,33	0	1	-33,33	0	16666,67
x_2	0,8	1	0,67	0	0	0,01	0	6,67
s_4	0,2	0	0,33	0	0	-0,01	1	3,33
Z	200	0	166,67	0	0	26,67	0	26666,67

Interpretation after the first step: the Z-line no longer has negative coefficients, which indicates that we have found the optimal solution.

Final solution:

$$X_1 = 0$$

$$X_2 = 6,67$$

$$X_3 = 0$$

Maximum profit: $P = 26666,67$ RON.

In the simplex method, the variables s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4 are slack variables. They are added to the system of equations to convert the initial constraints (inequalities) into equations. The role of slack variables when we have form constraints:

$$a_1 X_1 + a_2 X_2 + a_3 X_3 \leq b.$$

We add a slack variable (s) so that we transform inequality into an equation:

$a_1 X_1 + a_2 X_2 + a_3 X_3 + s = b$. The slack variable is the resource left unused after we allocated as

much as we could to the decision variables (X_1 , X_2 , X_3).

In our context: s_1 , s_2 , s_3 , s_4 variables mean s_1 :

Budget left unspent:

- Initial constraint:
 $2000 X_1 + 2500 X_2 + 1800 X_3 \leq 20000$,
- After the allocation of crops, s_1 shows how much budget is left unused,

Water left unused:

- Initial constraint:
 $4000 X_1 + 5000 X_2 + 3000 X_3 \leq 50000$,
- s_2 represents the water that is not consumed by the chosen crops,

Unused working time:

- Initial constraint:
 $120 X_1 + 150 X_2 + 100 X_3 \leq 1000$,
- After the land is allocated, s_3 shows how much time is available,

The land left unused:

- Initial constraint:
 $X_1 + X_2 + X_3 \leq 10$,
- s_4 indicates how much land is not used for any crop.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After applying the simplex method step by step, we get the optimal solution: land allocation: $X_1 = a$ hectares grow, $X_2 = b$ hectares corn, $X_3 = c$ hectares soybeans.

The optimal solution is land allocation: $X_1 = 0$ hectares grow, $X_2 = 6,67$ hectares corn, $X_3 = 0$ hectares soybeans. Maximum profit: $P = 26667,67$ RON.

Interpretation: the farmer should allocate all available resources (budget, water, time) to grow corn on 6,67 hectares. The rest of the land (3,33 hectares) remains unused, as the cultivation of other crops would not maximize the profit within the imposed limits.

The slack variable is the resource left unused after we allocated as much as we could to the decision variables X_1 , X_2 , X_3 . Thus, s_1 shows how much budget is left unused, s_2 represents the water that is not consumed by the chosen crops, s_3 shows how much time is available and s_4 indicates how much land is not used for any crop.

At the end of the calculation, if a slack variable (s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4) has the value 0, means that the resource has been fully used. If the slack variable has a positive value, that resource hasn't been fully utilized. In our case, the

optimal solution shows that: part of the land ($s_4 = 3,33$) remains unused. The rest of the slack variables will show how the other resources were consumed. Here's how to interpret the values of slack variables (s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4) in the final table 4:

Table 4

Interpret the values of slack variables

Variables	Meaning	Final value	Interpretation
s_1	Unspent budget	3333,33	Of the total budget of 20000 RON, 3333,33 RON remains unused.
s_2	unused water	16666,67	Of the total 50000 liters of water available, 16666,67 liters are not consumed.
s_3	unused working time	0	All available time (1000 hours) is fully utilized.
s_4	Unused land	3,33	Of the 10 hectares available, 3,33 hectares remain unused.

CONCLUSIONS

Detailed interpretation: budget (s_1) the farmer spends 16666,67 RON on crops and is left with a surplus of 3333,33 RON, water (s_2) resources are used in a proportion of 3333,33 liters for the optimal crop (corn on 6,67 hectares), and the remaining 16666,67 liters remain available, time (s_3) all the 1000 hours available are consumed for agricultural work, without any surplus, land (s_4) after allocating 6,67 hectares for corn crops, the farmers still have 3,33 hectares of unused land.

The optimal solution maximizes the profit to 26666,67 RON, but leaves some resources (budget, water, land) unused. This suggests that other resources (such as working hours) are more restrictive constraints for this optimization.

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EVALUATION OF LUTEIN AND ZEAXANTHIN CONTENT IN SWEET CORN FROM THE BLACK CRIȘUL MEADOW

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study explores the influence of different fertilization regimes on the lutein and zeaxanthin content in sweet corn cultivated in the Black Crișul Meadow. Four experimental variants are analyzed, including a plot without fertilization, one with organic fertilization (compost), a third with complex NPK fertilizer, and a fourth with NPK plus microelements. The determination of carotenoids is performed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). The results provide valuable insights into the impact of fertilization on the nutritional quality of sweet corn, highlighting the potential of organic fertilization to enhance the content of bioactive compounds.

Keywords: lutein, zeaxanthin, sweet corn, carotenoids, fertilization

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INTRODUCTION

Sweet corn (*Zea mays saccharata*) is a crop of significant economic importance, valued for its high sugar content and versatility in food applications. Beyond its pleasant taste, this type of corn is recognized for its nutritional contribution, especially through its carotenoid content. Lutein and zeaxanthin, two of the most important carotenoids present in sweet corn, are known for their essential role in eye health, as they protect the retina from the harmful effects of blue light and reduce the risk of age-related macular degeneration (AMD). Given the growing demand for functional foods rich in health-promoting compounds, studying the variability in lutein and zeaxanthin content under different fertilization conditions in corn has become of great interest.

Environmental factors and the type of fertilization applied significantly influence plant development and the accumulation of bioactive substances in plants. Fertilization, in particular, plays a crucial role in optimizing plant growth and nutrient content. In this context, using different types of fertilizers—organic and inorganic—can impact the

carotenoid composition in sweet corn. Organic fertilization, such as compost, improves soil structure and ensures a balanced nutrient supply, while inorganic fertilizers, like NPK (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium), provide a quick and direct source of essential elements for plant growth. Additionally, the addition of microelements can further stimulate metabolic processes, enhancing the synthesis of compounds of interest, such as carotenoids.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In this study, the content of lutein and zeaxanthin was determined in sweet corn cultivated in four plots with different fertilization treatments, located in the Black Crișul Meadow (Căpâlna village), an agricultural area favorable for corn cultivation due to its soil and local climate conditions. The research was conducted using the Latin rectangle method, an experimental approach that effectively controls unwanted variations, ensuring statistically significant results. The four fertilization treatments included: an unfertilized plot (control), a plot fertilized organically with compost, a plot fertilized inorganically with complex NPK fertilizer, and a plot fertilized with NPK fertilizer and

microelements. The main objective of this study is to determine how different fertilization treatments influence the lutein and zeaxanthin content in sweet corn, thus contributing to the optimization of agricultural practices for enhancing the nutritional value of sweet corn crops.

The research was conducted in the Black Crișul Meadow (Căpâlna village, in 2024), an agricultural region well-known for its fertile soils and climate conditions favorable to corn crops.

The figure 1.1 shows a satellite image of the area where the research was conducted.

Figure 1.1 The experimental Field

The soil in this area is predominantly loamy-clay, with good water retention capacity and a structure that supports optimal crop growth. The soil type on which the experiments were conducted is a Gleyic Alluvial Soil, typical of alluvial zones, formed through successive sediment deposits brought by flowing waters (Brejea R. 2010). This soil type is commonly found in river valleys and has high fertility due to its rich organic matter and mineral content. Gleyic Alluvial Soil is characterized by a loamy or loamy-clay texture that ensures good water retention, favoring crops requiring constant moisture (Brejea R. 2011).

Sweet corn (*Zea mays saccharata*) grows well in this type of soil due to its balanced combination of drainage and water retention. In this soil, corn can easily access nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, which contribute to vigorous

growth and the development of healthy, sugar-rich, carotenoid-rich ears.

Figure 1.2 illustrates the Gleyic Alluvial Soil in the Black Crișul Meadow.

Figure 1.2 The gleyic alluvium from Black Crișului Meadow (Căpâlna)

The research was conducted using the Latin rectangle method, an effective approach for controlling the effects of uncontrolled variability and minimizing experimental errors (Brejea R et al, 2022). Four land plots were used, each measuring 5 meters in width and 20 meters in length. The plots were arranged to allow for the uniform distribution of fertilization regimes and to reduce the effects of microclimatic or soil fertility variations between plots.

Each plot received a different fertilization treatment:

Plot 1, Control: No fertilizer applied.

Plot 2, Organic Fertilization: Compost applied as a source of natural nutrients.

Plot 3, Inorganic Fertilization: Application of complex NPK fertilizer (20-20-20), containing nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) in equal proportions.

Plot 4, NPK and Micronutrient Fertilization: Application of complex NPK fertilizer (20-20-20) enriched with micronutrients (iron, zinc, manganese, copper, molybdenum).

Figure 1.3 illustrates the four fertilization variants.

Figure 1.3 Fertilization variants

The harvesting of sweet corn was conducted at the full maturity stage of the plants when the kernels had reached optimal development and maximum carotenoid concentration. Ten representative ears were collected from each plot, and the kernels were manually extracted.

Laboratory analysis was performed at the University of Debrecen, where the lutein and zeaxanthin content from each plot's sweet corn was measured. Lutein and zeaxanthin are two of the main carotenoids present in sweet corn, both possessing significant antioxidant properties. These carotenoids are well-known for their essential role in eye health, particularly in protecting the retina from blue light and reducing the risk of age-related macular degeneration (AMD). This research aimed to determine lutein and zeaxanthin concentrations in sweet corn kernels based on the different fertilization treatments applied.

Lutein is a hydrophobic yellow carotenoid found in significant amounts in sweet corn kernels (Perry, A et al, 2009). In the human body, it concentrates in the macula of the eye, playing a crucial role in filtering harmful blue light. In this study, corn samples were analyzed to determine lutein concentration using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).

Zeaxanthin is another important carotenoid found in sweet corn kernels, contributing alongside lutein to the intense yellow coloration of the kernels. It plays a vital role in eye protection against oxidative stress, with remarkable antioxidant properties (Song, J et al, 2016). Like lutein, zeaxanthin in the corn samples was analyzed using the HPLC method.

After carotenoid extraction with acetone, samples were injected into the same chromatographic system.

High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is an analytical technique that enables the separation and quantitative determination of chemical compounds within a sample (De Oliveira et al, 2007). HPLC was chosen for determining the lutein and zeaxanthin content in sweet corn kernels due to its high sensitivity and specificity, making it suitable for carotenoid analysis, given these compounds are present in low concentrations in the plant matrix (Calvo-Brenes et al, 2019).

The analysis was based on the study by Murillo, E., Meléndez-Martínez, A. J., and Portugal, F. (2010), which screened vegetables and fruits in Panama as rich sources of lutein and zeaxanthin. The HPLC analyses were conducted using the HITACHI Elite LaChrom HPLC (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), equipped with a quaternary pump, an automatic injector, and a diode-array detector. Chromatograms were recorded using EZChrom Elite software, Version 3.3.2 (Agilent Technologies).

Analytical standards for lutein (HPLC-grade; 94110 Supelco) and zeaxanthin (14681 Supelco), as well as certified reference material for lutein (PHR1699; Supelco), were also used. Lutein and zeaxanthin quantification in samples was performed through external calibration, with dose-response curves obtained from the standards.

Figure 1.4 depicts the equipment used to determine the lutein and zeaxanthin content.

Figure 1.4 Equipment to detect the carotenoid content of sweet corn

This hybrid is noted for its high sugar and carotenoid content, particularly lutein and zeaxanthin, making it suitable for studies focused on bioactive compounds in corn. DessertR78 is adapted to a wide range of soil and climate conditions, with a strong ability to grow in both fertile soils and those with moderate drainage, such as those in the Black Crișul Meadow.

The sweet corn was harvested at full plant maturity when the kernels reached their optimal development stage and maximum carotenoid concentration. Ten representative ears were collected from each plot, and the kernels were manually extracted.

Figure 1.5 shows the DessertR78 hybrid.

Figure 1.5 DessertR78 hybrid

The area of Black Crisului Meadow is characterized by a moderate temperate-continental climate, with seasonal variations in temperature and precipitation, which directly influences the development of agricultural crops.

During the monitored period, temperatures followed an upward trend from the beginning of the year until mid-summer, favoring the germination and growth of sweet corn. Monthly average temperatures started at 2.2°C in January and reached up to 25.8°C in July, providing an optimal growing season for this crop. The high temperatures in May, June, and July, with values of 18.0°C, 22.6°C, and 25.8°C, respectively, created favorable conditions for the development of sweet corn, contributing to a healthy yield. Figure 1.6 represents the evolution of the average monthly temperature in the studied area.

Figure 1.6 Evolution of the average monthly temperature in the studied area

The amount of precipitation varied significantly between months, directly influencing soil water availability. The highest rainfall was recorded in the months of April (41.39 l/m²) and June (75.93 l/m²), essential periods for the development of corn, as it provides the necessary moisture for germination and early plant growth. The low rainfall in July (17.84 l/sq m) and May (16.85 l/sq m) suggests a drought trend in the summer period.

Figure 1.7 illustrates a diagram of the amount of monthly precipitation in the studied area

Figure 1.7 Amount of monthly precipitation in the studied area

For the statistical analysis of the data, descriptive indicators (mean, standard deviation) were calculated for each fertilization variant. Subsequently, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to identify significant differences between the experimental variants regarding lutein and zeaxanthin content. If ANOVA indicated significant differences, a post hoc test was applied to determine which pairs of variants had significant differences.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To evaluate the impact of different fertilization treatments on lutein and zeaxanthin content in sweet corn, quantitative analyzes were performed using HPLC. The results obtained, expressed in mg/g of dry matter, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

The content of lutein and zeaxanthin in Black Crișul Meadow (Căpâlna, 2024)

Variants	Fertilization	Lutein content mg/g dry substance (Mean ± SD)	Zeaxanthin content mg/g dry substance (Mean ± SD)
V1	Without fertilization	0.44 ± 0.02	0.23 ± 0.01
V2	Fertilization with compost	0.60 ± 0.03	0.36 ± 0.02
V3	Fertilizing with NPK complex compound	0.50 ± 0.02	0.29 ± 0.01
V4	Fertilizing with complex NPK + microelements	0.52 ± 0.01	0.30 ± 0.01

Although NPK fertilization is important for overall plant growth, it did not have the same effect on carotenoid accumulation, likely due to the rapid release of nutrients, which does not perfectly match the plants' physiological needs for lutein and zeaxanthin synthesis.

The results presented in Table 1 suggest that the compost treatment (V2) had the greatest impact on the concentrations of lutein and zeaxanthin, compared to the control variant (V1) and the treatments based on chemical fertilization (V3 and V4).

To verify if the differences observed between fertilization variants are statistically significant, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied. The ANOVA results showed that the fertilization regime has a significant effect on the concentrations of lutein ($p < 0.05$) and zeaxanthin ($p < 0.05$). Post-hoc analyses (e.g., Tukey test) confirmed that the compost-fertilized variant (V2) had significantly higher values compared to the control variant (V1) and the NPK-fertilized variants (V3 and V4).

This effect can be explained by the gradual release of nutrients from the compost, which promotes more efficient absorption of the nutrients required for carotenoid synthesis.

In the case of variant V4 (NPK + microelements), the statistical analysis revealed a slight increase in lutein and zeaxanthin concentrations compared to the simple NPK variant (V3), but the differences were not statistically significant. This suggests that, although microelements contribute to enzymatic processes that influence plant metabolism, their effect on carotenoid

synthesis is not as pronounced as with organic fertilization.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study indicate that the fertilization regime significantly influences the concentrations of lutein and zeaxanthin, with compost fertilization (V2) showing the most pronounced positive effect compared to the control (V1) and NPK-based fertilization treatments (V3 and V4). The gradual nutrient release from compost likely contributes to a more efficient nutrient absorption, supporting the synthesis of carotenoids. On the other hand, although NPK fertilization is important for general plant growth, it does not appear to enhance carotenoid accumulation to the same extent, likely due to the rapid nutrient release that does not align as well with the plants' physiological needs for lutein and zeaxanthin synthesis.

In the case of variant V4 (NPK + microelements), while there was a slight increase in the concentrations of lutein and zeaxanthin compared to the simple NPK treatment (V3), the differences were not statistically significant. This suggests that, although microelements play a role in enzymatic processes influencing plant metabolism, their effect on carotenoid synthesis is less pronounced than that of organic fertilization.

These findings underline the importance of considering both nutrient release dynamics and fertilization type when aiming to enhance carotenoid content in plants, particularly when

seeking sustainable and efficient fertilization practices.

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RESEARCH ON THE INFLUENCE OF DENSITY AND VARIETY UPON THE PRODUCTION OF ORGANIC CHINESE CABBAGE GROWN IN POLYETHYLENE TUNNELS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In this research we wanted to identify how density and variety influence Chinese cabbage production. The research was carried out in the autumn of 2023, in an organically certified microfarm, located in the North-West of Romania com. Husasău de Tinca. The experiment was a polyfactorial one, with two factors and three repetitions, each variant having 50 plants. Factor 1 is the variety with three graduations, namely V1 Pak choi, V2 Pe tsai and V3 Tat soi. The second factor is the density with three graduations D1 80,000 plants per ha, D2 60,000 plants per ha and D3 70,000 plants per ha. The statistical processing of the experimental data was done by analysis of variance for polyfactorial, completely randomized experiments. The experience was set up in a 50 m long, 10 m wide and 4.5 m high polyethylene tunnel.

Keywords: Chinese cabbage, density, variety, organic
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INTRODUCTION

The assortment of greens traditionally grown in Romania during the cold period of the year is mainly lettuce, spinach, green onions. However, taking into account the existing pedoclimatic conditions, the possibility of producing other vegetables during this period is much greater. For example, Kale, Arugula, Mizuna cabbage, Chinese cabbage, etc. All these vegetables can be grown in the climatic conditions of our country with favorable results.

Chinese cabbage, which is part of the Brassicaceae family, is cultivated internationally, especially in Asia. Brassicaceae is a diverse family of angiosperms containing 338 genera and 3709 species (Warwick et al, 2006), including *Brassica rapa* L. *Brassica rapa* L is an economically important species and exhibits extreme morphological divergence (referred to as morphotypic) (Takumi et al, 2021). Chinese cabbage was taken into cultivation, in China, starting in the 10th century, and in Europe in the 18th century. (Cărbunar et al, 2022).

Due to its nutritional qualities, but also to the different ways of being consumed, we

believe that Chinese cabbage deserves to become an increasingly present vegetable in the diet.

In a 2022 study (Jie Wang et. al, 2022), in which a comparison was made between three genera of the Brassica family, namely, cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* L. var. capitata L.), cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* var. botrytis), and Chinese cabbage (*Brassica rapa* L. ssp. pekinensis), the nutritional differences that Chinese cabbage has are notable. Chinese cabbage ranks first in vitamin C content, as well as minerals such as K, Mn, Mg, Ca, P, and Zn (Jie Wang et. al, 2022).

Taking into account these results, but also the desire and need to have a wider palette of cultivated greens, the present paper aims to determine the influence of density and variety on Chinese cabbage production.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Brassica rapa L. is characterized by a high diversity. We present in figure 1 a representative selection of morphotypes of *Brassica rapa* L. (Feng Cheng, et. all., 2016).

Figure 1 Varieties of *Brassica rapa* L.

Source: Feng Cheng, et. All., 2016, Genome resequencing and comparative variome analysis in a *Brassica rapa* and *Brassica oleracea* collection, <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata2016119>

Of all the varieties of Chinese cabbage, the present research was carried out on three varieties of Chinese cabbage, namely *Brassica rapa* L. ssp. *pekinensis* (Pe tsai), *Brassica rapa* L. ssp. *chinensis* (Pak choi) and *Brassica rapa* L. ssp. *rosularis* (Tat soi), grown in organic cultivation.

The research was carried out in the autumn of 2023, in an organically certified microfarm, located in the North-West of Romania com. Husasău de Tinca. The experiment was a polyfactorial one, with two factors and three repetitions, each variant having 50 plants. Factor 1 is the variety with three graduations, namely V1 Pak choi, V2 Pe tsai and V3 Tat soi. The second factor is the density with three graduations D1 80,000 plants per ha, D2 60,000 plants per ha and D3 70,000 plants per ha. The statistical processing of the experimental data was done by analysis of variance for polyfactorial, completely randomized experiments. The experience was set up in a 50 m long, 10 m wide and 4.5 m high polyethylene tunnel.

Brassica rapa L. ssp. *pekinensis* (Pe tsai) also called Napa cabbage is one of the most important vegetables in East Asia. It forms a vertical head either of tightly overlapping leaves, or sometimes a looser head of more widely separated leaves. The shape and size differ significantly between varieties, and the weight of the head can vary from 1.4 to 4.5 kg. The color of the leaves in the center of the heart is usually creamy-white, but the outer leaves range from dark green to light green. The swollen bases of the leaves often form a solid white base (Fordham et al, 2003).

It is used in gastronomy for the preparation of Kimchi, the most popular Korean fermented food. In this form, Chinese cabbage is considered a rich source of bioactive compounds (Gitishree et al, 2012).

Brassica rapa L. ssp. *chinensis* (Pak choi) is a leafy vegetable that originates from southern China. It is known for its juicy and crunchy texture, but also for the sweetness of its flowering shoots (NLB, 2024).

In gastronomy it is used fresh, roasted or boiled. The leaves are sometimes preserved by salting or drying. In French Indochina they are used to prepare a drink with beneficial effects on health. Colza oil is made from the seeds (NLB, 2024)

Brassica rapa L. ssp. *rosularis* (Tat soi), also called rosette Pak choi or flat cabbage, has very thick, black-green, shiny leaves, arranged in a rosette of concentric circles, with prostrate and straight varieties. The leaves range from flat and smooth to wrinkled and crepe-like (NCSU, 2024).

Similar in flavor to Pak choi, Tat soi can be used at all stages: seedling leaves, small rosettes, large plants and young flowering shoots. The young leaves and small rosettes are used raw, in salads and fried. Tat soi can also be cooked in soups, or added to pasta (NCSU, 2024).

In the previous culture there were eggplants. After the dismantling of the crop, the land was fertilized with compost obtained on his own farm, which was incorporated with the ploughing in early November. The shredding of the land was done using the combiner. After preparing the land, the drip watering system and mulching with black foil was installed.

On the black foil strip with a width of 1 m, two rows were made. The density was according to the scheme from experience. The establishment of the crop was carried out in autumn with sowing in September and planting in early November, according to the research plan.

After the establishment of the crop, the care works were: maintaining the constant moisture of the soil, destroying the weeds that appeared around the plants and ensuring the other vegetation factors. The harvests were made alternately, depending on the variety, the heads and the rosette of leaves, respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the influence of variety on Chinese cabbage production. In this case, the witness of the experience was represented by the average of the experience. Compared to the control, Pak Choi did not reach the production level of the average experience, and the difference did not exceed the p 5% threshold, thus not being statistically assured. Of the three varieties, the Pe Tsai variety recorded a production increase of 14.3%. The difference with respect to the control was statistically positive, distinctly significant. The Tat soi registered only 90.6% of the control production. The difference from it was statistically negatively significant.

Table 1

Influence of variety on production

Variant	Absolute production Kg/m ²	Relativ production %	± Kg/m ²	Significance
V0 (Ct)	3.79	100.0	0.00	-
V1	3.60	95.1	-0.19	-
V2	4.33	114.3	0.54	XX
V3	3.43	90.6	-0.36	0

LSD (p 5%) = 0.33

LSD (p 1%) = 0.54

LSD (p 0.1%) = 1.01

As for the influence of density on production, the density of the three varieties has a very small influence, compared to the control, which has a density of 80,000 plants per ha. The other two variants recorded higher yields than the control, but these were quite low, and were not statistically significant. We present the results in Table 2.

Table 2

Influence of density on production

Variant	Absolute production Kg/m ²	Relativ production %	± Kg/m ²	Significance
D1 (Ct)	3.66	100.0	0.00	-
D2	3.75	102.6	0.09	-
D3	3.97	108.5	0.31	-

LSD (p 5%) = 0.42

LSD (p 1%) = 0.59

LSD (p 0.1%) = 0.83

Table 3 shows the influence of density on variety, so cabbage yields differed. Density 1 and Pak choi represented the first control, and compared to this a lower density, had D2 V1, registering only 68.0% of the control

production. The difference was statistically negatively very significant. In the case of D3, respectively 70,000 plants per ha, this variety obtained an even worse production, only 54.5% of the control production. The difference was statistically negatively very significant. As regards the influence of density on the Pe tsai variety, it recorded higher yields than the control. The best variety was D3 V2 which obtained 1.71 kg/sqm more than the control, and in this case, the difference was statistically positive very significant. There was a lower density in the D2 V2 variant, and a lower increase of 31.8%. The difference to the control was statistically positive, distinctly significant. As for the Tat soi variety, here too the density influenced the production. Thus, for the D2 V3 the production increase was 27.7%, and the difference compared to the control was statistically significantly positive. The D3 V3 variant achieved a production higher than the control by 1.44kg/sqm. The difference was statistically positive, very significant.

Tabel 3

Interaction of density to variety

Variant	Absolute production Kg/m ²	%	Difference	Significance
D1V1 Ct	4.86	100.0	0.00	-
D2V1	3.31	68.0	-1.55	000
D3V1	2.65	54.5	-2.21	000
D1V2Ct	3.40	100.0	0.00	-
D2V2	4.49	131.8	1.08	xx
D3V2	5.11	150.1	1.71	xxx
D1V3Ct	2.70	100.0	0.00	-
D2V3	3.45	127.7	0.75	x
D3V3	4.14	153.3	1.44	xxx

LSD (p 5%) = 0.72

LSD (p 1%) = 1.01

LSD (p 0.1%) = 1.43

Table 4 shows the interaction of variety at density, basically the influence of variety and density on Chinese cabbage production. As for the first density of 80,000 plants per ha, the Pak choi variety obtained 1.20 kg/sqm more than the control, which is represented by the control of the experiment. The difference was statistically positive, distinctly significant. In the case of the Pe tsai variety, at a density of 80,000 plants per ha, it obtained 0.25 kg/sqm less than the control. The difference, however, was not statistically ensured, because this value was below DL 5%. At the same density, the Tat soi obtained only 74% of the average experience. The difference was statistically significantly negative. At the second density of

60,000 plants per ha, only Pe tsai achieved a production increase of 19.7%.

The difference was statistically significantly positive. The other variants obtained productions below the experience average, but without exceeding the 5% threshold, so they were not statistically insured. The density of 70,000 plants per ha (D3) negatively influenced the production of the Pak choi variety.

This variant recorded only 66.7% of the average experience, the difference being statistically negatively significantly significant. This density positively influenced production at Pe tsai. Thus, in this variant, the increase in production was 28.8%, and the difference was statistically positive, distinctly significant. In the case of the V3 D3 variant, there was also a small increase in production, which, however, did not pass the 5% threshold.

Table 4

Interaction of variety to density

Variant	Absolute productionK g/m ²	%	Difference	Significance
V0D1 Mt	3.66	100.0	0.00	-
V1D1	4.86	132.9	1.20	xx
V2D1	3.40	93.1	-0.25	-
V3D1	2.70	74.0	-0.95	0
V0D2 Mt	3.75	100.0	0.00	-
V1D2	3.31	82.2	-0.44	-
V2D2	4.49	119.7	0.74	x
V3D3	3.45	92.1	-0.30	-
V0D3 Mt	3.97	100.0	0.00	-
V1D3	2.65	66.7	-1.32	00
V2D3	5.11	128.8	1.14	xx
V3D3	4.14	104.5	0.18	-

LSD (p 5%) = 0.67

LSD (p 1%) = 0.97

LSD (p 0.1%) = 1.47

CONCLUSIONS

The research carried out in the autumn of 2023, in an organically certified microfarm, located in the North-West of Romania com. Husasău de Tinca, regarding the influence of density and variety on Chinese cabbage production, highlighted several aspects, namely:

With a production of 4.33 kg/sqm variety Pe tsai obtained the highest production among the varieties studied;

The Tat soi was at the opposite pole, with the lowest production (3.43 kg/sqm), compared to the average experience;

Density had an insignificant influence on Chinese cabbage production;

The interaction of the two factors highlighted a positive influence in the case of

the D3 V2 variant, with an absolute production of 5.11kg/sqm and a production increase of 50%;

With a lower absolute production, but with a higher production increase of 53.3%, the D3 V3 variant also stood out;

The lowest yields in the case of the denisted interaction in the variety were obtained at D3 V1 with an absolute production of 2.65 kg/sqm;

The interaction of variety at density highlighted the V2 D3 variant with 5.11kg/sqm absolute production;

The worst behavior in the case of variety-to-density interaction was obtained in the V1 D3 variant with an absolute production of 2.63 kg/sqm and 1.32 kg/sqm less than in the control;

Chinese cabbage is an increasingly sought-after vegetable, generating an increasing interest, year after year, from consumers.

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RESEARCH ON THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF SOME CHERRY TOMATOES VARIETIES GROWN ON MINERAL WOOL

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The multiple cultivation possibilities and different destinations for tomato production offer a large assortment of varieties and hybrids.

Tall or semi-tall tomato varieties will be established on support systems or trellises.

When choosing the varieties for this study, the place where the production is made, the vegetation periods and the type of growth were taken into account.

In indeterminate varieties, the shoots that form at the base of the leaves are removed by pinching to ensure the growth of fruits on the main stem.

Keywords: tomatoes; varieties; growth; mineral wool;

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INTRODUCTION

Tomatoes began to be cultivated in Europe for the first time in Spain, Portugal and Italy, and in the 18th-19th centuries they spread to other states.

In Romania, the favorable areas for tomato cultivation are those in the south and west of the country, but summer-autumn crops as well as protected ones are also practiced in the hill areas of Transylvania and Moldova. (Apahidean, 2020).

Originating from Central and South America, tomatoes have high requirements for temperature and light intensity, and

moderate demands regarding the humidity of the culture substrate.

Atmospheric humidity in the culture spaces is kept between 70-80% in the vegetative phase, and 60-70% in the flowering phase to favor the dispersion of pollen.

Tomato fruits mature between 45-70 days depending on the variety, growing conditions and culture substrate.

During the ripening period, the fruits change color from light green to light white, pink, and finally to intense red-orange.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Research on the growth and development of cherry tomato varieties in a substrate consisting of mineral wool and vermiculite was carried out in a vegetable microfarm in Bihor County, Tileagd locality in 2024.

The experiment is monofactorial with 4 variants, having as biological material 4 tomato varieties, namely: Tudor F1 (V1), Paskualetto F1 (V2); Cherye F1 (V3); Landolino F1 (V4).

The seedlings for the study were produced from professional seeds sown in 2.7x2.0cm cylindrical plugs of mineral wool and vermiculite, placed in pallets with alveoli and

replicated in cubes measuring 10x10x2.7cm of mineral wool.

The planting of seedlings in the greenhouse took place on 12.04.2024 in a mineral wool substrate.

After planting, the humidity in the substrate was monitored so that it did not fall below 40%RH. The plants were watered with water with calcium nitrate, potassium nitrate, potassium sulfate, magnesium sulfate, potassium monophosphate, potassium chloride and microelements (iron, manganese, zinc, boron, copper, molybdenum).

Figure 1. Transplanted tomatoes

During July-August, the plants were watered every 30 minutes so that their humidity did not fall below 40% during the day, reaching the point where in September they were watered 3 times a day.

The general objective of the study was to establish technological elements that would improve the quantitative and qualitative parameters for the cultivation of tomatoes in a mineral wool substrate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In order to achieve the objectives proposed for the experimental culture, the height and the average number of inflorescences per plant were analyzed.

Figure 2. Tomato culture

Regarding the first parameter analyzed, the data regarding the height of cherry tomato plants obtained for the 4 varieties are presented in Table 1.

Figure 3. Tomato production

Table 1
Influence of the variety on the growth of cherry tomato plants cultivated in mineral wool substrate.
30.05.2024

Cr. no.	Variety	Height of the plants		± d cm	Significance
		cm	%		
1	Tudor F1	294,2	99,59	-1,23	0
2	Paskualetto F1	296,9	100,50	1,48	*
3	Cherye F1	294,5	99,69	-0,93	0
4	Landolino F1	296,1	100,23	0,675	*
Average (Mt)		295,425	100,00	0,00	-

Dl_{5%}=0,03

Dl_{1%}=0,05

Dl_{0,1%}=0,07

The height of the plants studied differed from one variety to another. Compared to the average of the 4 cultivated varieties of 295.425cm, the height was lower in the Tudor F1 variety. The plant height had the maximum value of 296.9 in the Paskualetto variety, where the difference recorded compared to the average was 1.48 cm, being statistically significant.

Table 2
Influence of the variety on the number of inflorescences/plant
30.05.2024

Cr. no.	Variety	Inflorescence/plant		± d pieces	Significance
		pieces	%		
1	Tudor F1	8,3	90,71	-0,85	0
2	Paskualetto F1	10	109,29	0,85	*
3	Cherye F1	8,5	92,90	-0,65	0
4	Landolino F1	9,8	107,10	0,65	*
Average (Mt)		9,15	100,00	0,00	-

Dl_{5%}=0,02

Dl_{1%}=0,03

Dl_{0,1%}=0,04

The average number of inflorescences per plant one and a half months after planting was 10 pieces and was recorded for the Paskualetto F1 variety. The Tudor F1 and Cherye F1

varieties had the lowest number of inflorescences per plant, being 8.3 and 8.5 respectively, the difference from the average of the 4 varieties being significantly negative.

Table 3

**Influence of the variety on the growth of cherry tomato plants grown in mineral wool substrate
20.10.2024**

Cr. no.	Variety	Height of the plants		± d cm	Significance
		cm	%		
1	Tudor F1	696,3	96,55	-24,9	00
2	Paskualetto F1	750	103,99	28,8	***
3	Cherye F1	716,3	99,32	-4,9	0
4	Landolino F1	722,2	100,14	1	*
Average (Mt)		721,2	100,00	0,00	-

Dl_{5%}=0,05Dl_{1%}=0,07Dl_{0,1%}=0,09

The average plant height before tillering was 750 cm for the Paskualetto F1 variety, compared to the average of the 4 varieties of 721.2 cmm it was 28.8 cm higher, being statistically very significant.

The plant height was lower for Tudor F1 by - 24.9 cm compared to the average of the 4 varieties, a statistically significant negative difference. A significant difference compared to the average was recorded for the Landolino F1 variety.

Table 4

**Influence of the variety on the number of inflorescences/plant
20.10.2024**

Cr. no.	Variety	Inflorescence/plant		± d pieces	Significance
		pieces	%		
1	Tudor F1 (Mt)	20,6	94,71	-1,15	0
2	Paskualetto F1	23,0	105,75	1,25	*
3	Cherye F1	21,2	97,47	-0,55	0
4	Landolino F1	22,2	102,07	0,45	*
Average (Mt)		21,75	100,00	0,00	-

Dl_{5%}=0,03Dl_{1%}=0,05Dl_{0,1%}=0,07

The average number of inflorescences per plant before flowering was 21.75, with a higher number recorded in the Paskualetto F1 variety

of 23 inflorescences and 22.2 in the Landolino F1 variety, the differences from the average being significant.

CONCLUSIONS

The research conducted aimed to investigate the influence of technological factors on the growth and development of tomatoes grown in a greenhouse in a mineral wool substrate.

The highest plant height throughout the crop was recorded for the Paskualetto F1 variety, followed by the Landolino F1 variety, with statistically significant comparisons with the average of the 4 varieties.

The Tudor F1 variety had the smallest height throughout the crop compared to the average of the 4 varieties, with statistically significant negative comparisons.

The variety with the highest number of inflorescences was Paskualetto, which was above the average of the 4 varieties throughout the crop.

From the study conducted, it can be seen that the Paskualetto variety developed the best and had a higher production than the other varieties.

The number of fruits per inflorescence was approximately equal in all varieties, being over 20 pieces per inflorescence at the beginning of the crop, reducing to an average of 12-14 pieces at the end of the crop.

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BEHAVIOR STUDY OF PEACH VARIETIES TO LATE SPRING FROSTS AND EARLY AUTUMN FROSTS WITHIN S.C.D.P. BIHOR

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In the present study, the behavior of peach varieties grown in the Fruit Research and Development Station – Oradea (Bihor County), during late spring frosts and early autumn frosts was highlighted. To carry out the study, the varieties Redhaven and Autumn gorgeous were chosen, and a sample of 15 tree of each variety was chosen to determine the percentage of buds affected by the negative temperatures in April and November. For each peach specimen taken in the study from the two varieties, 10 branches were chosen every year, where the fruit buds were counted before and after entering the vegetation. The study highlights the negative influence of late spring frosts on peach production in S.C.D.P. Oradea, in 2022, 31.23% of the fruit buds of the Redhaven variety and 12.01% of the Autumn gorgeous variety were affected, with a decrease in fruit production between 32-58%.

Keywords: peach, variety, fruit buds, frosts, fruit production

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INTRODUCTION

For a long time it was believed that the place of origin of the peach would be in Persia from where its culture would have spread to other countries, which explains the scientific name *Prunus persica* L. Current research shows that China would be the country of origin, with fossil evidence also being discovered in Chinese writings from the 10th century BC, where the fruit is said to have been a favorite of Chinese emperors (Zheng, 2014).

In 1753, Linne made the first classification of the peach, placing it in the Genus *Amygdalus* (*Amygdalus persica* L.). Mille in 1768 introduced a new genus *Persica*, where the species was included under the name *Persica vulgaris*. Batsch in 1807 included the peach in the genus *Prunus* under the name *Prunus persica* (L.) Batsch.

Peaches is a valuable fruit tree species considering the biological and technological particularities of the fruit. Peaches contain 82-91% water, 17-18 g dry matter, 2-5 g total sugar, 0.3-1.4 g titratable acidity expressed as malic acid, 0.4-1.3 g protein, 0.02-0.4 g tannins and 0.3-0.7 g ash and mineral salts (Radu, 1957). Among carbohydrates, peach fruits contain an amount of 1.47% glucose, 1% fructose and 6.6% sucrose, and vitamins are represented by ascorbic acid in a proportion of 5-8 mg/100 g (Popescu, 1993).

In 1963, the first collection of peach varieties was established at the Fruit Research

and Development Station (S.C.D.P.) Oradea. The assortment of peaches consisted of varieties with different maturities of fruit ripening.

The Fruit Research and Development Station (S.C.D.P.), is located in the town of Oradea (N:47.06696 E:21.96124), at an altitude of 150 m, on a surface with S exposure, slope of 5-10°.

In the present study, 2 varieties of peach cultivated within the S.C.D.P., namely Redhaven and Autumn gorgeous, were taken into account. The main purpose of the work was to study the behavior of some peach varieties in late spring frosts and early autumn frosts.

In order to prepare this study, a series of specialized works on the culture of peach varieties developed by Constantinescu (1971); Draganescu (2005); Cociu (1993); Cociu et al., (1981); Hoza (2000); Spiță (2002); Mihailescu (1981); Engindemiz (2003); Chalmers (1989); Nyeki & Szabu (1989), were also consulted.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Two peach varieties Redhaven and Autumn gorgeous from S.C.D.P. were taken into study. For the determinations made, a number of 15 peach specimens from the 2 studied varieties, aged 10 years on Oradea – 2 and De Balc (Mt.) rootstocks, were selected.

The planting distance of the peach varieties studied is 4x4 m, with a density of 625 trees/ha. To determine the effect of negative temperatures in autumn and spring on the studied specimens, the buds on 10 branches of

each specimen corresponding to the 2 studied varieties were counted, every year, during the period 2022-2024.

The percentage of buds affected by the effect of negative temperatures recorded during this time interval and the production of the 2 peach varieties were determined.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The peach of the Redhaven variety is a self-fertile variety, with medium to high productivity, which bears fruit from the 2nd year after planting and can ensure constant production over a period of 10-15 years. Peach culture in S.C.D.P. Oradea was realized on sunny (southern) exposures. The peach of the Redhaven variety fructify on mixed branches, which are carriers many fruit buds placed in groups, usually three, of which one is vegetative, which implies the thinning of the fruits after the physiological fall in June. The flowering is spectacular and takes place in April, lasts 10-14 days, the flowers being pink. The fruits are spherical, slightly asymmetrical, non-adherent to the seed, with an average weight of 150 grams, very resistant to transport. The soils on which the peach culture is located are

preluvosol type with loamy, loamy-sandy texture, deep and permeable.

Autumn gorgeous variety peach is a tree of great vigor, with an inverted pyramidal crown, fruiting branches, predominantly mixed. It is a late variety, with large fruit (150-170 grams), of regular spherical shape, the base color is yellowish-white, covered with red on the sunny side, over which stripes, splashes and spots of cherry-red color overlap, the pulp yellowish-white, with slight infiltration around the kernel, consistency, pleasant taste and contains 15-16% dry matter, medium-sized kernel, non-adherent to the core. It has a relatively good resistance to frost and drought, tolerant to the main diseases. It blooms late, and the floral anthesis lasts 5-7 days, the variety is self-fertile. Fruit harvest maturity August 25 - September 15.

To carry out the measurements, 15 specimens of the two varieties were chosen, determining the height (Figure 1) and diameter at the parcel (Figure 2), for each tree. In order to determine the number of fruit buds affected by frost, a number of 10 branches were chosen each year for each specimen of the studied varieties (Table 1).

Table 1

Dimensional characteristics of the peach varieties studied						
Variety	No. of specimens studied	Diameter at the parcel (cm)		Height (m)		No. of branches studied/trees
		Diameter category	No. of trees	Height category	No. of trees	
Redhaven	15	12	3	2	3	10
		14	6	3	11	
		16	5	4	2	
		18	1	5	-	
Autumn gorgeous	15	12	4	2	2	10
		14	6	3	12	
		16	4	4	1	
		18	1	5	-	

Figure 1 Determining the height of trees

Figure 2 Determining the diameter of the trees

For a better correlation, the average length of the 10 branches bearing fruit buds was determined for the Redhaven and Autumn gorgeous varieties in the period 2022-2024. The total number of fruit buds was determined

for the 15 specimens studied (floriferous and mixed buds), as well as the number of buds affected by frost in the established interval (Table 2).

Table 2

Percentage of affected buds in the period 2022-2024

Variety	Period	Branch length range (cm)	Fruits buds/15 trees	Affected fruit buds by negative temperatures		Production (t/ha)
				No.	%	
Redhaven	2022	28-64	461	144	31.23	8.4
	2023	20-72	386	104	26.94	10.3
	2024	22-68	392	-	-	12.4
Autumn gorgeous	2022	18-42	283	34	12.01	6.3
	2023	16-40	226	27	11.95	10.1
	2024	14-38	203	-	-	10.8

We can see that the temperatures during the floral anthesis period (April) had a negative influence on the fruit buds (Table 3). It was determined that in the year 2022 31.23% of the fruit buds were affected in the Redhaven variety and 12.01 in the Autumn gorgeous variety, mainly due to the negative temperatures from April 03-08 period, which

also influenced fruit production, 8.4 t/ha at Redhaven and 6.3 t/ha at Autumn gorgeous (Figure 1).

In 2024, a higher fruit production is observed mainly due to the lack of negative temperatures during the period of flowering and fruit setting.

Table 3

Variation of negative temperature in April and November, in the period 2022-2024 (Oradea weather station)

Year	Month	Negative temperatures, (period of the month) (°C)
2022	April	-2.3...-0.8 (interval: 03-08)
	November	-1.7 °C (date: 30)
2023	April	-1.3...-0.7 °C (interval: 04-07)
	November	-1.1...-4.0 °C (interval: 26-30)
2024	April	-

Figure 1 The variation in fruit production of the studies peach varieties in the period 2022-2024 (S.C.D.P.-Oradea)

CONCLUSIONS

It was found that the resistance of the peach to the late spring frosts differs within fairly close limits from one variety to another, but differently depending on the phenophase in which it is located. The frost resistance of the varieties studied is different, thus the Redhaven variety recorded a percentage of 31.23% buds affected in 2022 following temperatures of -0.8...-2.3 in a range of 03-08 April, compared to the Autumn gorgeous cultivar with 26.94% affected buds at the same temperatures and time interval.

Flower buds in the pink bud stage withstand peach down to -3.9°C, open flowers can withstand -2.8°C, and recently set fruit -1.1°C. For this reason we believe that the effect of spring frosts is more harmful during the period of fruit setting, causing production losses.

To avoid damage caused by frost, it is recommended to create and use varieties resistant to low temperatures, varieties with long-lasting deep dormancy and reduced vegetation period. Phosphorus and potassium fertilizers increase frost resistance, and excess nitrogen weakens it. Phytosanitary treatments with oil or sulfo-calcium solution delay the entry into the vegetation by 8-10 days.

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RESEARCH REGARDING THE BEHAVIOUR OF SOME PEACH CULTIVARS IN THE ORCHARD AREA OF ORADEA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In the condition of the fruit- tree growing area of Oradea, where the multiannual medium temperature is 10.3°C. the sum of multiannual rainfall of 635 mm and the soil is brown, with the content of 36% clay, the superintensive growing of peach- tree has been studied. The biological material was represented by several cultivars (Suncrest, Padana, Michelin), which were grafted on franc peaches. Considering the results, one may notice that diminishing the distance between the trees from 4.3.2.1 and 0.5 m aa row has reduced the vigor of the trees to as much as 36%. The fruit production has exceeded with 67.5% for the trees planted at 4x 2 m and with 159-196% for the trees planted at 4x1 and 4x 0.5 m. Settling orchards with density of up to 2500 trees/ ha is possible and is recommended, in these cases the production obtained on small surfaces (1-5 ha) is of 30-150 tons.

Keywords: superintensive, peach cultivar, fruit production.

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INTRODUCTION

Cultivating trees in a super-intensive system is an increasingly common method for fruit-bearing species from the *pomoidae* subfamily, where the presence of rootstocks and low-vigor varieties offers wide possibilities for expanding plantations with a high density of trees per surface unit. Although relatively recent, the culture of the peach has gained a large scale in our country due to the special quality of the fruits, their very complex chemical composition and the large productions that can be obtained without much effort. The peach is a species little adapted to our climatic conditions, it suffers from frost in the winter, but it can ensure constant and large productions for 10-15 years (Blind, 2020). Peaches have the following in their composition: 10.4-16.2% dry matter, 5.4-11.9% total sugar, 0.36-0.44% total acidity, 12.6-21.5 mg% acid ascorbic, 0.3-0.6 g% pectins, 0.7-0.9 g% proteins, 0.07-0.16 g% tannoid substances, 0.03 mg% vitamin B1, 0.05 mg% vitamin B2, 0.90 mg% vitamin B6, 0.30 mg% vitamin A, 0.43

mg% vitamin E, a series of mineral ions: K, P, Mg, Ca, Na, Mn, Fe, Cu, Zn, etc., have an energy value of 29-64 calories per 100 g. Fruits are appreciated by consumers fresh or processed, in the form of compote, jam, juices, nectars, dehydrated, etc. (Cepoiu & co.,2008).

In the case of the peach species, the establishment of orchards with a high density of trees per hectare under the conditions of the presence in the culture of varieties and vigorous rootstocks was and is viewed with reserve by specialists. In Romania, peach culture is limited by the high demands on heat, the sensitivity shown by it to frost (Drăgănescu, 2006). The peach is a species with high heat requirements. It grows and develops in areas with an average annual temperature of 10-11.5°C. During the winter, it withstands temperatures of -24°C. Buds withstand temperatures of -3.9°C, and flowers abort at temperatures lower than -3°C (Asănică & Hoza, 2013).

The peach is resistant to prolonged drought, but for high productions, water becomes a limiting factor. In the absence of water, the peach fruits remain small, flattened,

the production being diminished both qualitatively and quantitatively. It reacts well to irrigation, especially in the period before the fruits ripen, thus obtaining significant increases in production.

Excess water in the soil, even for short periods, is harmful to the peach, causing asphyxiation of the roots. The high humidity in the air favors the establishment of diseases, and the fog in winter amplifies the negative effects of the frost (Ghena & co, 2014).

The face of the light has high requirements, so that, to make good use of the solar radiation, the cuttings must ensure good ventilation of the crown, and the orchard must be located only on slopes with southern exposure. In the absence of light, the shoots grow little, the trees are sensitive to frost, and the production is weak from a quantitative or qualitative point of view. It is very precocious, bears fruit from the 2-3rd year after planting, has high fertility, differentiates very well, etc.

The peach forms a richly branched root system, with thick skeletal roots, mostly oriented relatively parallel to the soil surface and some of them penetrating vertically to great depths. The lateral extension of the roots exceeds 1.7-2 times the projection of the crown, and vertically most of them are spread between 20 and 80 cm, a few reach 3-4 m. Regardless of the planting density, the roots of neighboring peaches do not intertwine. Because of this, in older plantations, filling in gaps does not give results, the roots of young trees no longer find the necessary space to supply the tree with water and mineral salts. The roots have two growth maxima, in spring and autumn, when the soil is 8-20°C, considered the optimal temperature.

Being a very productive species, the peach reacts well to fertilization, the optimal ratio between N:P:K elements being 1:0.25:1. Annually, per ton of fruit, the peach consumes about: 10 kg of nitrogen, 2 kg of phosphorus, 8 kg of potassium and a series of microelements: Fe, Mg, B, Zn, etc. Depending on the age of the plantation, the number of fertilizers is different (Papouschek, 2022). Thus, in the young plantation apply per surface unit: 80 kg of nitrogen, 60 kg of phosphorus and 40 kg of potassium annually and periodically 25-30 t of manure, and in the mature plantation annually apply: 120-150 kg of nitrogen, 50 -60 kg of phosphorus and 90-120 kg of potassium, along with 40 t of manure applied every 2-3 years.

Irrigation of peach plantations is mandatory to obtain productive performance and appropriate quality. Through irrigation, it is possible to reach an increase in production of over 40% and an increase in the quality of the fruits, which makes it economical to water the peach. By irrigating the peach at the entrance to the field, it is possible to obtain a 20-25% increase in production. The amount of water applied at one watering is 400-600 m³/ha, enough to moisten the thickness of the soil profile where most of the roots are distributed, and the number of waterings is 4-5, depending on the climatic conditions. Critical water needs are before flowering, during endocarp hardening, before fruit ripening and after harvest. The most economical way of applying water is dripping, but furrow irrigation also gives good results.

The duration of economic exploitation of peach plantations is 12-15 years, sometimes longer for solitary trees. The peach bears fruit on mixed branches with a length of 40-60 cm, branches that bear many fruit buds placed in groups, usually three, of which one is vegetative, which implies the thinning of the fruits after the physiological fall in June. During fruiting, most of the mixed branches are exhausted, so that they are not of interest in the crown for the following years' production (Oprea & Ropan, 2010).

The peach is located on light, fertile soils and well exposed to the sun. If there is a slope, only the middle and upper third will be planted to avoid or reduce the effect of spring return frost. The peach cannot be planted after itself in any form, because the roots leave toxic substances in the soil (amygdalin which hydrolyzes and forms hydrocyanic acid), but it can be planted after an apple or pear. Planting is done in autumn or spring, depending on the amount of material to be planted and the climatic conditions (Smith, 2022).

The peach being generally self-fertile, there are no problems with arranging the varieties in the plot, to cross-pollinate (Wallin, 2020). The number of varieties that are planted is directly related to the way the fruits are used; if they are sold directly on the market, many varieties will be planted with a small number of trees, because the fruits are quite perishable, and if they are used through industrial processing, 2-3 varieties will be planted to ensure large batches of fruit, convenient processing plant. Selling on the market is convenient for producers near cities and in the coastal area. Due to the greater

sensitivity of the nectarine to powdering, it will be planted in groups or even in separate plots, which allows ensuring the appropriate phytosanitary protection (Wheeler, 2023).

Through the very varied assortment, fresh fruit can be produced and consumed for a long period of time, from the end of June to the end of October, ensuring both the market and canneries. Due to these advantages, peach culture should be expanded in all favorable areas (Schmid, 2021).

The first attempts made in the fruit-growing area of Oradea revealed the fact that as the peach planting distance in a row is reduced from 5 to 4, 3, 2 m, the vigor of the trees decreases by up to 31%, while the fruit production increases by up to at 67%.

To deepen these aspects to contribute to increasing the productivity and efficiency of this valuable species due to the increase in the density of trees per hectare using existing biological material, experiments were carried out with variants that included high densities of up to 10-20 thousand trees /Ha.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The experience was in Oradea in 2015 on weak brown soil with a slight slope with southern exposure and a clay content of over 36%. The amount of precipitation fluctuated from 471 mm in 2016 to 799 mm in 2019, so that in the last four years, the rainfall level was 50-120 mm higher than the normal 635 mm, the experience not being irrigated. Multiannual average temperature of 10.30 C it oscillated annually around this value, and there were no climatic accidents attributed to the lowered temperatures. The planting material was Suncrest, Padana, Michelin, and frank peach as rootstock. The agrotechnical level applied was an ordinary one, obtained with soil maintenance, cultivated field and annual fertilization not N₁₅₀, P 1₅₀, K 1₅₀ kg/ha, active substance, and green and dry cuttings.

The observations and determinations referred to the increase in trunk thickness, fruit production and their quality in terms of size and dry matter content.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The increase in the thickness of the trunk is shown in table 1. It is found that the diameter of the trunk decreases as the distance between the trees in a row decreases from 5, 4, 3 and 2 m by up to 36%.

Table 1

Planting distance (trees/ha)	Cultivar			Average cultivar x distance	%
	Michelin	Padana	Suncrest		
V1= 4x 3 m= 833 trees/ ha	16.5	13.1	17.4	15.7	100
V2= 4 x 2 m= 1250 trees/ ha	19.9	15.4	17.9	17.7	112
V3= 4x 1 m= 2500 trees/ ha	15.0	12.1	13.6	13.6	87
V3= 4 x 0.5 m= 5000 trees/ ha	11.1	10.2	11.5	10.9	69
Average distance x cultivar	15.6	12.3	15.1	14.5	-

It is found that the simple thickening of trees in a row can reduce the vigor of the trees by up to 36% in the first 9 years after planting, a fact that opens the possibility of designing and implementing in the field orchards with a larger number of trees per surface unit. In table 1, the row distance was 3 m, then 2, 1 and 0.5 m, returning 833, 1250, 2500 and 500 trees/ha, the vigor of the trees at the end of the 3rd year from planting follows an almost identical trend to the first experience, the trees planted at distances of 1 and 0.5 m per row being 13 and 31% thinner compared to those planted at 3 m. Depending on the variety, the decrease in tree vigor as the nutrition space decreases is more reduced in the Padana variety, which is 23%, while the more vigorous Suncrest and Michelin varieties reduce their trunk thickness more by up to 38% as the distance of planting per row decreased to 0.5 m.

In table 2, including fruit production in the fourth year after planting, there are big differences depending on the number of trees planted per hectare. Following the values given in this table, we are convinced that as the trees were planted at smaller distances, the production per surface unit increased by 4, 7.8 and 9.3 t/ha, by planting 1250, 2500 and 5000 trees compared to the variant which includes 833 trees/ha.

Table 2

Planting distance (trees/ha)	Fruit production (t/ha)			Average cultivar x distance	Difference of distance	%
	Michelin	Padana	Suncrest			
V1= 4x 3 m= 833 trees/ ha	3.0	4.4	6.6	4.7	-	100
V2= 4 x 2 m= 1250 trees/ ha	7.0	8.9	10.5	8.8	4.1+	187
V3= 4x 1 m= 2500 trees/ ha	9.4	12.3	15.1	12.2	7.8 ⁺⁺	259
V3= 4 x 0.5 m= 5000 trees/ ha	12.8	10.1	18.9	14.0	9.3 ⁺⁺⁺	298
Average distance x cultivar	8.5	8.9	12.7	10.0	-	
DL 5%	3.58					
DL 1%	5.42					
DL 0.1%	8.70					

Table 3

Planting distance (trees/ha)	Average fruit weight (g)			Average cultivar x distance	%
	Suncrest	Padana	Michelin		
V1= 4x 3 m= 833 trees/ ha	88	123	166	126	100
V2= 4 x 2 m= 1250 trees/ ha	81	112	171	121	96
V3= 4x 1 m= 2500 trees/ ha	83	108	165	119	94
V3= 4 x 0.5 m= 5000 trees/ ha	84	100	152	112	89
Average distance x cultivar	84	111	164	-	-

The quality expressed by the average weight of a fruit is shown in table 3.

As expected, the differences under this aspect are primarily related to the variety, in the sense that they are larger from the Suncrest variety to the Michelin variety, which doubles its weight, making 6 fruits per kilogram. Depending on the nutrition space, a decrease in weight is observed, the variant with 5000 trees/ha presenting 11% smaller fruits, respectively instead of 8 fruits per kilogram, this variant presents 8, 9 fruits/kg. The slight tendency to reduce fruit weight can be greatly reduced by fertilization and differentiated irrigation depending on the number of trees/ha.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research undertaken in several stages, extended over a period of 9 years in which planting distances from 4 m to 0.25 m per row were experimented, the following conclusions can be formulated: the reduction of the nutrition space achieved by decreasing the distance of planting per row influences the vigor of the trees expressed by the thickness of the trunk, which is reduced by almost 40% compared to trees planted at standard distances; the production of fruits obtained under planting conditions of over 1250 trees/ha doubles and reaches average annual values of 20 t/ha. The further increase in the number of trees/ha by restricting the nutrition space per row and between rows proved beneficial for production up to the level of 5-10 thousand trees/ha, when over 30 t/ha, the average harvest, was recorded, after which reducing the nutrition space by planting a larger number of trees per surface unit leads to the

capping of the yield curve and then to its sudden decrease; the quality of the fruits obtained from the variants with trees planted at small distances has a slight tendency to decrease in terms of average weight, but this can be corrected by resorting to known agrotechnical means such as fertilization, irrigation; the super-intensive system that is envisioned to be promoted following these results has, in addition to the economic component given by the very high production and the reduction of expenses per ton of fruit, and a social side in the sense that on small areas of 1-5 ha, large quantities of fruits for industrialization and in fresh condition of the order of 30-150 tons annually.

The super-intensive peach cultivation system still needs to be perfected in terms of the production of planting material, the establishment of plantations, fertilization, and irrigation to make it more efficient and easier to exploit by an average qualified staff.

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DETERMINATION OF THE CONTENT OF ASSIMILATORY PIGMENTS IN VITRO CULTURES OF *Echinopsis chamaecereus f. lutea*, EXPOSED TO LIGHT EMITTED BY FLUORESCENT TUBES OF DIFFERENT COLORS AND WAVELENGTHS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

As a result of spontaneous mutations in cactus cultures, today we enjoy the unprecedented beauty of chlorophyll-deficient cacti, a phenomenon largely influenced by temperature and light, the number of chloroplasts in these species does not normally exceed one third of all plastids, the rest is mutated and are without possibility to synthesize chlorophyll. In the current experiment we used explants of *Echinopsis chamaecereus f. lutea*, the chlorophyll-deficient cactus, inoculated on culture media without growth regulators and exposed to the light of white or colored fluorescent tubes, respectively, blue, yellow, green and red, the control sample being exposed in natural light.

After 90 days of in vitro culture, we extracted the assimilatory pigments - chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and carotenoid pigments - separately from each experimental variant grown under fluorescent tube lights of different colors and wavelengths and compared it with similar parameter values from the control variant - vitro culture grown in natural light (N1) - data considered as representing 100%.

The results differed depending on the wavelength and color of the light emitted by the fluorescent tubes. We can conclude that regardless of the color emitted by the fluorescent tubes, in the explants of *Echinopsis chamaecereus f. lutea*, carotenoid pigments accumulated in a much greater amount than chlorophyll a and b, a phenomenon probably due to the fact that this cactus is a chlorophyll-deficient species. Among the chlorophylls, chlorophyll was synthesized in greater quantity in the case of phytoinoculae grown under the yellow light of fluorescent tubes.

Keywords: vitro culture, fluorescent tubes, chlorophyll a and b, carotenoid pigments

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INTRODUCTION

In its evolution, the plant world has adapted so that plants are able to exploit light energy in the development of physiological processes. For this purpose they have acquired a wide range of photoreceptors that perceive and respond to the stimulus of the light spectrum, quantifying the period, direction, quality and intensity of light (Galvao V.C. and Fankhauser C., 2015; Volta K. and Carvalho S.D., 2015).

The existence of vitroplants is due to the presence of carbohydrates in the culture medium and is not strictly conditioned by the realization of photosynthesis, they are mixotrophs, but light affects a series of physiological reactions, phenomena closely related to the optical characteristics of chlorophyll (Ptushenko et al, 2020, Seyedi et al., 2024).

The visible spectrum of solar radiation, the photoenergetic and photochemical effects exerted on plants include the following emission wavelengths (in nm): 380-400 (violet), 400-480 (indigo), 480-500 (blue), 500 - 580 (green), 580-600 (yellow), 600-650 (orange) and 650-780 (red) (Nassau K. , 2024). Light does not have the same type of influence on all plants, it acts differently depending on the species and the color of the light, so the use of fluorescent tubes of different lighting colors in vitro cultures is becoming more and more used, especially after the discovery of the benefits arising from their use. (Frade et al, 2023; Gonçalves et al, 2023)

According to (Van Ieperen and Trouwborst, 2008, Sontag-González M., et al, 2022), artificial light sources can be calibrated to emit a specific wavelength, so that in order to provide plants with optimal light conditions, they they look through filters to be able to stop

UV radiation and their light can be directed or can choose the most effective viewing angle for plants. There are currently studies to determine how many photons of a given wavelength induce plant growth and development (Friesen, 2024).

Chlorophyll-deficient cacti, due to their very different shapes and colors, represent a completely unusual but highly appreciated occurrence. This fact has determined the emergence of a true extremely profitable industry, in countries such as the Netherlands, Japan, Korea, Germany and others where new technologies are currently being sought for the rapid and economically efficient multiplication of these plants (Smith et al, 2021).

In the current experiment, as a continuation of the experiments carried out by us (Vidican et al., 2010), we used as biological material chlorophyll-deficient cactus with the stated aim of studying changes in the content of assimilatory pigments (chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and carotenoid pigments) from the vitroplants of *Echinopsis chamaecereus f. lutea* illuminated - for 90 days - with fluorescent lamps of different colors compared to those illuminated with natural light (N1), considered as the control sample.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The plant material was sterilized by immersion in ethyl alcohol at 96° for one minute, after which it was covered with a 0.8% sodium hypochlorite solution, mixed 1:2 with sterile water to which was added, as a surfactant, three drops of Tween 20 (Cachiță et al., 2004), stirring continuously for 20 minutes.

The future inocula are represented by buds of *Echinopsis chamaecereus f. lutea* sized so that each contains 3-4 areoles (Vidican and Cachiță, 2011) and approximately 1 cm long, 0.5 cm thick and a diameter of 0.5-1, 5 cm, (fig.1).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of how operating fragments *Echinopsis chamaecereus f. lutea* to be inoculated aseptic environments.

Explants were inoculated on basic medium (MB) (Murashige and Skoog, 1962),

microelements (Heller, 1953), to which vitamins were added: pyridoxine HCl, thiamine HCl and nicotinic acid (each 1 mg/l), 100 mg/l myo-inositol, 30 g/l sucrose and 7 g/l agar - agar, the pH of the medium - prior to its autoclaving - was set at a value of 5.7. Culture media do not contain growth regulators.

The inoculum vials were transported and placed in the growth chamber, where the temperature varied between 20 and 24°C.

For this experiment, when lighting the vitro cultures of *Echinopsis chamaecereus f. lutea*, white or colored fluorescent tubes, respectively blue, yellow, green or red, were used as a light source (fig.2). The control sample (N1) was exposed to natural light. We obtained the following experimental series:

N1 - vitro cultures exposed to natural light - data considered as 100% reference values.

And depending on the color of the light generated by the fluorescent tubes, we obtained several variants, as follows:

N2 - white fluorescent light ($\lambda=400\text{nm}$);

N3 - blue fluorescent light ($\lambda=470\text{nm}$);

N4 - yellow fluorescent light ($\lambda=580\text{nm}$);

N5 - green fluorescent light ($\lambda=540\text{nm}$);

N6 - red fluorescent light ($\lambda=670\text{nm}$);

The extraction of assimilatory pigments for each experimental variant was carried out with pure dimethylformamide (DMF 99.9%). The working method consisted of crushing a 50 mg fragment of cladodes in 5 ml DMF [after Moran and Porath, 1980]; the obtained composition was kept for 72 hours at 4°C, then the supernatant was decanted and the resulting solution was determined for the assimilatory pigment content through a photometric extract with a SPEKOL 11 type spectrophotometer. In the present operation, the determination of the pigments in the liquid samples photometric extract was done using selective filters with different wavelengths, as follows: 664 nm for chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and 647 nm to 480 nm for carotenoid pigments. Five repetitions were made for each experimental variant.

The obtained data were processed by photometric mathematical formulas, as proposed by [Moran and Porath (1980)]. Averages of five replicates/experimental variant were performed. By summing the average data obtained from the measurements of chlorophyll a, with those from the tests carried out to identify the level of chlorophyll b, the total content of green pigment was obtained, by adding these figures of the

average values, a complete content of the result in carotenoid pigments was obtained, resulting in a complete picture of the level of assimilatory pigments determined in vitro in

Figure 2. In vitro cultures of *Echinopsis chamaecereus f. lutea*, illuminated with fluorescent tubes that emit light of different colors, respectively, different wavelengths. Where: 1-white light ($\lambda=400\text{nm}$); 2-blue light ($\lambda=470\text{nm}$); 3-yellow light ($\lambda=580\text{nm}$); 4-green light ($\lambda=540\text{nm}$); 5-red light ($\lambda=670\text{nm}$); a-culture medium; b-phyto inoculum.

Statistical analysis was performed using analysis of variance or the Anova test for completely randomized multifactorial experiments. By entering the data, I obtained the following general data:

The monitored indicator: the amount of pigments

Unit of measure: mg/g

Number of factors: 2

Number of repetitions: 3

The N factor – the color emitted by the fluorescent tube – 6 graduations

Witness

Factor P – type of pigment – 3 graduations

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Following the observations made at 90 days in the current experiment, from the data presented in table 1, it is noted that variant N1 (control sample, values considered to be 100%) in vitro seedlings grown in natural light accumulated the largest amount of assimilatory pigments, respectively, 0.28 mg pigments/g plant material while in vitro seedlings grown in the green light of fluorescent tubes (N5) with 0.05 mg pigments/g plant material recorded the lowest value of this parameter which represents a minus of 81.9%. The best result was recorded in vitro with seedlings grown under the blue light of fluorescent tubes (N3) where with 0.15 mg pigments/g plant material a deficit of 46.3% was found, followed by in vitro seedlings grown under the incidence of white light neonates (N2) which, with 0.14 mg pigments/g plant material, shows a minus of 50.9% compared to the control N1. In vitro seedlings grown under yellow (N4) and red

Echinopsis chamaecereus f. lutea plants after 90 days of culture in vitro, exposed to different lighting regimes.

(N6) neon lights assimilated 0.07 mg pigments/g plant material, which represents a minus of 74.8%. In the case of this parameter, in all experimental variants the difference compared to the control was statistically very significantly negative (table 1).

Table 1
The influence of the N factor (light type) on the quantity of pigments

Cr. no.	Vari ant	Absolute production of pigmenți mg/g	Relative production of pigmenți %	$\pm d$ g/mg	Signifi cance
1	N1	0,28	100,0	0,00	Mt
2	N2	0,14	49,1	-0,14	000
3	N3	0,15	53,7	-0,13	000
4	N4	0,07	25,2	-0,21	000
5	N5	0,05	18,1	-0,23	000
6	N6	0,07	25,2	-0,21	000

$Dl_{5\%}=0,03$

$Dl_{1\%}=0,05$

$Dl_{0,1\%}=0,07$

Table 2 shows the influence of the P factor (pigment type) on the amount of pigments assimilated by in vitro seedlings exposed to different colored light from fluorescent tubes, it can be noted that carotenoid pigments (P3) have the largest contribution to the amount of synthesized pigments expressed in mg pigments/g plant material, thus with 0.36 mg carotenoid pigments/g plant material this parameter was above control P0 by 186%. This result being considered from a statistically significant positive point of view.

Table 2.
The influence of the P factor (pigment type) on the amount of pigments

Cr. no	Vari- ant	Absolute production of pigmenți mg/g	Relative production of pigmenți %	± d g/mg	Signifi- cance
1	P0	0,13	100,0	0,00	Mt
2	P1	0,01	7,6	-0,12	000
3	P2	0,01	7,6	-0,12	000
4	P3	0,36	286	0,23	xxx

DL5%=0,02 DL1%=0,03 DL0,1%=0,04

The influence of chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b on the amount of pigments assimilated by in vitro seedlings exposed to different colored light from fluorescent tubes is below the control P0 with 0.12 mg chlorophyll a and b/g plant material which represents a deficit of 92.4%, provided statistically very significant negative compared to the witness.

Table 3.
The interaction of the factor P (type of pigment) to N (type of light)

Cr no	Vari- ant	Absolute productio n of pigmenți g/mg	Relative productio n of pigmenți %	± d g/mg	Signifi- cance
1	P0 N1	0,28	100,0	0,00	Mt.
2	P1N1	0,01	3,6	-0,27	000
3	P2N1	0,03	10,2	-0,26	000
3	P3N1	0,81	286	0,53	xxx
5	P0N2	0,14	100,0	0,00	Mt.
6	P1N2	0,01	6,3	-0,13	000
7	P2N2	0,01	6,3	-0,13	000
8	P3N2	0,81	286	0,27	xxx
9	P0N3	0,15	100,0	0,00	Mt
10	P1N3	0,04	24,2	-0,12	000
11	P2N3	0,02	11,6	-0,14	000
12	P3N3	0,74	264,3	0,25	xxx
13	P0N4	0,07	100,0	0,00	Mt.
14	P1N4	0,01	6,3	-0,07	0
15	P2N4	0,01	6,3	-0,07	0
16	P3N4	0,79	281,5	0,13	xxx
17	P0N5	0,05	100,0	0,00	Mt.
18	P1N5	0,01	17,1	-0,04	-
19	P2N5	0,01	17,1	-0,04	-
20	P3N5	0,77	274,2	0,09	xxx
21	P0N6	0,07	100,0	0,00	Mt.
22	P1N6	0,01	12,3	-0,06	0
23	P2N6	0,01	12,3	-0,06	0
24	P3N6	0,79	281,5	0,13	xxx

DL5%=0,05 DL1%=0,07 DL0,1%=0,09

The interaction between the two factors P (type of pigment) and N (type of light) is presented in table 3. It should be noted that the carotenoid pigments (P3) showed a significant increase compared to the control (P0) regardless of the color of the light emitted by fluorescent tubes. Thus, the variant P3N1 the amount of carotenoid pigments in vitro

seedlings grown under natural light and P3N2 the amount of carotenoid pigments in vitro seedlings grown under the white light of fluorescent tubes exceeded the control (0.28 mg/g plant material) by 0.53 mg carotenoid pigments/g plant material, which represents an increase of 186%. With 0.79 mg carotenoid pigments/g plant material, the varieties P3N4 (in vitro plants grown under yellow light) and P3N6 (in vitro plants grown under red light) had an increase of 181.5% compared to the control, while with 0.77 mg carotenoid pigments/g plant material, the P3N5 variant (in vitro plants grown under green light) recorded an increase of 174.2% compared to the control. P3N3 (in vitro plants grown under blue light) with 0.74 mg carotenoid pigments/g plant material has an increase of 164.3% compared to the control. For all the variants presented, the differences compared to the control were statistically very significantly positive.

In the case of seedlings grown in vitro under yellow light, the amount of chlorophyll a (P1N5) and chlorophyll b (P2N5) with an absolute value of 0.01 mg pigment/g plant material recorded a deficit of 82.9%, in which case none of the values exceeded the LD5%=0.05 threshold and thus were not statistically assured.

In the variants of *Echinopsis chamaecereus* f. *lutea* grown under yellow light, the amount of chlorophyll a (P1N4) and chlorophyll b (P2N4) is 0.27 mg pigment/g plant material lower than in the control, thus in these variants a minus 82.9%, we find the same absolute values recorded in vitro for seedlings grown under red light (P1N6) and (P2N6) where a deficit of 83.7% is noted. Variants where the difference was ensured statistically negative, significant.

From table 3, it can be seen that in vitro seedlings grown both in natural light and in the white or blue light of fluorescent tubes recorded absolute values of chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b below the control value, differences that from a statistical point of view were ensured very negative significant.

Analyzing the data from table 4, namely the influence of the color of the light emitted by the fluorescent tubes on the amount of pigments: chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and carotenoid pigments, it is observed that; chlorophyll a has the highest absolute value of 0.04 mg/g plant material in the case of *phytoinocula* grown under the yellow light of

fluorescent tubes which represents an increase of 258.3%, however it did not exceed the threshold of $DL5\% = 0.05$ and thus the value is not statistically assured. In the case of the other variants grown under the incidence of white, blue, green or red neon lights, a chlorophyll a deficit of 56.3% is noted, values not statistically guaranteed.

The absolute values of chlorophyll b synthesized in vitro *Chamaecereus f. lutea* cultures were below the control (0.03 mg/g plant material), thus with 0.02 mg/g plant material in vitro the cultures grown under blue light (N3P2) a minus of 38.8% was found, while in vitro cultures grown under white, green, yellow and red neon lights this parameter was 0.01 mg/g plant material, registering a deficit of 69.6%. Values that did not exceed the threshold of $LD5\% = 0.05$ and thus are not statistically assured.

Table 4.
The interaction of the factor N (type of light) to P (type of pigment)

Cr no	Varianta	Absolute production of pigmenți g/mg	Relative production of Pigmenți %	$\pm d$ g/mg	Significanțe
1	N1P1	0,01	100,0	0,00	Mt
2	N2P1	0,00	43,7	-0,01	-
3	N3P1	0,04	358,3	0,03	-
3	N4P1	0,00	43,7	-0,01	-
5	N5P1	0,00	43,7	-0,01	-
6	N6P1	0,00	43,7	-0,01	-
7	N1P2	0,03	100,0	0,00	Mt
8	N2P2	0,01	30,4	-0,02	-
9	N3P2	0,02	61,2	-0,01	-
10	N4P2	0,01	30,4	-0,02	-
11	N5P2	0,01	30,4	-0,02	-
12	N6P2	0,01	30,4	-0,02	-
13	N1P3	0,81	100,0	0,00	Mt
14	N2P3	0,41	49,9	-0,41	000
15	N3P3	0,40	49,6	-0,41	000
16	N4P3	0,20	24,8	-0,61	000
17	N5P3	0,14	17,4	-0,67	000
18	N6P3	0,20	24,8	-0,61	000

$DL5\% = 0,05$

$DL1\% = 0,07$

$DL0,1\% = 0,10$

As for carotenoid pigments, compared to the control, they showed different values influenced by the color of the light to which the in vitro cultures were exposed. The highest values of this parameter are below 0.81 mg/g plant material, a value recorded in the control, so in vitro cultures grown under the white light of fluorescent tubes (N2P3) showed 0.41 mg carotenoid pigments/g plant material, closely followed by in vitro cultures grown under the blue light of fluorescent tubes (N2P3), with 0.40 mg/g plant material, which represents a deficit of 50.1% and 50.4%, respectively. The

variants grown under the yellow (N4P3) and red (N6P3) light of fluorescent tubes recorded an absolute value of this parameter of 0.20 mg carotenoid pigments/g plant material and the in vitro culture grown under green light (N5P3) synthesized 0.14 mg carotenoid pigments/g plant material, a deficit of 75.25 and 82.6% corresponding to the N5P3 variant was recorded. %. In all the variants presented above, the difference was ensured statistically negatively, very significantly.

CONCLUSIONS

1. After 90 days from the initiation of in vitro culture in *Chamaecereus f. lutea*, different values of the assimilative pigment content are noted: chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and carotenoid pigments depending on the wavelength and color of the light emitted by the fluorescent tubes.

2. The light factor directly influenced the amount of pigments, natural light proving to determine the highest value of this parameter, followed by the blue light of fluorescent tubes, the minimum value was found to be recorded in vitro seedlings grown in green light of neons.

3. It is noted that carotenoid pigments (P3) have the largest contribution to the amount of synthesized pigments, thus with 0.36 mg carotenoid pigments/g plant material this parameter was above the control P0 by 186%.

4. In the interaction between the two factors P (type of pigment) and N (type of light) it is found that carotenoid pigments show a significant increase compared to the control (P0) regardless of the color of the light emitted by the fluorescent tubes, a phenomenon probably due to the fact that *Chamaecereus f. lutea* is a chlorophyll deficient cactus.

5. The yellow color of the light emitted by fluorescent tubes directly influenced the amount of chlorophyll a, in vitro cultures grown under this color showed an increase of 258.3% compared to the control.

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THE ORIGIN OF THE WOODY SPECIES OF PINES CULTIVATED IN THE SYLVA ARBORETUM IN GURAHONȚ, ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The Sylva Arboretum, located in Gurahonț, Romania, serves as a key site for the research and conservation of tree species, including pines. This arboretum boasts a remarkable assortment of tree species from around the world, with a particular focus on the origins of pine species, which are the subject of this study. The present work delves into the origins of the pines planted here, highlighting their ecological diversity. Through a meticulous analysis of the collected data, it was established that the majority of these species originate from Europe, North America, and Asia, with a particular emphasis on native species from the Carpathian Mountains. Furthermore, the research underscores the importance of introducing and acclimatizing exotic species, which play a crucial role in enhancing biodiversity and promoting ecological stability. The findings of this study have significant implications for the sustainable management of forest resources and biodiversity conservation amidst the challenges posed by climate change. In summary, the Sylva Arboretum exemplifies an effective model for the conservation and study of pine tree species, illustrating the critical need to integrate traditional knowledge with contemporary scientific approaches in the management of forest ecosystems.

Keywords: arboretum sylva, pinus, forest ecosystem, Biodiversity, Forest resources

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INTRODUCTION

The distinguished forestry engineer Eusebiu Ștefan took on the significant task of identifying and utilizing the geographical area known to the inhabitants of that period as the "old park," located within the picturesque boundaries of the Honțisor Valley, in the Gurahonț commune of Arad County. Both the Monograph of the Park, written by the esteemed engineer Eusebiu Ștefan in 1992, and the SYLVA Arboretum 1983, explicitly state that the "Garden Journal" contains a comprehensive account detailing the origins of this notable park. This documentation clarifies that between 1882 and 1889, significant efforts and steps were taken toward establishing a unique dendrological park, designed to encompass a layout defined by trees and flowers, accompanied meticulously by detailed planting instructions and cultivation guidelines. Furthermore, the aforementioned journal reveals that the initial plantings within the limits of Gurahonț began as early as 1750, with various botanists making observations starting in 1883.

During this crucial period, the construction of the Arad-Brad railway was also underway, a project that began in 1885. It is noteworthy that the land upon which the "Sylva" Arboretum now stands was once part of the estate owned by Benjamin Boroș, who, with great foresight, developed this area into a space for recreation, cultivating both native and exotic plant species and maintaining the land with the diligence characteristic of a true nature enthusiast.

Upon the unfortunate death of Benjamin Boroș, the estate, which had been lovingly cared for, was inherited by his son, who, being a lawyer and lacking the necessary knowledge, made the decision to sell the property. Following the sale of this historically significant land, it fell into neglect and degradation, resulting in numerous destructive actions, including the removal of trees, acts which could be considered criminal, particularly cases of abusive grazing that further exacerbated the deterioration of the ecosystem.

In light of these unfortunate circumstances, in 1965, forestry engineer

Eusebiu Ștefan, visiting the site once known as the park, found it in a completely deplorable state, characterized by destruction, overcrowding, and extensive grazing, with parts of the area being used by certain individuals as an improvised refuge and recreational spot.

Subsequent to 1965, initial efforts were launched with the aim of transforming this neglected land area into a dendrological botanical garden, commonly referred to as an Arboretum, covering an area of 4.6 hectares, which represented the historical extent of the old park. It was also here that engineer Eusebiu Ștefan succeeded in expanding this park by an additional 8 hectares, ultimately recording the presence of 2,578 taxa with 3,465 specimens.

In the period after 1990, the efforts of engineer Eusebiu Ștefan to keep the entire area 12.6 ha were in vain because optimal solutions were not found to fairly reconcile the former owners of the land. Due to the resulting situation, in the period that followed only the initial area of 4.6 ha benefited from adequate care, to the detriment of the collection made on 8 ha. As argued by F. Morozan (2018): The negative effect of the authority of *res judicata* refers to the party who lost the trial, as he can no longer call into question his right in another trial. Thus, a solution agreed at the local level was found, and in 2003, by a decision of the Gurahonț local council, the Sylva Arboretum entered the custody of the University of Oradea for a period of 49 years. Since 2015, the University of Oradea, the West University of Timisoara and the University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Banat, have joined a consortium for the management of the park.

In a broad and comprehensive examination of the climatic variable of temperature in the specified geographical region over the analyzed time period, it can be conclusively stated that:

- The annual average temperature fluctuates between 8.8°C and 12.2°C, which is considered extremely favorable for the vigorous and healthy growth of various plantation species. Moreover, the conclusions outlined above also apply to observations regarding the recorded annual minimum and maximum average temperatures during the same period. Analytical evaluation suggests that the soil composition in this region is predominantly classified as sandy clay, characterized by a significant presence of particles ranging from 0.2

to 1.002 mm in size, constituting approximately 57.2% of the total soil composition.

- Furthermore, the soil exhibits a slightly acidic reaction, as indicated by the low pH value of 5.65, which suggests an acidity level that may influence the biological and chemical processes occurring in this soil ecosystem..

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The SYLVA Arboretum is geographically located at 46°15'59" N, 22°20'47" E (Google Earth, 2024).

For determining the results, all pine specimens cultivated in the Sylva Arboretum were identified from the archive, with specifications regarding their origin.

Field data were collected to verify the presence or absence of these specimens, as well as their characteristics (height, number of existing specimens, health status). It should be noted that data were collected only for the 19 plots currently managed in this study.

The data were collected during the 2023-2024 period. The biomorphological analysis of the woody plants in the SYLVA Arboretum was conducted according to the criteria set by Sokolov S.Ya. and Sviazeva O.A. (1965), and more recently utilized by E., A. Parakhina et al. (2021), as follows:

- D1 – tree size I (height greater than 20 m);
- D2 – tree size II (height 16-20 m);
- D3 – tree size III (height 11-15 m);
- D4 – tree size IV (height up to 10 m);
- K1 – shrub grade I (height greater than 6 m);
- K2 – shrub grade II (height 4-6 m);
- K3 – shrub grade III (height 2-4 m);
- To4 – shrub grade IV (height up to 2 m).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Arboretums represent meticulously curated botanical gardens primarily dedicated to the extensive collection, careful cultivation, and comprehensive study of a diverse range of trees and shrubs. These remarkable sanctuaries fulfill multiple functions, encompassing scientific research, conservation efforts, educational initiatives aimed at both students and the general public, as well as recreational opportunities that allow individuals to engage with nature.

The significance of arboretums lies not only in their ability to conserve biodiversity by providing living collections that serve as essential resources for ecological and evolutionary research, but also in their capacity to offer invaluable educational experiences to

learners of all ages, thereby enhancing public understanding of botanical sciences. Moreover, these vital landscapes contribute to broader urban greening initiatives and play a crucial role in environmental conservation efforts aimed at mitigating the impacts of urbanization and promoting ecological sustainability.

In essence, arboretums are not merely repositories of plant life but dynamic centers of

knowledge that foster a deeper appreciation for the natural world and highlight the importance of conserving the diverse ecosystems of our planet. Ultimately, the multifaceted contributions of arboretums to society underscore their significance as both scientific institutions and community resources in the pursuit of environmental management and education.

Figure 1 Specimens of *Pinus sylvestris* L., remaining from the old park of Benjamin Boros

Figure 2 Specimen of *Pinus pinaster* Aiton and *Pinus armandii* Franch, Sylva Arboretum 2024

Table 1

The Origin and Characteristics of Pine Trees in the Sylva Arboretum

No.	The Name	Size				Identification / Plot number	The number of specimens	The health condition	The origin
		D1	D2	D3	D4				
1	<i>Pinus banksiana</i> Lamb			*		146/IV	1	Good	Montreal Canada
2	<i>Pinus nigra</i> var. <i>Poiretiana</i> (Ant) Asch et Graebn		*			17/V	1	Good	Kamoni Ungaria
3	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> L.		*	*		21/V 102/VI	1 1	Good	Gurahonț Romania
4	<i>Pinus strobus</i> L.		*			44/V	1	Good	Simeria România
5	<i>Pinus dalmatica</i> Ait			*		77/V	1	Broken tree top	Kiev (Foemina) Ucraina
6	<i>Pinus ponderosa</i> Laws		*	*		81/V 83/V	1 1	Good	Bazos Romania
7	<i>Pinus Armandi</i> Franch		*			96/V	1	Good	Kamoni Ungaria
8	<i>Pinus koraiensis</i> SZ		*			103/5	1	Good	Potsdam Germania
9	<i>Pinus resinosa</i> Ait		*			116/V	1	Good	Bazos Romania
10	<i>Pinus peuce</i> Griseb			*		11/VI	1	Good	Kamoni Ungaria
11	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> „ <i>Glauca</i> „			*		19/VI	1	Good	Kamoni Ungaria
12	<i>Pinus pinaster</i> L.		*			57/VI	1	Good	Nancy Franta
13	<i>Pinus pinaster</i> Ait „ <i>Magrebiana</i> „		*			85/VI	1	Good	Antibes Franta
14	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> var. <i>hamata</i> Stev		*	*		128/VII 138/VII	1 1	Good	Chorog Tadjikistan
15	<i>Pinus nigra</i> var. <i>Poiretiana</i> (Ant)Aschers			*		147/VII	1	Good	Kamoni Ungaria
16	<i>Pinus nigra</i> var. <i>caramanica</i> (Loud)Rehd			*		166/VII 196/VII	1 1	Good	Soci Rusia
17	<i>Pinus monticola</i> Lamb			*		77/XI 78/XI	1 1	Good	Liege Belgia
18	<i>Pinus rigida</i> Mill		*			96/IX	1	Good	Otawa Canada
19	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> L. var. <i>mongolica</i> Litvin		*			85/XIII	1	Good	Snagov Romania
20	<i>Pinus Thunbergii</i> Parl			*		89/XIII	1	Good	Snagov Romania
21	<i>Pinus armandi</i> Franch				*	90/XIV	1	Good	Alba Iulia Romania
22	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> L. var. <i>mongolica</i> Litv			*		96/XIV	1	Good	Snagov Romania
23	<i>Pinus mugo</i> Turra		*			118/XVI	1	Good	Iasi Romania
24	<i>Pinus kokiana</i> Klotz ex C. Koch		*			96/XVIII	1	Good	Pamir Tadjikistan
25	<i>Pinus sosnowskii</i> Nakai		*			105/XVIII	1	Good	Tbilisi Georgia

CONCLUSIONS

The origin and characteristics of the pine specimens meticulously cataloged in the esteemed Sylva Arboretum are notable for the fact that a substantial majority, constituting a significant 50%, originates from Romania. This can be easily explained by referring to the comprehensive monograph expertly authored by the distinguished engineer Eusebiu Ștefan. This situation is contextualized within the historical framework of the Communist regime, which predominated in earlier periods, a time when establishing correspondence and maintaining communication with other institutions and similar entities in the same field of study was exceedingly difficult. It appears that a remarkable collaboration existed between engineer Eusebiu Ștefan and several entities located within the geographical confines of Hungary, as evidenced by the interesting statistics indicating that the percentage of pine specimens cultivated in the arboretum is an impressive 17% of the total pine species cultivated in this sanctuary.

The provenance of pine taxa, accounting for 7%, is deduced to be from both Canada and France based on the empirical data collected in the current investigation. The provenance of pine taxa, comprising 4%, has been established for Ukraine, while a uniform percentage of 3% is recorded for each of the following nations: Germany, Russia, Belgium, Tajikistan, and Georgia.

Debazac E.F. (1964) argues that pines, except for those species whose native habitats are specifically mountainous or subalpine regions, have not withstood the harsh conditions of the Hort de Dieu. ("Thus, large reforestation species such as Scots pine, Austrian black pine, and Corsican pine yielded poor or mediocre results. The failure of American-origin pines (*P. strobus*, *P. rigida*, *P. ponderosa*, *P. banksiana*) has been more or less complete. Only mountain pines, such as *Pinus cembra*, *P. pence*, *P. leucodermis*, *P. uncinata*, and *P. pumilio*, are vigorous, though all grow slowly.")

The various species within the genus *Pinus*, when situated within the confines of an arboretum, play an extremely crucial role in enhancing the local ecosystem, not only by increasing biodiversity but also by facilitating processes associated with ecological restoration. These species simultaneously exert a significant influence on the interactions between the various species within that ecosystem. These multifaceted contributions can be viewed as

encompassing a wide range of direct and indirect ecological functions that are vital for maintaining ecological balance. More specifically, the presence of different *Pinus* species serves to create and support suitable habitats for a multitude of diverse organisms, aids in the restoration of degraded areas, and influences the complex dynamics of plant communities through intricate mechanisms involving both interspecies competition and their potential for coexistence in a shared environment.

With regard to biodiversity enhancement, *Pinus* species can support a diverse range of plant and animal species by providing habitat and resources. For instance, in Portugal, *Pinus pinaster* forests are associated with various taxonomic groups, and management decisions can enhance biodiversity conservation in these areas (Maia et al., n.d.). In Indonesia, *Pinus merkusii* forests support a variety of tree species, with 83 species recorded in different growth stages, indicating their role in maintaining species diversity (Supartono et al., 2023).

Another aspect is species diversity, where *Pinus* species can both support and inhibit biodiversity. In some cases, they facilitate the growth of native species by providing a habitat that mimics natural succession processes, as seen in the facilitation of endangered cloud forest species under *Pinus patula* plantations (María Luz et al., 2016).

Habitat provision: Pine forests can serve as important habitats for various species, including some that are endangered. They offer structural diversity that supports different life forms, although this can vary depending on management practices and site quality (Ponce et al., 2017).

Arboretum Sylva, currently appreciated and recognized as a vast and well-organized open-air laboratory, fundamentally dedicated to the rigorous study and systematic observation of a diverse range of plant life forms, serves as a vital component of the practical training and experiential learning of students enrolled in the Department of Forestry and Forest Engineering of the University of Oradea, with various educational activities and exercises carried out within its limits. The remarkable and diverse collection of pine species, together with a significant multitude of other tree species that have been carefully cultivated, carefully organized and strategically positioned in this special location, is poised to exert a profoundly

beneficial influence on ecological and environmental outcomes in the future.

Figure 3 Practical activity of students from the Department of Forestry and Forest Engineering, University of Oradea

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THE IMPACT OF LEGISLATION ON THE WOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Conformity to the Community normative act has generated a series of obligations for European economic operators, obligations that have influenced various aspects of economic-commercial operations and business strategy.

The compliance of economic operators with the legal obligations mentioned above generates bureaucracy and requires costs. The relatively high amount of costs can be of its nature to alter commercial competition, favoring larger and financially stronger companies. From the perspective of the final consumer/beneficiary, the high costs of the producer will be reflected in the increase of the final price of the purchased products.

Keywords: cost, bureaucracy, competition, price

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INTRODUCTION

The importance of wood in the economy is indisputable. Wood is a versatile and durable building material, used in the construction of houses, furniture, and other structures. It is preferred for its aesthetic and ecological properties.

Wood and derived products such as pellets and briquettes are important sources of renewable energy.

The use of wood for heating and energy production contributes to reducing dependence on fossil fuels and implicitly to protecting the environment. Wood is therefore a crucial element in the economy, having a significant impact on various industries and on sustainable development.

However, trade in wood of unregulated origin can have multiple risks and negative consequences: illegal deforestation and implicitly a harmful impact on the environment and human health.

These risks underscore the importance of strict regulation of the timber trade to protect the environment, the economy and public health.

Illegal logging – harvesting timber in a way that violates the laws or regulations of the country of harvest – has a serious economic, environmental and social impact on some of the world's most valuable forests and the communities that depend on them. It leads to loss of income, undermines the efforts of legal operators, and is associated with deforestation, biodiversity decline and greenhouse gas emissions, as well as conflicts over land and

resources, along with the disempowerment of indigenous communities.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The materials used in writing this paper are composed of legislation and web sites. The methods used are legal, namely the formal method, the comparative method, the logical and sociological method, the analytical method. The use of these methods has the role of performing a systematic analysis of the information from the studied sources in order to elaborate the points of view and the conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Illegal logging – harvesting wood in a way that violates the law – has a positive economic impact on the profitability of the beneficiary company, but a serious social and environmental impact on the countries from which the wood was harvested.

Compared to the higher financial possibilities, the companies from the countries of the European Union were among the final beneficiaries of the export of illegally exploited wood in the countries of origin.

In this context, in 2003 the European Union published the Forest, Law, Enforcement, Governance and Trade (FLEGT) Action Plan in 2003, with the aim of consolidating the sustainable management of forests and promoting the trade in wood of legal origin.

As part of FLEGT, on 3.03.2013 the EU Timber Regulation came into force (EUTR - [Regulation (EU) no. 995/2010], a document that prohibited European operators from

introducing illegally harvested wood or products obtained into the single market from this one.

Compliance with the Community normative act has generated a series of obligations for European economic operators, respectively

- access to information describing wood and wood products, country of harvest, species, quantity, supplier details and information on compliance with applicable national legislation.

- keeping records of suppliers and their clients

Being a member of the European Union since 2007, the aforementioned Regulation has acquired direct applicability in national legislation, imposing changes in domestic law, in order to harmonize secondary legislation with the Community normative act. In this context, several internal normative acts have undergone changes and/or entered into force, respectively Law 46/2008 Forestry Code, GD no. 497/2020 regarding the origin, circulation and commercialization of wood materials, to the regime of storage spaces of wood materials and round wood processing facilities, as well as those regarding the origin and circulation of wood materials intended for the owner's own consumption and some measures to apply the provisions of the Regulation (EU) no. 995/2010 of the European Parliament and of the Council of October 20, 2010 establishing the obligations of operators who place wood and wood products on the market, Law 171/2010 on forestry contraventions.[3,1,5,4]

The normative acts mentioned above are essential for protecting forest resources and for ensuring a sustainable industry and have the merit of conforming national legislation to international standards.

However, the same normative acts had a significant impact on the industry, influencing various aspects of economic-commercial operations and business strategy.

I. The compliance of economic operators with the legal obligations mentioned above requires additional costs

Specifically, it is necessary to:

1. contracting legal consulting services in special legislation

2. the specialization of employees or the employment of employees already specialized in the application of special legislation and the monitoring of how it is applied at the company level.

3. Thinking, drafting and operationalizing a monitoring and subsequent reporting system requires the contracting of specialized software programs, on a subscription basis

4. Companies are motivated to obtain sustainability certifications to demonstrate compliance with international standards. (eg FSC - Forest Stewardship Council) [6]

II. The application of legislation on the wood processing industry generates bureaucracy.

Beyond the costs, the implementation of the special legislation implies the adoption of complex administrative procedures, consuming resources and time.

A concrete example, in this sense, would be the Methodology for the application of the environmental assessment for forestry facilities (approved by Decision 236/2023 for the approval of the methodology for carrying out the environmental assessment procedure for forestry facilities). [2]

The assessment includes the analysis of potential effects on protected natural areas of community interest and the integration of conservation objectives into forest management plans.

Even if this procedure is important not only for compliance with national and European legislation, but also for the protection of natural resources in the long term, it generates costs and bureaucratic procedures, of the nature of delaying the completion of forestry facilities and implicitly the exploitation of wood material.

The environmental assessment for forestry facilities involves several essential stages, and has, as main steps:

- a) Initiation of the procedure.

- b) Evaluation of potential effects: The impact on protected natural areas and biodiversity is analyzed.

- c) Public consultation: The public has access to the information related to the forestry facilities since the first version was developed.

- d) Issuance of the regulatory act: The procedure is completed with the issuance of the environmental approval, after which the forestry management is approved in the Technical Forestry Approval Commission.

III. The cumbersome procedure of the environmental assessment and, implicitly, of the completion of forestry management, requires time, and this is likely to generate a crisis of the existing wood mass for sale.

The lack of wood has the immediate effect of increasing the price of the raw material, i.e. an additional difficulty for smaller economic operators (from the field of wood processing) and an additional risk, for them, of closing/restructuring their activity.

IV. Companies that invest in compliance and sustainability can become more competitive in the long term by attracting customers who value social and environmental responsibility.

V. Strict regulations can stimulate innovation in woodworking processes, leading to the development of more efficient and greener technologies.

CONCLUSIONS

It is as obvious as possible that the existing regulation is essential to ensure the sustainable management of forest resources and to prevent illegal logging. It is equally obvious, however, that the implementation of legal obligations is likely to generate additional costs, throughout the economic chain, from the operating company to the final beneficiary/consumer.

The high costs required for compliance and the conditioning of access to important markets by following these expensive and bureaucratic procedures can affect competition, in the sense of supporting large companies with high budgets and important human resources. Expensive procedures can create market distortions by favoring companies that already have a dominant position. These companies can use their financial resources to comply with regulations, while newcomers are de facto excluded.

In addition, in the context of limited budgets, high costs can discourage innovation, as small companies, which are often important sources of innovation, cannot afford to invest in the development of new products or technologies due to the financial burden imposed by expensive procedures.

The disadvantages for small companies, on the other hand, are genuine opportunities for large companies that, by escaping the competition and quickly adapting to the new

regulations, can benefit from competitive advantages and access to new markets.

The costs of implementation, monitoring, purchase of wood material will ultimately generate an increase in the price of the entire production chain, generating a higher final price for the final beneficiary.

To address these issues, regulators can simplify procedures and reduce associated costs by ensuring that regulations are proportionate and do not create undue barriers to competition.

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A NEW STUDY REGARDING THE DIGITAL PRINTING ON WOOD MATERIALS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The introduction of digital printing in the production lines that produce chairs was and is a real success for the most big companies in the domain. Each of them are very interested in developing this technology. But this technology does not stop here, because the chairs also have curved elements, namely digital printing on curved surfaces, at speeds up to 70m/min. Having a very well-technological production line one can guarantee these tolerances for digital printing, and at the moment it can produce up to 4500 printed chairs weekly. This paper describes the digital printing method using CNC (Computer Numerical Control) machining manufacturing technique.

Keywords: digital printing, wood materials, advanced technology, printed colors.

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INTRODUCTION

The present project was developed to protect the environment and certain slow-growing wood materials, such as oak, but also to be able to better refine the wood. Digital printing therefore requires very advanced technology, because the printer's colors are automatically combined through the four basic colors (Black, Yellow, Magenta and Cyan), in order to illustrate any image. Recently, digital printing has gained momentum and is done on any type of surface, starting from paper, wood, etc.

The process of digital printing on wood is a very difficult one because over time the wood works both in thickness and width, but also in length, and the deposition of dust on the surface of the wood is difficult to remove. As a result of these criteria, a printer was developed that does not have to touch the printing surface, as in the case of classic printers, which touch the paper.

The printer heads developed (by Industrial Inkjet) can print on wood, from a distance between 0.3 and 5 mm with an HD resolution at speeds that can easily exceed 120m/min. This distance allows us to print on almost any type of surface, but which must have a thickness variation between 0 and 5 mm or less.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Digital printing using a 4+1 axis CNC is very complex, because this CNC must be calibrated to PIXEL, which is not allowed to have deviations because, if there is play or wear on these axes, the image quality will no longer be able to be provided, or the print heads may fail.

This printing system is composed of the actual 4+1 axis CNC,

- The X axis moves the print heads left-right;
- The Y axis moves the work tables forward and backward;
- The Z axis moves the print heads up and down;
- The A axis rotates the print heads;

Axis 1 (additional) keeps the secondary tank permanently at the same distance, while axis A rotates, otherwise the ink hoses could be strangled, or air could infiltrate the installation. The print heads are electronically driven by 1024X4 lines of nozzles for each base color. The four lines (Figure 1) provide the gray level of each color, to best illustrate the image, and the printer has a total of 16384 nozzles.

Figure 1. Four nozzles lines

These print heads can only be touched with special wipes, which do not have lint, including skin grease, or dust particles that can damage them. If they become clogged, these heads are very difficult to clean and require quite a lot of time, especially since these heads are encapsulated.

The connection between the print heads and the image is made by the software owned (by Industrial Inkjet), namely the GIS server, which converts the image into electrical impulses and which coordinates the entire printing system such as:

- Vacuum systems that keep the ink from coming out of the heads and that pull back excess ink.
- The ink temperature that must be constantly maintained at 50 degrees Celsius.
- Resolution systems and printing speed.
- The system that coordinates the ink supply.
- The system for checking the voltage in the print heads.
- The automation and numbering system of barcodes.
- The image calibration system, which is made in the standard CMYB format.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To print the highest quality images, the image needs to be in TIF format, in order to be able to calibrate on each standard color level.

The ink used to print on wood is a water-based UV ink, which is aligned with all environmental standards, both chemically and physically. Working with UV ink, we will also

- The system that monitors the volume of grain in the tank and the values from the vacuum pump.

In any movement there is an acceleration and a deceleration, and in this case it must be treated very precisely so as not to distort the image. The synchronization accuracy from the encoders of the CNC tables and the print heads is done with five decimal places, and if they do not synchronize, the machine stops immediately.

The calculation formulas for printing are very well calculated and constantly checked with the help of control drivers, because there is always an acceleration and deceleration, respectively an image compensation.

The dimensions of the CNC tables are 1200mm/2000mm, and physically on these distances 70m/minute is obtained on a very small distance, and for this reason the values on the table encoders are constantly synchronized perfectly with the image, otherwise a deformed image will be obtained. The maximum size of a printed piece can be 3000mm/2000 mm, and an image for this format has an average size of between 5-8 GB.

need very fast UV lamps, in order to be able to gel or dry the ink.

The amount of ink is directly proportional to the density of the image, for example if we want to print barcodes we will use a lower density, which will use approximately 1gr of ink per square meter, at a speed of 140 m/min, and if we want to print a landscape at a high density to cover the natural colors of the wood we will

use 12-20 g of ink per square meter and a speed of 10 m/min.

In wood printing production, image calibration can be done in two ways:

1. using high-speed and high-resolution video cameras, which measure and calibrate the image according to the color of the wood, but which is very expensive, since a high-performance computer is also required, which can perform these operations at speeds of 70m/minute, taking into account that we have 5-6 GB images.

2. visual calibration of the image by modifying the color curves, which is not so expensive and can be done between 3-8 hours, but which will not be able to calibrate the color for each piece of wood.

In series production, images photographed using high-resolution photospectrometers are used, which extract up

to 12 image layers from real official color samples of wood essences.

Currently, around 15,000 marks are printed every 8 hours, of which over 80% are dried immediately on the machines, and the rest are dried later.

The print head anti-collision safety systems were developed to reduce damage to the print heads in the event of a collision with non-compliant parts. If this system detects an unevenness one step ahead of the print head, the machine's safety system is activated, which instantly stops the machine, blocking all CNC servomotors.

CONCLUSIONS

Digital printing is currently done to protect wood species that grow very slowly and are increasingly in demand, the oak image is printed on beech wood and is very popular with customers because it is very affordable and the color is very close to reality. In conclusion, we

can say that environmental protection can also start with digital printing on wood materials. We present below some samples for different printed colours (Fig.2, Fig.3, Fig.4).

Figure 2. Real and printed wood

Figure 3. Real and printed wood for the same colour

Figure 4. Printed oak wood

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MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF THE BEHAVIOR UNDER ACTION OF DIFFERENTS TYPES OF WOODEN STRUCTURES SUBJECTED TO COMPOUND LOADS

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Abstract

The problems related to the way of behavior of the frame-type structures made of wood are a topical problem in the case of practical applications. The way of loading the structures with external forces highlights the countless problems related to their resistance and rigidity..

The present paper deals with a work situation often encountered in frame-type structures, namely a first situation being their simple loading on the horizontal crossbar, followed by the loading composed of a horizontal force distributed on one of the frame pillars and the same vertical force on the crossbar.

The analysis follows the maximum percentage deviations recorded both in the case of the kinematic parameters and in the case of the static parameters, which define the characteristics related to the strength and rigidity of the structures. Therefore, the author does not perform a classical static analysis using the analytical methods used, but only pursues the determination of the maximum percentage deviations for the parameters determined in the case of the two types of loads.

Keywords: frame, kinematics, static, parameters, load.

INTRODUCTION

The author considers for the study and analysis the case of a frame with two vertical pillars with a length of 2 [m] and a horizontal beam with a length of 1 [m]. Between the left vertical pillar and the horizontal crossbar, the connection is made by means of an internal joint. Ground support is considered to be by means of two articulated supports. Considering the external way of fixing the frame, the structure is statically indeterminate. From the point of view of the way of loading the structure, two cases are considered, namely with a force concentrated on the cross member, respectively in the second case with the same force concentrated in the same way located and a force distributed on the pillar on the left side of the frame. The distributed force can be considered from a practical point of view as the loading force of the structure from the action of the wind.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The problem was treated in the work from a static point of view through a numerical analysis carried out with the help of the LISA 8 calculation program. The author did not resort to an analytical study in order to analyze the results, because the analytical methods were extensively treated for static structures undetermined by many authors (Ille 1977), (Ille, Bia, Soare 1977).

. Through the obtained results, the author aims to present from a statistical point of view the percentage deviations between the

kinematic and static parameters obtained in each of the two loading modes. The structure is considered to have a diameter of 0.15 [m] both on the horizontal beam and on the pillars. Young's modulus is 100000 [N/mm²], Poisson's ratio is 0.2, and the density is 700 [Kg/m³] for the oak species from which the structure is made.

The force acting on the horizontal crossbar is 10 [KN] in both loading cases, and the uniformly distributed force on the left pillar of the structure - wind force, is 10 [KN/m].

In the case of the analytical study of the structure by other authors, the efforts method was applied in order to determine the static parameters for both loading cases (axial tension forces, shear forces and bending moments) (Bârsan, 2003), (Martian 1999).

To determine the kinematic parameters in order to evaluate the stiffness of the structure, other authors applied the direct integration method, Mohr's method or the method of initial parameters (Bors 2005).

The study and analysis carried out by the author considered the isotropy of the material as a simplifying hypothesis. The study followed by the numerical analysis was based on the application of the finite element method (Fireteanu 2004), (Soare, 1999).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After running the LISA 8 program for the two loading cases of the structure, the following kinematic parameters were determined: the displacements along the X reference axis, the

vertical displacements along the plane Y reference axis, as well as the rotations of the cross sections of the main sections around Z axis. The determined static parameters are: axial stretching force, cutting force and bending moment. The analysis of the values obtained by the author is based only on the extreme values obtained for both the kinematic and static parameters. The extreme values of these parameters are presented in two tables. Table 1 includes the extreme values of the kinematic parameters. Table 2 shows the extreme values of the axial force, the cutting force and the bending moment.

The extreme values of these parameters are presented in two tables. Table 1 includes the extreme values of the kinematic parameters. Table 2 shows the extreme values of the axial force, the cutting force and the bending moment.

moment. Also, the graphic representation of the numerical values obtained and the mode of static and kinematic loading of the frame for the two cases is presented by means of a number of 12 figures. Figures 1 and 2 show the kinematic parameter the movement on the X axis, figures 3 and 4, the movements on the Y axis, and figures 5 and 6 the rotations of the sections in relation to the Z axis. Figures 7, 8 show the numerical variation of the axial force, in figures 9 and 10, the numerical variation of the cutting force and in figures 11 and 12, the numerical variation of the bending moments. The deformed shape of the structure for compound loading. Figures 13 and 14 show the deformed shapes of the structure for compound loading, respectively for loading with a concentrated force.

Table 1

The kinematic parameters considered in the module

Minimum displacements	Maximum displacements	Min Rotation	Max Rotation
Concentrated force			
0.005 (X Axes)	0.0365 (XAxes)	0.009	0.13
0 (Y Axes)	0/055 (Y Axes)		
Concentrated force and distributed forces			
0 (X Axes)	0.19 (X Axes)	-0.099	0.27
0.099 (Y Axes)	0.28 (Y Axes)		

Table 2

The static parameters considered in the module

Tensile force	Shear forces	Bending moments	
Concentrated force		0.085	1.87
0	0.51		
4.905	5.043		
Concentrated force and distributed forces			
0	0.43	0.20	3.39
2.63	7.93		

Figure 1 Displacement in X by concentrated force

Figure 2 Displacement in X by concentrated force and distributed force

Figure 3 Displacement in Y by concentrated force and distributed force

Figure 4 Displacement in Y by concentrated force

Figure 5 Rotation about Z by concentrated force

Figure 6 Rotation about Z by concentrated force and distributed force

Figure 7 Tensile force by concentrated force

Figure 8 Tensile force by concentrated force and distributed force

Figure 9 Shear Force by concentrated force

Figure 10 Shear Force by concentrated force and distributed force

Figure 11 Bending Moment by concentrated force

Figure 12 Bending Moment by concentrated force and distributed forces.

Figure 13 The deformed shape of the structure for compound loading.

Figure 14 **The deformed shape of the structure for concentrated force.**

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the results carried out by the author takes into account only the extreme values run by the program. The minimum displacement on the X axis from the concentrated force is 5 [mm] compared to the value 0 [mm] in the case of the compound load. The maximum displacement on the X axis in the case of compound loading is 81% higher than in the first case of concentrated force action. For the values of the maximum displacement on the Y axis, the displacement from the compound load is 80% higher than the case with a concentrated load. The analysis of the results carried out by the author only considers the extreme values run by the program. The minimum displacement on the X axis from the concentrated force is 5 [mm] compared to the value 0 [mm] in the case of the compound load. The maximum displacement on the X axis in the case of compound loading is 81% higher than in the first case of concentrated force action. For the values of the maximum displacement on the Y axis, the displacement from the compound load is 80% higher than the case with a concentrated load. In the case of the static parameter - axial force -, the maximum value is obtained in the case of loading with concentrated force approximately 53% higher than the case of compound loading. The maximum values are recorded on the right pole of the structure. The value of the cutting force

on load case 1 is 63% compared to the compound load. These extreme values are manifested in the sections of the structure on the crossbar in both loading cases, respectively also on the left pillar in the case of compound loading. The value of the bending moment for load case 1 is 55% compared to the case of compound load. The maximum values for both cases appear on the cross member, respectively and in the sections of the left pillar for the compound load. Therefore, for the same type of structure as the geometric and dimensional shape, in the case of compound stresses, an oversizing of the cross-section should be taken into account in order to ensure its strength and rigidity.

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THE EVOLUTION OF CONTROL STRUCTURES IN THE FORESTRY SECTOR FROM 1990 TO 2024

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

This article examines the evolution of control structures in the forestry sector, focusing on the attributions and the nature of the organization. Given that the organization and operation of these structures are governed by regulatory acts, the basic references are those related to legal aspects and their alignment with current realities in the field of forestry. The purpose of this material is to establish some key principles that need to be followed when modifying or creating optimal control structures in forestry, taking into account the experience gained over the last three decades and the economic, ecological, and social environment specific to the field in question.

Keywords: legislation, forestry, forestry control, forestry regime, forestry field, control structures

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INTRODUCTION

Romania's forests occupy a significant share of the national territory (according to INSSE Statistics the forest area is 6459.9 thousand ha, while according to IFN Statistics the forest area is 6929.0 thousand ha). The management of this important resource has been a constant challenge, due to the environmental, social and economic impact it generates.

The forestry sector, as described by Nichiforel (2018), is a complex field that begins with the forest itself, whose management is carried out through silviculture, and is completed with the exploitation and the industrialization phase. (fig. 1)

Each of these sectors (forestry, exploitation, industrialization) requires both a specific, targeted approach and a holistic approach that takes into account both access to resources and the best way to use them.

Figure 1 Organizations in the Forestry Economy Sector (Nichiforel, 2018)

With this in mind, the state has developed, over time, a series of legal provisions that regulate both the management of the resource (the forest) and the methods of forestry exploitation and even the industrialization of

wood. The legal framework for forestry dates back to 1786 when Emperor Joseph II issued the "Forest Decree for Bukovina". Later, in 1881, the first forestry regulation was published, the *Forestry Codex*, which was inspired by the

French forestry code. Since then, four other similar legal acts have been developed: the Romanian Forest Code of 1910, the Forest Code of 1962, the Forest Code of 1996 and the Forest Code of 2008. Each of these codes has undergone numerous amendments and additions over time. These changes have been driven primarily by political changes and shifts in ownership, the recognition of the ecological role of the forest, and evolving economic and social needs.

In the course of 2023, a new Forest Code was drawn up and, for the first time, this code is based on a medium- and long-term strategy (the National Forest Strategy 2030).

In addition to technical or administrative provisions, all of the aforementioned regulations also include articles or references to inspection and control activities in the forestry sector. With the development of society, the increase in demand for wood on the market, the need to develop agriculture or industry, and growing awareness of the role of the forest in maintaining the quality of life, the state has felt the pressure exerted on this resource and has taken increasingly decisive measures to protect it.

The earliest forestry regulations placed the responsibility for control primarily on the forest owner or the employed forester. Later, the need for establishing specialized entities with both administrative and control roles was identified. This shift in approach emerged as a result of diversified ownership, as well as the identification of the active role the state must play in the management of forests, as an asset of national interest

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The analysis of the structures with control attributions in the forestry sector was carried out from both a legal and a functional perspective.

Two periods can be clearly distinguished with regard to the structure of forest ownership and its influence on the institutions with control functions:

-1990–1992: The forest was owned by the state;

-1992–2024: The forest is in both state and private ownership.

This second period in turn consists of three stages, each defined by the way in which forest properties were returned:

a) Law No. 18/1991 on Land Resources

This normative act allowed the restitution of forest property as follows: up to 1 hectare for individuals or their heirs and up to 30 hectares for former communal owners, undivided communes, or their heirs. According to Bouriaud (2008) and Herța (2014), *the result was, as can be seen in Table 1, a considerable fragmentation of forest properties, so that by 2007 there were almost 360,000 properties, with an average area of 60 ares (0.6 hectares).*

Table 1

The evolution of forest areas by category of owners

Surfaces (ha)	1947	1990	1996	1998	2000	2007
Total forest area	6.487.000	6.372.000	6.372.000	6.367.000	6.342.538	6.397.027
State public forests	1.878.723	6.372.000	6.033.322	6.028.000	5.998.784	4.093.061
Private forests owned by natural persons	1.514.486	-	338.678*	339.000*	343.754*	359.573*
Natural persons' average forest area	3,1	-	0,6	0,6	0,56	0,6
Forests belonging to different private legal entities	567.399	-	-	-	-	526.042 of which collective forests approx. 500.000
Forests of collectives (compossessorates, communes, wealth communities)	1.330.000	-	-	-	-	500.000
The average area of forests belonging to legal entities, including communities	-	-	-	-	-	332
Cult institutions	approx. 300.000	-	-	-	-	79.952
Forests belonging to the communes	1.761.000	-	-	-	-	863.094

Source: Bouriaud (2008)

* Forests retributed according to Law No. 18/1991

** Forests retributed according to Law No. 1/2000 and Law No. 247/2005

Although the state has retained a large part of the forest area since the implementation of this law, this excessive fragmentation of the ownership has had a severe impact on the restituted properties, most of which have been subject to illegal logging.

b) Law No. 1/2000 on the restoration of property rights over agricultural and forest lands, applied for in accordance with the provisions of the Law on Land Fund No. 18/1991 and of Law No. 169/1997.

This normative act supplemented Law No. 18/1991 and authorized the restitution of forest land as follows: restitution of a maximum of 10 ha (including the area restituted under Law no. 18/1991) in the case of natural persons or their heirs, restitution of the entire owned area, which cannot exceed the area resulting from the application of the agrarian reform of 1921, in the case of the former members of the associative forms of ownership of the lands with forest vegetation, compossessorates, undivided freeholder communes, border forests and other associative forms assimilated to them, and their heirs.

c) Law No. 247/2005 on the reform in the fields of property and justice, and certain related measures

This normative act allowed for the full restitution of the previously owned land, providing for compensatory measures when full restitution was not possible, regardless of the type of owner.

Unfortunately, the development of land restitution legislation was not accompanied by adequate forestry legislation. In the absence of an appropriate legal framework, the administrative and control institutions were not adapted to the changes regarding the structure and size of the forest ownership. The lack of clear regulations regarding the owners' obligations, administrative responsibilities and concrete management methods for small properties, correlated with the absence of dissuasive penalties and strong control structures led to and facilitated illegal logging. According to (the Romanian Court of Accounts 2013), *"The legislation on forest management and control was disconnected from the laws on property restitution, which had a disastrous impact on state-owned public forests."*

Furthermore, the volume of illegally harvested timber between 1990 and 2011, as reported by the Court of Accounts (2013), underscores the above-mentioned issues. (Figure 2)

Figure 2 Illegally harvested timber 1990-2011

Source: (the Court of Accounts, 2013)

The main regulations, at the level of the Forestry Code, that regulate the activities of forestry structures in the period 1990-2024 are:

1. Law no. 3/1962
2. Law no. 26/1996
3. Law no. 46/2008

The Forestry Code of 1962 (Law No. 3/1962) defines in the very first article that forests "constitute (...) state property". It also defines the forestry regime as "a set of technical, economic and legal forestry rules regarding the development, cultivation, exploitation,

protection and guarding of this fund." This regulation also designates the entity that is responsible for forest administration and protection": "The Ministry of Forestry Economy establishes the technical forestry and protection rules applicable to land with forest vegetation, coordinates, guides and controls compliance with these rules." Chapter 4 of this Code, entitled "Protection and Guarding of Forests and Other Areas with Forest Vegetation", contains clear provisions regarding the persons or structures responsible for guarding duties. Thus, the entities with responsibilities in this field are: state enterprises for the forestry economy, socialist organizations with operational administration or use of forests. These duties are effectively carried out by "specialized technical personnel of state enterprises for forestry economy". Apart from these personnel directly involved in protection and control activity, the Forestry Code of 1962 also mentions other categories of personnel required to provide support or even conduct control activities: the executive committees of the popular councils, the bodies of the Ministry of Internal Affairs as well as road and railway wardens, forest owners and keepers. It should also be mentioned that this code contains provisions on the control of forestry operations and the circulation of wood material.

Law No. 26/1996-The Forestry Code defines in Art. 4 the types of forest ownership (public and private), and the fact that forests are assets of national interest. The central authority responsible for forestry is in charge of developing forestry policies and controlling the way in which the forestry regime is applied in privately-owned forests. At the time this Forestry Code was enacted, most of the forest areas were owned by the Romanian state, and thus, the responsibility for protection and control continued to rest with the National Forestry Administration. Prefects, county and local councils, as well as police and gendarmerie units, were appointed as supporting structures for forest protection activities. As far as private property is concerned, Law No. 26/1996, stipulates that the owner is responsible for the management and guarding of private property. The guarding of the forest could also be entrusted to the National Forest Administration, based on a contract. In this case, the obligations related to forest exploitation and the control of the

timber movement are maintained and regulated in detail. Additionally, with respect to control, this code also contains provisions on the control of installations for processing wood material into timber.

Law No. 46/2008 - The Forestry Code, promulgated three years after the last major amendment to the legislation on the restitution of forest land, took into account the fact that a significant part of the forest fund had become privately owned, requiring an adjustment in the approach to management and control. The National Forestry Administration remains the administrator of the state's publicly-owned forestry fund. The private forest fund, as well as the public property of the territorial administrative units can be managed through private forest cooperatives, or based on a contract for the provision of forestry services/administration with any forestry structure (state or private).

According to the Forestry Code of 2008, the state forestry authority is the central public authority responsible for forestry. Territorial structures are defined in order to implement forestry policies and to ensure control, and at the same time minimum area criteria for these structures are specified, as well as the size of the workforce. Thus, *the Forestry Subunits of the central public authority responsible for forestry are established at territorial or county level, having the minimum area of the forest*

fund, as follows:

- a) 60,000 ha in the lowland;
- b) 120,000 ha in the hill areas;
- c) 180,000 ha in the mountain areas.

Regarding the personnel employed in the territorial subunits of the authority, it is specified that *for an area of up to 12,000 hectares of forest fund, a forest engineer must be employed within the specialised territorial structures of the central public authority responsible for forestry.*

The control powers of the state authority are outlined in Article 102, as follows:

- a) *control over the implementation and compliance with the forestry regime in the national forest fund;*
- b) *control over the application of and compliance with the specific regulations in forest vegetation outside the forest fund;*
- c) *control over the movement of wood materials, processing plants, and timber storage facilities;*
- d) *control over the movement of non-timber products from the national forest fund.*

It can be observed that, by defining these control responsibilities, the entire forestry field is covered (forestry, forest exploitation, and industrialization).

Tables 2 and 3 provide a brief overview of the development of official control structures in the forestry sector, both at central and territorial level.

Table 2

Chronological evolution of the central public authority responsible for forestry

Name of the entity	The normative act of establishment	Period
Ministry of Forest Economy	Decree 162/1948	1948-1990
Ministry of Environment	GD no. 687/1990	1990-1992
Ministry of Waters, Forests and Environmental Protection	GD no. 792/1992 regarding the organization and operation of the Ministry of Water, Forests and Environmental Protection	1992-2001
Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forests	GD no. 12/2001 regarding the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forests	2001-2003
Ministry of Agriculture, Forests, Waters and Environment	GD no. 739/2003 on the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forests, Water and Environment	2003-2004
Ministry of Agriculture, Forests and Rural Development	GD no. 409/2004 on the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Rural Development	2004-2007
Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	GD no. 385/2007 regarding the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	2007-2009
Ministry of Agriculture, Forests and Rural Development	GD no. 8/2009 regarding the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forests and Rural Development	2009-2009
Ministry of Environment and Forests	GD no. 1,635/2009 regarding the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Environment and Forests	2009-2013
Ministry of Environment and Climate Change	Decision 48/2013 regarding the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Environment and Climate Change and for the alteration of some normative acts in the field of environment and climate change	2013-2015
Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests	GD no. 38/2015 regarding the organization and operation of the Ministry of Environment, Water and Forests	2015-2017
Ministry of Waters and Forests	GD no. 20/2017 regarding the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Water and Forests	2017-2020
Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests	GD no. 43/2020 regarding the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests	2020- present
National Forest Guard	GEO No. 77/2021	

Table 3

The evolution of the territorial structures of the central public authority responsible for forestry

Name of entity	The regulatory act	Number of entities at national level	Number of personnel allocated according to normative acts
Territorial inspectorates for forestry and hunting management	GEO no. 96/1998 regarding the regulation of the forestry regime and the administration of the national forest fund	unspecified	1 forest engineer/20,000 ha forest fund, 1 forest engineer or technician/10,000 ha forest fund
Territorial forestry inspectorates	Law no. 141/1999 for the approval of Government Ordinance no. 96/1998 regarding the regulation of the forestry regime and the administration of the national forest fund	unspecified	1 forest engineer inspector/20,000 ha forest fund, 1 forest engineer or technician/10,000 ha forest fund
Territorial inspectorates for Forestry and Hunting Management	Law no. 75/2002 for the amendment and completion of Government Ordinance no. 96/1998 regarding the regulation of the forestry regime and the administration of the national forest fund, republished	unspecified	1 forest engineer inspector/20,000 ha forest fund, 1 forest engineer or technician/10,000 ha forest fund
Inspectorates for Forestry and Hunting management under the National Environmental Guard	Decision 761/2003 for the reorganization and operation of the National Environmental Guard	8	259
	Ordinance 41/2004 on the establishment of territorial forestry and hunting regime directorates	8	102
Forestry and hunting inspectorates	GD no. 333/2005 for the reorganization of the forestry and hunting territorial directorates into forestry and hunting territorial inspectorates	9	361
Commissariats for Forestry and Hunting Management	GEO no. 58/2012 regarding the modification of some normative acts in the field of environmental protection and forests	9	662
Forest Guard	GEO no. 32/2015 regarding the establishment of Forest Guards	9	1007
Forest Guard	GD no. 743/2015 regarding the organization and operation of the Forest Guards	9	602
Forest Guard	GEO no. 77/2021 regarding the establishment of the National Forestry Guard	9	922

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The enforcement of compliance with forestry regulations within the publicly-owned forest fund was consistently ensured by the National Forest Authority. However, the private forest fund has been the most vulnerable to illegal logging. Although the obligations to monitor and guard these forests were assigned to private owners or administrative structures, these responsibilities could not be enforced for a long period (1992-2005) for objective reasons:

- Insufficiently regulated legal framework;
- Fragmentation of properties;
- Owners' inability to guarantee the security of the forest;
- Social and economic pressure on wood resources;
- The reluctance of owners toward association and toward state forestry management structures.

The central authority responsible for forestry has been administered by ministries responsible for either agriculture or the environment, which has affected the stability and strength of this structure.

The emergence of some territorial structures of the public authority responsible for forestry, has created the premises for

reducing illegal logging, overseeing forest operations, controlling the movement of timber materials, and monitoring wood processing facilities, thus covering the entire forestry sector. These entities have maintained a stable territorial jurisdiction from 2005 to the present.

The responsibilities of these entities have increased significantly over time, with many of the tasks being detailed and supplemented as a result of the evolution of forest management regulations. While the original regulations outlined around 10 general duties, formulated in a general way, the latest Regulation on the Organization and Operation of the Forest Guards, approved by Ministerial Order No. 2185/08.10.2024, contains a number of 219 attributions of a technical nature.

The number of employees in the regional structures has fluctuated significantly in terms of regulatory requirements (from 259 to 1,007 employees). Despite these regulations, for a very long period, regional structures operated with a personnel shortage, due to insufficient funding, low attractiveness due to salary levels, hiring freezes by central regulations, and structural changes.

In conclusion, the effectiveness of forest control is contingent upon adherence to the following principles:

- A stable, coherent legal framework adapted to the realities of the sector;
- Stability of the control structure regarding territorial competence, responsibilities, and allocation of personnel and material resources;
- High professionalism among personnel within these institutions;
- Consideration by the central public authority of feedback from territorial structures;
- Efficient and transparent communication of activities and results.

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- ***Law no. 141/1999 for the approval of Government Ordinance no. 96/1998 regarding the regulation of the forest regime and the administration of the national forest fund
- ***Law no. 1/2000 for the restoration of property rights over agricultural and forest lands, as requested according to the provisions of the Law no. 18/1991 on land resources and of Law no. 169/1997
- ***Law no. 75/2002 for the amendment and completion of Government Ordinance no. 96/1998 on the regulation of the forestry regime and the administration of the national forest fund, republished
- ***Law no. 247/2005 on the reform in the fields of property and justice, as well as some related measures
- ***Law no. 46/2008- Forestry Code
- ***GEO no. 96/1998 regarding the regulation of the forestry regime and the administration of the national forest fund
- ***GEO no. 58/2012 amending Certain Regulations in the Field of Environmental and Forest Protection
- *** GEO no. 32/2015 regarding the establishment of Forest Guards
- *** GEO no. 77/2021 on the establishment of the National Forest Guard
- *** Ordinance no. 41/2004 on the establishment of the territorial directorates of forestry and hunting regime
- ***GD no. 687/1990
- ***GD no. 792/1992 on the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Waters, Forests, and Environmental Protection
- ***GD no. 12/2001 on the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Agriculture, Food, and Forests
- ***GD no. 761/2003 on the reorganization and functioning of the National Environmental Guard
- ***GD nr. 739/2003 on the Organization and Functioning of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forests, Waters, and Environment
- ***GD no. 409/2004 on the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forests and Rural Development
- ***GD no. 333/2005 on the reorganization of the forestry and hunting territorial directorates into forestry and hunting territorial inspectorates
- ***GD no. 385/2007 on the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development
- ***GD no. 8/2009 regarding the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Rural Development
- ***GD no. 1,635/2009 regarding the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Environment and Forests
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ENVIRONMENTAL AND ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF WOOD HARVESTING FOR THE MAIN PRODUCTS BY MEANS OF HARNESES. A CASE STUDY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This paper discusses various aspects of wood collection using horses, emphasizing ecological and economic considerations. Seven felling areas within the Production Unit (P.U.) III Galbena of the Bihor Forestry Administration in Romania were selected. These areas feature progressive cuts, with the exploitation method being changed to a definitive and multiple wood system. This adjustment was made to yield smaller wood pieces suitable for collection with horses. Operating costs were calculated and compared under different scenarios, specifically analyzing the impact of wood collection with horses versus the traditional method using winches.

Three major factors were identified as having a significant influence on operating costs when using horses: average log volume, accessibility, and collection distance. Although the wood system itself has limited theoretical influence, cutting larger pieces is necessary to facilitate efficient horse-based collection in the forest.

Keywords: wood system, ecological collection, felling area, costs, collection variant

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INTRODUCTION

One of the oldest and most environmentally friendly methods of transporting wood is the use of horses or other draft animals. This method is gentle on the soil and vegetation and is ideal for delicate terrains where heavy machinery would cause significant damage. Moreover, this method is highly adaptable in mountainous areas where mechanized access is difficult (Mitchell & Malechek, 1983). Animal traction reduces soil compaction, prevents erosion, and allows for selective extraction, protecting forests and resources in the long term. Animal traction protects the soil and contributes to maintaining the integrity of forest ecosystems (Mitchell & Malechek, 1983).

The benefits of this method of wood collection are:

-Zero carbon emissions: Using animals does not produce greenhouse gas emissions, thus contributing to the protection of the atmosphere.

-Minimal impact on soil and vegetation: Horses do not cause significant soil compaction and can maneuver through rough terrain without damaging the vegetation.

-Adaptability: animal traction can be used in various conditions, including in protected forests or mountainous areas.

The advantages of environmentally friendly forest accessibility methods are:

-Reducing impact on soil and water: by using extraction methods such as cables, animal traction, or low-capacity equipment, soil impact is minimized, preventing erosion and protecting water resources.

-Biodiversity conservation: ecological exploitation methods allow the forest to maintain its biodiversity by protecting habitats and reducing fragmentation (Giurgiu, 2006).

-Long-term sustainability: these methods ensure the natural regeneration of forests and maintain their productivity in the long term without degrading the ecosystem.

-Reducing greenhouse gas emissions: Using electric equipment or animal traction helps reduce carbon emissions and combat climate change.

Some authors consider the use of animal traction as an ecological solution to gather wood (Horodnic, 2014), while other foreign authors argue that animals/horses should not be used in heavy forest labor in the 21st century (Romania has been criticized for using animals – horses and oxen – in the forest).

It can be said that the use of horses in the exploitation of wood is an ecological way of extracting wood. However, there are some requirements regarding the use of animals/horses in collecting logs. First of all, the weight of the logs should be as light as possible, so it is recommended to use the horses for hygiene and care work, especially when the volume of the average log is small, frequently below 0.45 cm. If horses are to be used in primary operations, then the logs must be much shorter in length. Thus, it is mandatory to change the method of exploitation to the shortwood system. The multiple assortment method is accepted, but the pieces must be manageable for the horses to pull.

Of course, climatic conditions, land conditions, the state of the trails, the species, the shape of the logs, the slope, and other factors influence the weight of the load and the distance the horses can haul the logs. A lighter weight and a shorter length of the pieces will cause much less damage to the remaining trees, soil, and seeds (Bereziuc, 2006; Horodnic, 2003). Collecting wood with draft animals is certainly an environmentally friendly method of collection.

The tools and means of collection are important factors influencing the operating costs (Oprea, Sbera, 2004). Thus, you can compare (Timofte, Enescu, 2019):

- Eco-friendly collection variants with less eco-friendly variants;
- Variants with a full assembly using a specific machine (tractor, cableway) with fragmented variants (e.g., using horses to assemble);
- Highly mechanized variants (with a high need for new roads) with less mechanized variants, etc.

When a single method is used for the collection operation, it is called integral collection with a tractor/cableway. When multiple methods are used for the gathering operation, such as draft animals and a winch, it is called fragmented collection. The same applies to the skidding and forwarding operations: they can be done entirely with a tractor or in a fragmented manner using a cableway and tractor.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study was carried out at the Sudrigiu Forest District, production unit III Galbena (fig. 1), and included the analysis of 7 felling areas proposed for operation in the period 2021-

2023. Even though the necessary documents for valorization were prepared, the operation of these parcels was postponed due to reduced accessibility, in the absence of an adequate collection network (Irimie, Timofte, 2019). There are even no roads available for tractors.

The felling areas are provided with progressive cuts and range in age from 117 years old (stand 1832) to 128 years old (stands 1887, 1911). Other data, such as volumes, degree of accessibility, age, and slope, are presented in Table 1.

Figure 1 Study Localization – Trees Map PU III%, Sudrigiu Forest District, Bihor Forest Administration (AS, 2014)

To determine the costs of operation, as a working methodology, the initial data (general memo, felling plan) are entered into the program *Deviz_exploatari.xls*, on the initial data sheet (Timofte, 2012, updated). The program automatically determines the costs in a tabular format, and on the summary sheet, the unit tariff for the entire wood volume is shown, with/without crates, along with separate costs for logging residues in case they are brought to the platform.

Table 1

Data on analyzed partisans (Irimie, Timofte, 2023)

No. crt.	Coupe no./ year of inventory	Plots	Volume of the average tree, in m ³ /tree	Age, years	Area, ha	Volume, m ³	Accessibility grade	Slope, degrees
1	742/2021	43B%	1.02	122	10.00	1964.0	3	30
2	1798/2021	43B%	1.15	122	5.00	1254.58	4	30
3	1802/2021	43B%	1.25	122	5.11	1507.27	4	30
4	1832/2021	48A%	1.25	117	5.50	926.25	4	25
5	1884/2022	48A%	1,11	118	9,29	1708,26	5	25
6	1887/2022	49A%	1,64	128	14,0	1652,11	3	34
7	1911/2022	49A%	2,10	128	10,0	1312,05	4	34
Total		-	-	-	58.9	10324.52	-	-

In order to facilitate the calculation of operating costs for a particular felling area, the program *Deviz_exploatare.xls* was used for the automatic calculation of volumes, time resources, and the fuel and lubricants required by operations and phases. Direct, indirect, and total expenses were determined based on the introduction of initial data characteristic of each forest district. The program also includes hourly rates as of 2023 and automatically applies the specific time norms used in wood exploitation works, specific fuel consumption (Ciubotaru, 1996), payroll grids, etc. The operating terms were taken from OM 1540/2011, updated by OM 487/2021.

A simulation is intended in which horses are incorporated into the gathering task in proportions of 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, and entirely with horses (100%) of the harvested area, in place of the tractor-mounted winch. The purpose of this simulation is to show that as horses are increasingly used in the gathering operation, the costs will rise, reflecting the expense of this environmentally friendly

method of extracting the wood mass compared to using tractor or cableway roads.

When using horses, the method of operation applied will be for final assortments. When using only winches mounted on tractors for the gathering operation, the method of operation will be in trunks and stems, which is also recommended in the APV.

For the horses, a maximum distance of 100 m was adopted in the calculations, and for the winch, the maximum distance given by the load cable (>50 m) was used. When using horses exclusively (fully assembled with horses), forming and tying the load to the tractor will require a minimum winch clearance (<15 m) in the calculations. These specifications are necessary because time norms and consumption vary depending on the gathering method and the distances over which the wood is collected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

For the 7 felling areas, direct costs, fuel and lubricant costs, indirect costs and total costs were determined (Table 2).

Table 2

Centralization of the operating costs of the 7 felling areas by gathering with winch (>50m) and forwarding wood with forestry tractors

Calculated indices	Number of felling area						
	742/2021	1798/2021	1802/2021	1832/2021	1884/2022	1887/2022	1911/2022
Total costs, without crunch, lei	292328,89	146386,16	154479,45	100498,63	186314,15	166541,84	141084,46
Total costs, without crunch, lei/m ³	122,15	125,38	110,33	118,37	116,50	107,37	116,40

In order to show that gathering with horses is more expensive than skidding the harvested parts with a winch, a simulation was conducted showing the influence of the two collection methods on the costs according to their weight. In Table 3 below, the following notations were used:

- ✓ T100 - the situation in which the collection is done entirely (100%) with the tractor;
- ✓ T80A20 - gathered with 80% winch, horses on 20% of the felling area;
- ✓ T60A40 - gathered with 60% winch, draft animals on 40% of the felling area;

- ✓ T40A60 - gathered with 40% winch, horses on 60% of the felling area;
- ✓ T20A80 - gathered with 20% winch, horses on 80% of the felling area;
- ✓ A100 - the operation is done entirely (100%) with animals/horses.

The values were obtained for skidding in the distance category >50 m for the first 5 situations and a distance <15 m for the last situation (A100), with the maximum distance to be gathered with the horses being 100 m.

Tabel 3

Operating costs, for the 7 felling areas with the method of gathering by pulling with winch on >50m and/or horses in different proportions, gathered with horses for a maximum distance of 100 meters

Felling areas	Costs, lei/mc	The way to collect, in different proportions, winch and/or horses					
		T100	T80A20	T60A40	T40A60	T20A80	A100
742	Direct - labor works	78,75	85,00	89,71	94,97	100,78	113,14
	Fuels and lubricants	13,43	12,81	12,30	11,96	11,79	12,09
	Indirect (expenses necessary for other activities required by the preparation and conduct of the operational works)	29,96	31,20	32,41	33,65	34,86	36,10
	Total costs	122,15	129,21	134,82	141,19	148,23	162,33
1798	Direct - labor works	71,34	77,55	82,23	87,45	93,22	107,53
	Fuels and lubricants	10,15	9,53	9,03	8,69	8,52	8,85
	Indirecte	43,89	44,34	44,78	45,22	45,64	46,09
	Total costs	125,38	131,62	136,44	141,97	148,18	163,47
1802	Direct - labor works	65,59	71,61	76,33	81,60	87,41	101,86
	Fuels and lubricants	7,24	6,61	6,10	5,76	5,58	5,92
	Indirecte	37,50	38,75	39,95	41,20	42,40	43,61
	Total costs	110,33	117,16	122,78	129,16	136,20	152,39
1832	Direct - labor works	66,63	72,35	76,87	81,95	87,57	101,07
	Fuels and lubricants	7,46	6,85	6,37	6,04	5,87	6,20
	Indirecte	44,29	44,74	45,19	45,61	46,06	46,48
	Total costs	118,37	124,14	128,82	134,19	140,30	154,75
1884	Direct - labor works	73,55	79,82	84,55	89,82	95,63	110,24
	Fuels and lubricants	9,63	9,00	8,50	8,16	7,98	8,32
	Indirecte	33,32	34,57	35,78	36,99	38,20	39,41
	Total costs	116,50	123,59	129,23	135,57	142,62	158,96
1887	Direct - labor works	67,23	73,29	78,03	83,32	89,14	103,86
	Fuels and lubricants	5,92	5,30	4,79	4,45	4,27	4,61
	Indirecte	34,21	35,46	36,67	37,88	39,08	40,29
	Total costs	107,37	114,25	119,90	126,25	133,30	149,75
1911	Direct - labor works	65,91	71,67	76,24	81,38	87,06	100,62
	Fuels and lubricants	7,79	7,16	6,66	6,32	6,14	6,47
	Indirecte	42,69	43,93	45,17	46,40	47,64	48,87
	Total costs	116,40	122,96	128,47	134,69	141,64	156,96

Additionally, the unit costs were represented in order of accessibility levels (from G1 to G5) and in order of increasing use

of draft animals as a method of gathering wood, at the expense of winch usage (fig. 2).

Figure 2 Representation of the unit operating costs for the studied felling areas, depending on the method of gathering (horses and/or winches), in order of accessibility levels.

CONCLUSIONS

Here is the revised version with "compartments" replaced by "felling areas":

Analyzing the results obtained in Figure 2 and Table 3, it is found that the addition of horses involves higher costs than the winch for all 7 analyzed felling areas, regardless of the degree of accessibility. There is a positive correlation between costs and the share of the operation to be gathered with the horses, but also between costs and the degree of accessibility.

Comparing the unit costs obtained by the simulation proposed as a case study, it is noted that the addition of horses has a significant influence, with the total operating costs increasing by 30.37% for stand 1798 to 39.48% for stand 1887 as the share of the horses increases from 0% (method T100) to 100% (method A100) to the detriment of the winch.

The skidding and forwarding operation method was only applied to full tractor collection (T100), and here the costs were the lowest for all 7 felling areas. For the other 5 situations (where the skidding is done partially or totally with the winches), the method was

applied in final assortment, and the costs were higher.

Although the horses lead to higher costs, the length of the parts and their weight must be reduced to facilitate the work of the animals. There are measures that can be taken to reduce the effort of the animals when collecting: notching (beveling, rounding with the axe) the ends of the logs, cutting into pieces as short as possible, cleaning the logs at the face of the wood, moving on snow to make the effort as small as possible, arranging roads (paths) to be 1.5 meters wide with a maximum slope of 40%, helping to start the load, etc.

In conclusion, ecological methods for forest accessibility, such as the use of ecological forest roads, cableways, animal traction, and low-capacity equipment, contribute significantly to the protection of forest ecosystems. Implementing these solutions is essential to ensure sustainable exploitation while protecting biodiversity and essential natural resources. By applying these methods, forests can remain productive and functional in the long term, without compromising the ecological balance.

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RESEARCH ON 5225 FOREST ECOSYSTEM TYPE SESSIL OAK WITH COMMON HORNBEAM MIXED STAND WITH CAREX PILOSA (REGIONAL VERSION WITH TURKEY OAK AND WITH A HIGHLY PRODUCTIVE SUBTYPE) WITHIN THE SEGMENT OF LANDSCAPE SITUATED ON LOW WESTERN HILLS OF TINCA FOREST DISTRICT

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The problem of establishing regional typological units is now the order of the day, but through new approaches, both theoretically and methodologically. In the research undertaken, the concept and method of establishing the types and their regional variants existing in Romanian works was adopted, but with more depth regarding the study of soils and phytocenoses.

Forest typology evolved from the necessity of differentiating management measures of the forests according to composition, structure, productivity, features of the stands, i.e. after their eco-systemic features (Doniță et al., 1990). In this type of forest ecosystem the nucleus of constant species consists of: *Quercus petraea* ssp. *Polycarpa*, *Quercus petraea* ssp. *dalechampii*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Quercus cerris*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Rubus hirtus*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Cornus sanguinea*, *Rosa canina*, *Carex pilosa*, *Dactylis polygama*, *Melica uniflora*, *Cruciata laevipes*, *Stellaria holostea*, *Galium schultesii*, *Ajuga reptans*, *Geranium robertianum*, *Stachys sylvatica*, *Mycelis muralis*, *Euphorbia amygdaloides*, *Lapsana communis*, *Veronica officinalis*, *Festuca heterophylla*, *Glechoma hirsuta*, *Carex sylvatica*, *C. divulsa*, *Fragaria vesca*, *Hypericum perforatum*, *Campanula persicifolia*, *Fagopyrum convolvulus*.

Keywords: forest ecosystems, geographical segment landscape, ecological landscape environment, sustainable forestry

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INTRODUCTION

This priority of this period is to establish types of forests ecosystems on small geographic units, at the level of landscapes, the typology having thus a strong regional feature.

We tried, as the research of this paper to establish ecosystem-based forest type principal existing in a territory smaller but representative low western hill within Tinca Forest District, to state the current status of types and propose appropriate management measures this state and designed to bring a type similar to the natural state.

The Low Hills, situated in the southwestern part of the study area, have average altitudes of 200-300 m, have reduced vertical fragmentation, with flat or slightly curved interfluves, elongated slopes and mid values inclinations. The valleys are rare, the clay deposits conditioning the formation of heavy soils, and on slopes the clay-loam deposits, with

alternation of sand and gravel deposits, conditioning the formation of normal hydric soils.

The relief is fragmented by valleys, the slopes being the main relief form, but also extended plateaus. On slopes, the sedimentary formations of sand, loam, clay, gravel, caused the formation of basic stagnic luvisols, at most mid basic, with a well-balanced hydric regime and on few areas eutricambosols, more fertile and with a well-balanced hydric regime.

The aim of the study was to establish the main forest ecosystem type within Tinca Forest District and to establish the state of these ecosystems in order to find the best management solution for a sustainable use, preserving and conserving the optimum biodiversity of the forest. The aim of the research was also the scientific fundamentation, very useful both in forest management and in applied forestry, in order to find the best management solutions for a sustainable use.

The soil indicators herbaceous and shrub layer consists of: *Festuca drymeja*, *Carex pilosa*, *Asperula-Asarum-Stellaria*. These types characterize stationary low-hill ecosystems where there are also soils with higher trophic levels, with balanced hydric regime, due to richer precipitation and permeable soils. Also, in the western low hills we meet: *Genista-Glechoma-Geum* type. This characterizes the ecosystems on moderately acid - weakly acid soils, with more a medium trophicity and with a quasi-balanced water hydric regime.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The locations of the research are the forests administrated by Tinca Forest District; the study has started in 2023 and continued in 2024.

The forest ecosystems were analyzed according to **location** within the study area; **the features of the ecosystem type**: surface area, geographical parameters (average altitude, altitude range); relief forms: types, inclination of the slopes, slope exposition, lithology, soil types and subtypes, ecological limitative factors); the description of the stands, the description of the herbaceous layer; the **correspondence with**: types of forests, types of stations, plant associations, types of habitat, **present state of the stands and management measures (particularities)**: main features, distribution according to age classes, the source of main elements, natural regeneration, productivity classes, management measures, variability and succession tendency (forms of type, successional tendencies and forest facies).

The description of the forest ecosystem was made based on collected field data. In order to analyze the collected data were used different softwares, such as Excel, ArcGis.

After determining the types, they were mapped by researching all the planning units and classifying them into types, considering the composition of the trees, the type of grass-subshrub layer, the type of humus (Moțiu and co., 2011; Moțiu and co., 2012). The delimitation method of the forest ecosystems had as base some typological schemes made for the study area (for ex forest corps) (Moțiu and co., 2011; Moțiu and co., 2012). The landscaping units with non-native species cultures were classified into types based on the type of resort.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

TYPE OF ECOSYSTEM: 5225 Sessil oak with common hornbeam mixed stand

medium-productive, with mull-moder, on stagnant luvosols, meso- and oligo-mesobasic, hydric quasi-equilibrium and alternating on profile, with *Carex pilosa* (regional variant with Turkey oak and a highly productive subtype)

Subtypes:

52251 highly productive subtype

52252 mid productive subtype.

Dispersion: this type of forest ecosystem is distributed in the low hills within: U.P.III - Trup Pădurea Gorunului, Trup Gânței; U.P.IV - Trup Miheleu - Topile, Trup Dumbrava, Trup Valea Mare, Trup Holod - Hodiș, Trup Forosig Trup Cărăndeni, Trup Bicăcel, Trup Miheleu; U.P.V - Trup Hodișel, Trup Măgura.

Characteristics of the type of ecosystem within the researched area:

a. Surface: 787 ha.

b. Forest resorts:

- average altitude 219 m (altitude variation 155-280 m);

- relief: by shape - middle and lower slope; by slope: moderate and steep slopes; after the exhibition - mostly shady or partly sunny slopes, rarely on sunny slopes;

- type of rock: sands alternating with sandy clays; clays, gravels, sands; red clay, gravels, sands;

- types and subtypes of soil: Typical and stagnant Luvosol, very little typical and molic Eutricambosol;

- limiting ecological factors: on steeper slopes medium edaphic volume, higher compaction in the Btw horizon, on partly sunny and sunny slopes low humidity in the second part of summer.

c. Compositions of the stands: in the dominant floor of *Quercus petraea ssp. Polycarpa* (in high proportions), disseminated may appear *Quercus petraea ssp. dalechampii*, *Quercus cerris* and *Prunus avium*; in the dominated floor it is met *Carpinus betulus* varied coverage of 5% - 80% of the area. In some situations *Sorbus torminalis* may occur with low frequency.

d. Compositions of the sub-stands: *Crataegus monogyna*, *Rubus hirtus*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Cornus sanguinea* and *Rosa canina* may occur less frequently. Shrubs are generally variably developed and unevenly scattered, depending on the shading of the hornbeam understory, with 5% to 25% cover. *Carpinus betulus* is also present in the understory; *Ulmus procera* can also be found in some situations.

The subtree is variably developed,

covering 10% - 50% of the surface, depending on the degree of illumination.

e. Composition of the herbaceous layer: *Carex pilosa*, *Dactylis polygama*, *Melica uniflora*, *Cruciata laevipes*, *Stellaria holostea*, *Galium schultesii*, *Ajuga reptans*, *Geranium robertianum*, *Stachys sylvatica*, *Mycelis muralis*, *Euphorbia amygdaloides*, *Lapsana communis*, *Veronica officinalis*, *Festuca heterophylla*, *Glechoma hirsuta*, *Carex sylvatica*, *C. divulsa*, *Fragaria vesca*, *Hypericum perforatum*, *Campanula persicifolia*, *Fagopyrum convolvulus*.

Figure 1: Sessile oak with common hornbeam mixed stand with *Carex pilosa* in u.a. 72B, U.P.V Belfir-Hodișel area, (photo - P.T. Moțiu)

Correspondence with:

- **Forest types²: : 5323** - *Sessile oak mixed stand* medium productivity (m)(situations without *Tilia*);

- **Resort types³: 6.3.1.1.** - Hilly oak (Sessile oak, *Quercus cerris* ± *Quercus frainetto*) Pm, luvosols, including whitish luvosols (± **hypostagnic**) medium edaphic, with mesoxerophyte grasses; **6.3.1.2.** - *Quercus frainetto* (*Quercus petraea*, *Quercus petraea* - elms, hilly elm with Sessile oak ± **Quercus cerris, Quercus frainetto**) Ps, luvosols (± **hypostagnic**), highly edaphic, with mesoxerophytic grasses and elements of mull flora;

- **Vegetable associations⁴:** *Lathyr* (*hallersteinii*) - *Carpinetum Coldea* '75;

²Forest types are cited from N. Doniță et al., 2005.

³Resort types are cited from F. Dănescu, C. Costăchescu, Elena Mihăil, 2010.

⁴Vegetal associations are cited from N. Doniță et al., 1990, and the types of new ecosystems, after V. Sanda, A. Popescu, D. I. Stanciu, 2001.

Among the sub-shrubs are *Chamaecytisus hirsutus* and *Genista tinctoria*.

In some situations they can also be found: *Viola reichenbachiana*, *Poa nemoralis*, *Festuca drymeja*, *Potentilla micrantha*, *Lychnis coronaria*, *Calamagrostis epigeios*, *Veronica chamaedrys*, *Agrostis stolonifera*, *Lysimachia nummularia*, *L. vulgaris*, *Carex praecox*, *Peucedanum carvifolium*.

The grass cover is developed unevenly, in patches, depending on the degree of shading, covering 20-30% of the surface.

- **Type of habitat⁵: R4132** - Dacian forests of sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*), beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) and hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus*) with *Carex pilosa*.

The current state of stands and management measures (peculiarities):

f. The structure of the stands: Figure 2 shows the distribution of the number of trees by diameters, and Figure 3 shows the vertical and horizontal structure of a representative arboretum, inventoried in u.a.72B, U.P.V.

g. Distribution according to age intervals: 0-5 years old - 1%; 6-10 years old - 13%; 11-20 years old - 30%; 21-40 years old - 33%; 41-80 years old - 21%; over 80 years old - 2%.

h. The source of the main elements of the stand: sessile oak - natural sowing 8%, shoots 33%, plantation 59%; common hornbeam - natural sowing 15%, shoots 85%;

⁵The habitat types are cited from N. Doniță et al., 2005.

Fig. 2: The distribution of tree numbers per hectare in stand, according to diameter categories and species in u.a. 72B, U.P.V Belfir-Hodisiel area

Legend:

Quercus petraea

Quercus cerris

Sorbus torminalis

Fig. 3: The diagram of vertical structure (left) and plan projection of the canopy (right) for test plot of 2500 sqm, using SVS software, 3.36 version, in u.a. 72B, U.P.V Belfir-Hodisiel area

i. Production classes of the main species of the stand: Go cl III; Ca cl III/IV; Ce cl III.

j. Natural regeneration through seeding: the sessil oak regenerates very well, the turkey oak and the other species regenerate well, the hornbeam abundantly; the quercines encounter difficulties from the hornbeam seed. We encounter situations with total regeneration in sessil oak (Moțiu and Bartha, 2006), but the lack of sufficient light and fierce hornet competition lead to the complete elimination of the sessil oak seed.

k. Indicated composition: 7Go 1Ci,Pa 2Ca.

l. Management measures on age intervals: 0-5 years - uncovering natural regenerations and/or plantations; 6-10 years -

the promotion of vigorous, well-conformed gorun specimens and valuable mixed species through the application of removal. It is obligatory to maintain the species of help (field maple, beam tree, hornbeam) in order to create a vegetation layer; 11-20 years - the proportioning of the mixture in accordance with the set target composition, through cleanings, the maintenance of valuable sessile oak specimens and of the mixture and aid species; 21-40 years - designation of future trees (from seed) of the main basic species – sessile oak, but also of the main mixed species (sycamore maple, plane maple tree) in order to increase the biodiversity of the tree stand and the application of combined thinning around these trees; 41-80 years - continue to promote the trees of the future by combined light intensive

thinning around them, keeping the rest of the stand closed; over 80 years - applying hygiene cuts.

m. Other management measures: keeping the stand structure closed.

Shoots should be converted gradually, as far as possible by natural regeneration (if the stand is of fruiting age) or by restoration. In the case of crops with ecologically non-indicated and seasonally unsuitable species (European black pine, Scots pine, acacia, American red oak, spruce, European larch), and pioneer species (European aspen, goat willow, European white birch); ecological reconstruction of the basic natural forest ecosystem type is recommended, by replacing them with native species adapted to local seasonal conditions. The only exception is Douglas fir, which in pure cultures, under favorable seasonal conditions, achieves very good growth and excellent wood quality (Moțiu, 2004). It is recommended to keep the hornbeam under control, to extract in time (before fruiting) the European aspen and the goat willow, which tend to eliminate the sessile oak and other mixed species. On sites with a greater abundance of undergrowth, work to aid natural regeneration is mandatory in years with abundant sessile oak fruiting.

It is also recommended to reconstruct the basic natural type of forest ecosystem in the case of partially or totally derived stands of hornbeam by substitution.

n. Variability and successional trends (forms of type, successional tendencies and forest facies):

in the situations with trophic soils - Eutricambosols (in the lower third of the slopes) the sessile oak is in the second production class, (in places) the succession to ecosystem type 5216 - Sessile oak stand with hornbeam, with *Asperula-Asarum-Stellaria*; the turkey oak is in some situations in the facies proportion.

o. Observations: gorun, but also the sky (present in the sky facies) can realize class II production, differentiating within this type of forest ecosystem also a highly productive subtype.

The ecosystem type 5225 - Sessile oak with hornbeam with *Carex pilosa*, is a stable type, the sessile oak regenerates very well from seed - stands with total regeneration (Moțiu and Bartha, 2006). In the investigated territory the regional variant with turkey oak and a highly productive subtype are formed.

CONCLUSIONS

The regional variants of forest ecosystem types arise due to the influence of regional variants of climate and soil - pedogenetic sub-layers. Knowing the physical-geographical conditions of the territory in which researches were carried out, are important for knowing the ecological complex of factors and determinants of the forest ecosystem biotope (forestry resort). The present work is a case study for the development of the regional ecosystem forest typology.

Regarding the regional particularities of ecosystem type

The regional variant of the sessile oak ecosystem type with hornbeam with *Carex pilosa* is given by the presence of the turkey oak in the dominant stage, from disseminated to facies proportion and by the existence of a highly productive subtype, where the sessile oak realizes the second production class, in forest resorts with trophic soils - Eutricambosols (in the lower third of the slopes).

Silvicultural recommendation

Keeping hornbeam regeneration under control, within the application of silvicultural treatments, to achieve the succession of stands in good conditions, with optimal compositions for the type of forest ecosystem. Preparatory cuts are mandatory to extract badly shaped hornbeam specimens with defects, especially those originating from shoots; thus avoiding the transmission of their genetic characteristics in the future stand, improving the gene pool of the hornbeam population and at the same time, maintaining the desired proportion of hornbeam.

It is recommended to reconstruct the basic natural type of forest ecosystem in the case of partially or totally derived stands of hornbeam by substitution. Ecological reconstruction of the basic natural forest ecosystem type is recommended, replacing ecologically unsuitable and seasonally unsuitable species (European black pine, Scots pine, acacia, American red oak, spruce, European larch) and pioneer species (European aspen, goat willow, European white birch) with native species adapted to forest resorts conditions.

Regarding forestry measures by type of forest culture have revealed that there were concerns relating to differentiating normal types but not about their current condition as a result of more or less proper management

methods. Forester practitioner is forced to differentiate on the basis of this action and the current state of forest types that manage them.

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CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE PHYTOCOENOLOGIC STUDY IN PURE EUROPEAN BEECH STAND FORESTS WITH *SYMPHYTUM CORDATUM* IN BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In the present study, a synthesis of the floristic diversity of pure beech stand forests with *Symphytum cordatum* from Bihor County is presented. The territory of Romania benefits from a great geomorphological and pedoclimatic diversity, favoring the development of a great floristic and phytocenological diversity of forest vegetation. *Symphyto cordati-Fagetum* Vida 1963, forest plant association is part of the forest phytotaxons with a more restricted distribution in our country, including a number of relict, endemic or rare species. The description of the *Symphyto cordati-Fagetum* Vida 1963 association from Bihor County was made by summing up 5 phytocenological studies carried out in the Codru-Moma Mountains, Plopiș Mountains, Pădurea Craiului Mountains, the northern part of the Bihor Mountains and the upper of the Crișului Repede basin (the interfluvium of Valea Iadei-Valea Drăganului), made in different periods of time. Presentation of the studied association was made by drawing up a synthetic table, selecting the relevés carried out in different areas of Bihor County in certain periods of time.

Keywords: phytocoenoses, floristic composition, beech forests, relevés, association

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INTRODUCTION

Phytocoenoses edified by *Fagus sylvatica* and *Symphytum cordatum*, forms pure zonal stands on limited territories in the Carpathian chain in our country. The phytocenological study of the beech forests with *Symphytum cordatum* in Bihor County was done in the Codru Moma Mountains (Pășcuț, 2012), Plopiș Mountains (Coldea, 1975), Pădurea Craiului Mountains (Groza, 2008), the northern part of the Bihor Mountains (Togor, 2016), the upper basin of Crișului Repede River (Iadei Valley-Drăganului Valley interfluvium) (Pop, 2024).

In the last 25 years the *Symphyto cordati-Fagetum* Vida 1963 association has been studied in our country by several authors, from Piatra Craiului Massif (Mihăilescu, 2001), Gurghiului Valley (Sămărghișan, 2005), Prahova Valley (Biță, 2003), Moldova (Chifu et al., 2006), Cernei of Olteț Basin (Răduțoiu, 2006), Luncavaț River Basin (Niculescu, 2006), Bistriței Basin (Aoncioaie, 2008), Stânișoara Mountains (Oprea & Sârbu, 2009), Orăștie River Basin (Vințan, 2014), Bihor Mountains (Ursu, 2013), Meseș Mountains (Ștef, 2021), Semenic Mountains (Bojinescu, 2022).

These phytocoenoses occupy flat, gently sloping to steep lands, with deep, soft brown, pseudogleyic, sometimes slightly skeletal, moderately rich in nutrients, rich in humus, moist soils (Chifu et al., 2014).

The association includes pure and mixed beech forests with fir and spruce in the climax stage. These phytocoenoses are well individualized floristically and ecologically in relation to the beech stand forests of central and western Europe through a group of Carpatho-Balkan species such as *Symphytum cordatum*, *Dentaria glandulosa*, *Euphorbia carniolica*, *Hepatica transsilvanica*, *Primula elatior* ssp. *leucophylla*, *Pulmonaria rubra*.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the phytocenological characterization of the association, the characteristic species were taken into account, species that are located only or almost only in the studied association (Borza & Boșcaiu, 1965). For the individualization and characterization of the studied association, a group of species that constantly develop in these phytocoenoses was considered.

The scientific name of the association and the name of the author were matched taking into account the International Code of Phytosociological Nomenclature, Edition 3 (Weber et al., 2000). The classification of the association into higher syntaxonomic units, suballiance, alliance, order and class was established on the basis of a group of characteristic species indicated in various specialized works, especially those developed by Oberdorfer (1977, 1978, 1983), Sanda et al., (1983), Coldea (1991, 1997), Pott (1995), Mucina (1997), Chifu (2004-2006).

The description of the plant association is based on the vegetation (floristic) relevés that are gathered in a synthetic table. In the table, the species are presented first, those that give the name of the association, then the differential species, and in alphabetical order the characteristic species of the suballiance, alliance, order, class, and finally the accidental, random ones from various vegetation classes (Chifu et al., 2014).

The species are mentioned in the association table by their constancy (I-V), and the adopted scientific name was in accordance with the work developed by Sârbu et al., (2013). The size of the reliefs is between 400-1000 m² (Cristea et al., 2004).

In order to highlight the floristic similarity of the phytocoenoses corresponding to the *Symphyto cordati-Fagetum* Vida 1963 association, in the 5 studied areas the Jaccard index was used as a calculation model, determined with the help of the Past 5 statistical program.

The classification of these forest phytocoenoses into habitat type and ecosystem type was carried out according to the classification made by Doniță et al., (2005).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Beech forests with *Symphytum cordatum* taken in the study occupy limited areas in Bihor County and were described from the Codru Moma Mountains (7 relevés), the Plopiș Mountains (5 relevés), the northern part of the Bihor Mountains (10 relevés), the Pădurea Craiului Mountains (5 relevés), the upper basin of Crișului Repede River (Iadei Valley-Drăganului Valley interfluve) (7 relevés).

These beech forests with black burdock are widespread in Bihor County at altitudes of 460-1364 m (Table 1). The specific relief of this association is that of slopes with varied

inclination (5-46°), with different exposures, plateaus and valley bottoms. The lithological substrate generally consists of basic, intermediate and rarely acid rocks. The soils on which these forests grow are of the eutricambosol, districambosol type, deep or weakly skeletal, medium-moist, with high trophicity, rich in mull-type humus.

In the tree layer, which reaches heights of 18-31 m and diameters of 20-120 cm, consistency 0.4-0.9, the dominant and edifying species is *Fagus sylvatica*. In this layer of vegetation the following species can also be sparsely found: *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Abies alba*, *Picea abies*, *Ulmus glabra*, *Betula pendula*, *Acer platanoides*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Populus tremula*, *Carpinus betulus*.

The shrub layer is well represented, but has a low coverage, being made up of *Sambucus nigra*, *Sambucus racemosa*, *Corylus avellana*, *Euonymus latifolius*, *Euonymus verrucosa*, *Salix caprea*, *Rosa canina*, *Viburnum opulus*, *Staphylea pinnata*.

In the herbaceous layer, which has a general coverage of 7-100%, the high presence of black burdock is noted (Figure 1).

Figure 1 *Symphyto cordati-Fagetum* Vida 1963, association (Dealul Ronțaru-Munții Codru Moma)

It is an association with a rich floristic composition, totaling a number of 145 species (Table 1).

Among the species with the highest presence that subordinate the association of the *Symphyto-Fagenion* suballiance and the *Symphyto cordati-Fagion* alliance we mention: *Dentaria glandulosa*, *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Abies alba*, *Festuca drymeja*, *Helleborus purpurascens*, *Aconitum vulparia* ssp. *vulparia*, *Fagetalia sylvaticae* order: *Rubus hirtus*, *Allium ursinum*, *Galium odoratum*, *Lamium galeobdolon*,

Mercurialis perennis, *Oxalis acetosella*, *Athyrium filix-femina*, *Actaea spicata*, *Sanicula europaea*, *Asarum europaeum*, *Quercus-Fagetum* class: *Dentaria bulbifera*, *Anemone nemorosa*, *Dryopteris filix-mas*, *Hedera helix*, *Mycelis muralis* (Table 1).

Within this association, the species with the highest share, from the point of view of bioforms, are hemicryptophytes, followed by geophytes and phanerophytes. In the phytocoenoses of the association, the floristic

elements with a large weight are Eurasian species, followed by European and Central European ones. Ecological indices highlight the dominance of mesophyllous, micro-mesothermophyllous, acid-neutrophyllous and weakly acid-neutrophyllous species, which corresponds to the distribution of these beech forests in the mountain floor on calcareous substrate (Groza, 2008; Pășcuț 2012; Togor 2016; Pop 2024).

Table 1

Symphyto cordati-Fagetum Vida 1963

Location	A	B	C	D	E
The number of relevées carried out	7	5	10	5	7
Altitude (m)	680-900	480-740	750-1250	460-830	630-1364
Exposition	N, NE	N, NV, NE	E, V, SE, SV, NV	N, NV, S	N, NE, S, SE, E, V
Consistency of tree layer	0.8-0.9	-	0.7-0.9	0.7-0.9	0.4-0.9
Height of the trees (m)	20-30	-	18-24	-	20-31
Trunk diametres (cm)	60-120	-	40-80	-	20-80
Herbaceous cover layer (%)	65-100	50-100	30-95	7-80	10-60
Slope (°)	5-10	5-18	2-30	15-40	8-46
Surface of relevées (m ²)	400	400	400	1000	400-800
<i>As. Symphytum cordatum</i>	V	V	V	V	V
<i>As. Fagus sylvatica</i>	V	V	V	V	V
Symphyto cordati-Fagenion,					
Symphyto cordati-Fagion					
<i>Abies alba</i>	I	I	IV	I	V
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	IV	II	II	.	II
<i>Aconitum napellus</i> ssp. <i>hians</i>	I
<i>Aconitum variegatum</i> ssp. <i>paniculatum</i>	.	.	I	.	I
<i>Aconitum vulparia</i> ssp. <i>vulparia</i>	I	I	II	.	I
<i>Crocus vernus</i>	II
<i>Dentaria glandulosa</i>	V	II	V	II	V
<i>Euphorbia carniolica</i>	.	I	.	.	.
<i>Festuca drymeja</i>	I	I	II	III	III
<i>Helleborus purpurascens</i>	III	III	I	II	.
<i>Hepatica transsilvanica</i>	.	I	.	.	.
<i>Listera ovata</i>	.	I	.	.	.
<i>Moehringia muscosa</i>	.	.	II	.	.
<i>Pulmonaria rubra</i>	.	.	II	.	II
Fagetalia sylvaticae					
<i>Actaea spicata</i>	II	II	I	I	I
<i>Adoxa moschatellina</i>	I
<i>Allium ursinum</i>	V	III	III	III	I
<i>Anemone ranunculoides</i>	V	III	II	II	.
<i>Aposeris foetida</i>	.	I	I	.	.
<i>Arum maculatum</i>	IV	I	I	III	.
<i>Asarum europaeum</i>	I	II	III	II	III
<i>Athyrium filix-femina</i>	III	II	III	I	IV
<i>Atropa belladonna</i>	I	.	I	II	.
<i>Brachypodium sylvaticum</i>	.	I	I	.	.
<i>Carex sylvatica</i>	II	I	III	.	I
<i>Chrysosplenium alternifolium</i>	II
<i>Circaea lutetiana</i>	II	II	I	.	III
<i>Corydalis solida</i>	III	I	.	II	.
<i>Daphne mezereum</i>	II	I	II	.	I
<i>Epipactis helleborine</i>	I	I	.	.	.
<i>Euphorbia amygdaloides</i>	III	II	IV	I	.
<i>Gagea lutea</i>	.	I	I	.	.
<i>Galanthus nivalis</i>	III	I	II	.	.
<i>Galium odoratum</i>	V	III	III	III	IV

<i>Geranium phaeum</i>	II	I	.	.	.
<i>Geum urbanum</i>	.	II	.	.	.
<i>Impatiens noli-tangere</i>	.	II	I	I	I
<i>Isopyrum thalictroides</i>	V	II	I	II	.
<i>Lamium galeobdolon</i>	IV	III	III	IV	IV
<i>Lamium maculatum</i>	II	I	.	.	II
<i>Lathraea squamaria</i>	.	I	.	.	II
<i>Lathyrus vernus</i>	I	I	II	.	.
<i>Leucosium vernum</i>	IV	.	I	.	III
<i>Lilium martagon</i>	I	.	.	.	I
<i>Mercurialis perennis</i>	IV	IV	III	III	I
<i>Milium effusum</i>	II
<i>Myosotis sylvatica</i>	II	I	.	.	II
<i>Neottia nidus-avis</i>	I	I	.	.	.
<i>Oxalis acetosella</i>	IV	II	IV	II	V
<i>Paris quadrifolia</i>	II	II	I	.	I
<i>Polystichum aculeatum</i>	II	.	II	I	IV
<i>Primula elatior</i> ssp. <i>leucophylla</i>	I	.	I	.	II
<i>Pulmonaria officinalis</i>	IV	IV	I	.	II
<i>Rubus hirtus</i>	V	IV	IV	I	V
<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	I	I	.	I	III
<i>Salvia glutinosa</i>	II	I	I	I	.
<i>Sanicula europaea</i>	II	II	I	I	I
<i>Scrophularia nodosa</i>	I	I	I	.	I
<i>Stachys sylvatica</i>	II	.	.	I	I
<i>Symphytum tuberosum</i> ssp. <i>nodosum</i>	I	II	.	.	.
<i>Ulmus glabra</i>	II	I	II	.	.
Quercus-Fagetia					
<i>Acer platanoides</i>	.	I	I	I	.
<i>Alliaria petiolata</i>	I	I	.	.	.
<i>Anemone nemorosa</i>	IV	V	III	II	V
<i>Asplenium scolopendrium</i>	I	I	II	.	.
<i>Betula pendula</i>	II	I	.	.	.
<i>Calamagrostis arundinacea</i>	.	.	I	I	III
<i>Carex digitata</i>	.	I	II	.	II
<i>Carex pilosa</i>	I	I	II	.	.
<i>Carex remota</i>	I
<i>Cardamine pratensis</i>	I
<i>Carpinus betulus</i>	.	.	I	II	.
<i>Corydalis cava</i>	III	II	II	II	.
<i>Cruciata glabra</i>	.	I	.	.	.
<i>Dentaria bulbifera</i>	V	V	III	II	IV
<i>Dryopteris dilatata</i>	III
<i>Dryopteris filix-mas</i>	IV	III	III	IV	II
<i>Epilobium montanum</i>	II
<i>Erythronium dens-canis</i>	III	II	.	.	.
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	.	I	II	.	.
<i>Geranium robertianum</i>	III	.	II	I	I
<i>Glechoma hirsuta</i>	III	II	I	.	I
<i>Hedera helix</i>	I	II	I	I	I
<i>Hepatica nobilis</i>	I	II	I	.	.
<i>Lilium martagon</i>	.	.	I	.	.
<i>Luzula luzuloides</i>	.	.	I	I	I
<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i>	.	I	.	.	.
<i>Maianthemum bifolium</i>	I
<i>Moehringia trinervia</i>	.	II	.	.	I
<i>Mycelis muralis</i>	I	I	I	I	III
<i>Platanthera bifolia</i>	I	I	I	.	I
<i>Polygonatum odoratum</i>	II	II	.	.	.
<i>Populus tremula</i>	I	I	.	.	.
<i>Ranunculus ficaria</i>	III	III	.	.	.
<i>Scilla bifolia</i>	III	II	.	I	.
<i>Scopolia carniolica</i>	.	I	.	.	.
<i>Stellaria holostea</i>	I	I	.	.	.

<i>Stellaria nemorum</i>	II	II	.	.	V
<i>Viola reichenbachiana</i>	I	II	I	.	I
Vaccinio-Piceetea					
<i>Picea abies</i>	.	.	IV	.	V
<i>Luzula sylvatica</i>	.	.	II	.	III
<i>Homogyne alpina</i>	.	.	I	.	I
<i>Huperzia selago</i>	I
<i>Campanula abietina</i>	I
<i>Soldanella oreodoxa</i>	II
<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	.	.	I	I	IV
Betulo-Adenostyletea					
<i>Adenostyles alliariae</i> ssp. <i>kernerii</i>	I
<i>Doronicum austriacum</i>	II	I	II	I	II
<i>Gentiana asclepiadea</i>	.	.	I	I	I
<i>Petasites albus</i>	III
<i>Polygonatum verticillatum</i>	.	.	I	.	IV
<i>Ranunculus platanifolius</i>	III
<i>Ribes petraeum</i>	.	.	I	.	.
<i>Ribes uva-crispa</i>	I
<i>Veratrum album</i>	II	.	III	.	III
Rhamno-Prunetea					
<i>Corylus avellana</i>	II	.	I	I	II
<i>Euonymus latifolius</i>	I	I	.	.	.
<i>Euonymus verrucosa</i>	.	I	.	.	.
<i>Galeopsis speciosa</i>	II	I	.	.	I
<i>Rosa canina</i>	I	I	.	.	.
<i>Salix caprea</i>	I	I	.	.	.
<i>Sambucus racemosa</i>	I	.	I	.	I
<i>Sambucus nigra</i>	IV	III	II	.	I
<i>Staphylea pinnata</i>	.	I	I	.	.
<i>Viburnum opulus</i>	.	I	.	.	.
Asplenietea trichomanis					
<i>Cystopteris fragilis</i>	.	.	II	.	.
<i>Poa nemoralis</i>	.	.	.	I	I
<i>Polypodium vulgare</i>	.	.	.	I	.
<i>Saxifraga paniculata</i>	.	.	I	.	.
<i>Sedum maximum</i>	.	I	.	.	.
Variae syntax					
<i>Ajuga reptans</i>	II
<i>Cardamine amara</i>	I	I	.	.	.
<i>Cephalanthera damasonium</i>	I	I	.	.	.
<i>Doronicum columnae</i>	.	I	.	.	.
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	.	.	I	.	.
<i>Lunaria rediviva</i>	I	I	II	.	.
<i>Senecio nemorensis</i>	.	.	II	I	I
<i>Solidago virgaurea</i>	.	.	I	.	I
<i>Spiraea chamaedryfolia</i>	.	.	I	.	.
<i>Telekia speciosa</i>	.	I	.	.	.
<i>Trollius europaeus</i>	I
<i>Urtica dioica</i>	II	.	I	.	I
<i>Veronica urticifolia</i>	.	.	II	I	.

The place and period carrying out relevées: A - Codru-Moma Mountains (2010-2024); B - Plopiș Mountains (1975); C - The northern side of the Bihor Mountains (2016); D - Pădurea Craiului Mountains (2008); E - The upper basin of Crișului Repede River (Valea Iadei - Valea Drăganului interfluvie) (2024). K - Constancy of species.

Cenotaxonomically, the *Symphyto cordati-Fagetum* Vida 1963 association, is included in the *Symphyto cordati-Fagenion* Boșcaiu et al. 1982 suballiance, the *Symphyto cordati-Fagion* Vida 1963 alliance, the *Fagetalia sylvaticae* Pawlowski in Pawlowski et al. 1928 order and the *Quercu-Fagetea* Br.-Bl. et Vlieger in Vlieger 1937 class.

Dendrogram of the phytocoenoses within the association (Figure 1), highlights a high

similarity between all the reliefs analyzed. It is observed that the closest phytocoenoses from a floristic point of view are those of the Codru Moma Mountains (A) and the Plopiș Mountains (B), as well as those of the Bihor Mountains (C) and the upper basin of the Crișului Repede River (Iadei Valley-Drăganului Valley interfluvie) (E).

Figure 1 Jaccard similarity index of the *Symphyto cordati-Fagetum* association, from Bihor County

CONCLUSIONS

They are naturally rare forest ecosystems, represented by virgin and quasi-virgin secular forests, with a high conservation value, sheltering a series of rare, endangered, vulnerable, endemic, tertiary relict, monuments of nature species such as *Symphytum cordatum*, *Cardamine glanduligera*, *Crocus vernus*, *Pulmonaria rubra*, *Aconitum napellus* ssp. *hians*, *Aconitum variegatum* ssp. *paniculatum*, *Aconitum vulparia* ssp. *vulparia*, *Sanicula europaea*, *Listera ovata*, *Lilium martagon*, *Platanthera bifolia*, *Maianthemum bifolium*, *Adenostyles alliariae* ssp. *kernerii*, *Soldanella oreodoxa*, *Trollius europaeus*, *Neottia nidus-avis*, *Primula elatior* ssp. *leucophylla*, *Cystopteris fragilis*, *Saxifraga paniculata*, *Cephalanthera damasonium*.

The beech forests with *Symphytum cordatum* in Bihor County are important from an ecological point of view, providing basic environmental services of nature, regularization of surface runoff, erosion control, protection of hydrographic basins.

The phytocoenoses of this association are included according to the work Habitats of Romania in R4109 Southeast Carpathian beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica*) with *Symphytum cordatum*, corresponding to the Natura 2000 classification in type 91V0 Dacian beech forests (*Symphyto-Fagion*), EMERALD: !41.1 Beech forest, PAL.HAB: 41.1D211 Dacian *Dentaria glandulosa* beech forest, EUNIS: G1.6D21. Dacian *Symphytum* beech forest, with ecosystem type 3316 Beech forest with *Oxalis-Dentaria-Asperula*.

These phytocoenoses are characterized by a great floristic diversity, highlighting the group of mesophyllous, microthermophyllous and acid-neutrophyllous species.

Regarding the floristic similarity of these forests, a stronger similarity is observed between the phytocoenoses of the Codru Moma Mountains and those of the Plopiș Mountains, as well as those of the Bihor Mountains and the upper basin of the Crișului Repede, mainly due to the geological, geomorphological and climatic factors that characterize these regions.

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CONSIDERATIONS ON THE HEALTH STATUS OF LOGGERS IN SUMMER AND WINTER WORKING CONDITIONS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Outdoor work, especially for loggers in forestry operations, involves significant health risks amplified by extreme weather conditions and climate change. This article examines the health risks and working conditions of forestry loggers, who are considered outdoor workers exposed year-round to extreme climatic factors. The analysis details the seasonal impact of high and low temperatures, which can lead to serious health conditions, including cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, as well as injuries from frostbite or sunburn. In summer, loggers face risks of dehydration, heat exhaustion, and ultraviolet radiation, while in winter, extreme cold and moisture increase vulnerability to hypothermia, frostbite, and reduced immunity. Prolonged exposure to extreme temperatures is associated with decreased productivity, increased stress, and a higher risk of accidents. The article also highlights the need for protective and adaptive measures, such as health monitoring, equipment innovation, and psychological support, to mitigate the impact of extreme conditions on the health and performance of loggers.

Keywords: loggers, environmental factors, seasonal work, heat stress, cold exposure

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INTRODUCTION

The health and safety of outdoor workers can be affected by various factors, such as rising temperatures, exposure to pathogens, ultraviolet radiation, air pollution near work sites, and extreme weather conditions. Each of these extreme factors can lead to different health issues. For instance, severe weather conditions can increase the risk of burns, frostbite, toxic gas poisoning, and extreme heat. These hazards amplify existing risks or can lead to new ones, including heat-related illnesses, vector- and waterborne diseases, accidents, allergies, and even cancer (ANSES, 2018). The emergence of such health issues results in a diminished quality of life, increased healthcare costs, and, ultimately, decreased work productivity and reduced output (Dasgupta et al., 2021; Dasgupta & Robinson, 2023). Beyond physical effects, these factors can also impact the mental health of workers (Schulte et al., 2016; Dasgupta et al., 2021). The severity of health issues is particularly high among older workers, those with preexisting medical conditions, and individuals with a low socioeconomic status.

Loggers, who form an important category of workers in the forestry industry, are included among outdoor workers. They are responsible for cutting and processing wood for various uses. In their work, loggers rely on chainsaws to ensure efficient cutting processes. Although

productivity and efficiency are greatly enhanced, the health and safety risks are significant. Prolonged use of this tool can substantially impact the health and performance of workers.

The purpose of this article is to present aspects related to the health of loggers, classified as outdoor workers, during their work in summer and winter. The presentation is organized separately for these two seasons, with climatic factors, especially temperature, considered the primary significant factor in this analysis.

WORKING IN SUMMER CONDITIONS

Loggers work outdoors and are exposed to numerous environmental factors that can impact their physical and mental health. In summer, high temperatures can impair the body's ability to regulate its temperature, which may worsen respiratory, cardiac, and renal conditions, lead to dehydration, and, in extreme cases, cause heat strokes (Parsons, 2002; Varghese et al., 2018; Wiki SSM, 2023). These conditions create heat stress as loggers perform strenuous physical activities in hot and sunny environments, straining their bodies. Extreme heat affects cardiovascular function, forcing the heart to work harder to cool the body through sweating. For loggers, intense physical exertion under the sun significantly increases the risk of hypertension and other cardiovascular issues, particularly during periods of extreme heat. If

loggers work overtime in such heat, recovery from heat stress may be insufficient, impacting reflexes, concentration, and other functions (Jones et al., 2020; Narock, 2021). Loggers are exposed to high temperatures for at least a quarter of their working hours. Research indicates that in the summers of 2020–2022, elevated temperatures in southern Europe led to numerous accidents and fatalities among outdoor workers, including those in forestry (EU-OSHA, 2024).

During summer, working in high temperatures causes loggers to lose fluids and electrolytes rapidly through sweat. Without adequate rehydration, symptoms of dehydration and heat exhaustion can occur, such as fatigue, dizziness, and nausea. As the body strives to regulate temperature, loggers may experience muscle fatigue and slower reflexes due to overheating, increasing the risk of accidents and diminishing concentration in high-risk tasks. Prolonged work in intense heat can raise stress and anxiety levels. Physical and mental exhaustion are particularly pronounced in summer, with associated discomfort affecting overall well-being, potentially leading to irritability and sleep disturbances. Such conditions are common among workers exposed to daily sun and heat.

The environment in which loggers work - forests, underbrush, and grasslands - can also increase disease risks (Covert & Langley, 2002). Such areas can harbor insects that carry pathogens, including ticks. Due to climate change, the proliferation of these pathogens and vectors is expanding across Europe, exposing loggers to vector-borne diseases such as tick-borne encephalitis and Lyme disease (Jones et al., 2020; Meima et al., 2020; EU-OSHA, 2024). Additionally, diseases previously non-endemic to Europe, like Rift Valley fever, yellow fever, and malaria, are now potential threats (EU-OSHA, 2024).

In summer, loggers are frequently exposed to pollen, dust, and other particles that can irritate the respiratory system. Additionally, heat increases the risk of air dryness, which can exacerbate pre-existing respiratory conditions such as asthma or bronchitis. The combination of heat and dust may have long-term impacts on loggers' lung health.

Loggers are also at an increased risk of exposure to ultraviolet (UV) radiation due to the changing climate, which can heighten the risk of sunburn and, ultimately, skin cancer. Studies show that outdoor workers, including loggers,

in Europe face a higher risk of skin cancer than indoor workers with similar skin types (Trakatelli et al., 2016; EU-OSHA, 2024). Continuous sun exposure can lead to skin irritation and sensitivity, especially on exposed areas such as the face, neck, and hands. Heat stroke is a serious condition that occurs when the body cannot cool itself fast enough. This can result in confusion, dizziness, nausea, and even unconsciousness. In severe cases, heat stroke can damage the central nervous system, with lasting effects on mental and cognitive motor health, raising the risk of injury (Piil et al., 2020; EU-OSHA, 2024).

WORKING IN WINTER CONDITIONS

During winter, loggers face health risks due to extremely low temperatures. Exposure to severe cold increases the risks of hypothermia and frostbite. Working in subzero temperatures impacts blood circulation and can strain the immune system, making workers more vulnerable to respiratory infections. Prolonged exposure to cold prompts the body to restrict blood flow to extremities to conserve heat around vital organs. This reaction can place stress on the cardiovascular system, raising the risk of high blood pressure and other heart conditions, especially for loggers engaging in intense physical activity in the cold. Frostbite is also a common issue for outdoor workers in freezing conditions; skin exposed to extreme cold can suffer severe damage, and in severe cases, there is a risk of numbness and infections. Frequent cold exposure can lead to excessive skin dryness, causing painful cracks, especially on the hands.

Repeatedly inhaling cold, dry air can irritate the respiratory tract and worsen preexisting conditions like bronchitis or asthma. For loggers who are also exposed to wood dust and other particles during work, respiratory health risks are heightened in the cold season. Physical labor in freezing temperatures affects joints and muscles, making them more prone to stiffness, pain, and inflammation. Cold temperatures reduce muscle flexibility and can exacerbate existing joint issues, such as tendinitis or arthritis, which loggers commonly experience after prolonged winter work. Long-term exposure to cold can weaken the immune system, leaving loggers more vulnerable to infections like colds, flu, and other respiratory illnesses. The immune system expends extra energy to maintain body temperature in cold conditions, which can impair its ability to fight

off pathogens, increasing the risk of chronic conditions, including rheumatism, over time.

Winter cold requires the body to expend more energy to stay warm, which can lead to pronounced fatigue. For loggers, the physical effort combined with the need to generate warmth can lead to quicker exhaustion and reduced productivity. Chronic fatigue can impair reflexes and focus, raising the risk of accidents. Working in extreme cold and the isolation typical of forested environments can also significantly impact loggers' mental health. Continuous exposure to harsh conditions, along with fatigue and isolation, can lead to stress, anxiety, and, in severe cases, seasonal depression.

WORKING THROUGHOUT THE SEASONS

Separate factors encountered in both summer and winter include humidity and precipitation in various forms. During both seasons, increased humidity due to precipitation can cause thermal discomfort for loggers. In summer, high humidity combined with heat can exacerbate issues of dehydration and heat exhaustion. In winter, humidity can lead to hypothermia more quickly, given that wet clothing loses body heat faster.

Precipitation, such as rain or snow, can make the terrain where loggers work unstable and slippery, increasing the risks of accidents, such as falls or slips. These challenging conditions can lead to injuries like sprains or fractures. Additionally, large amounts of precipitation can affect the efficient functioning of the tools used by loggers. For example, chainsaws or other equipment may become more difficult to use or may malfunction due to excessive moisture. This not only affects productivity but can also create additional injury risks.

Prolonged exposure to wet conditions can promote the development of allergens, which can worsen respiratory problems such as asthma or allergies. Loggers working in consistently damp conditions may be more susceptible to respiratory infections. Furthermore, challenging working conditions during rain or snowfall can lead to mental fatigue and decreased morale. A damp and cold working atmosphere can contribute to feelings of isolation and increased stress, negatively affecting the well-being of loggers. Increased humidity can influence how the body regulates temperature. In cold and damp weather, blood circulation can be affected, leading to inefficient

thermoregulation and increasing the risk of hypothermia among loggers.

In addition to the challenges posed by humidity and precipitation, the cold season brings with it additional risks related to freezing. Freezing conditions can cause tools to become stiff and more difficult to handle, thereby increasing the effort required for their use. Furthermore, working under these conditions can affect motor coordination, increasing the likelihood of accidents. Loggers may also be exposed to electrical hazards, especially when working near electrical cables or equipment that can become wet and thus dangerous. These situations underscore the importance of training in safety practices and the correct use of equipment in adverse weather conditions.

Additionally, the impact of humidity and precipitation on personal protective equipment is noteworthy. The materials used to make clothing and footwear can become ineffective in the face of moisture, reducing the protection offered against cold and wind. Inadequate or damaged protective equipment can compromise the safety of loggers and lead to decreased work performance. Therefore, it is essential for employers to ensure that all workers have the appropriate equipment to cope with varied weather conditions and to prevent potential health and safety issues.

CONCLUSIONS

Repetitive work in extreme conditions, whether hot or cold, can have cumulative effects on the health of loggers. In the long term, loggers may face an increased risk of chronic diseases, such as hypertension, cardiovascular conditions, and rheumatism. Exposure to cold can lead to accelerated wear on the joints, while excessive heat can accelerate chronic fatigue and respiratory problems. The human body attempts to adapt to extreme temperatures through mechanisms such as sweating, dilation or constriction of blood vessels, and modifications in heart rate. Intense physical work in extreme temperatures significantly increases energy requirements. During summer, loggers need food that prevents fatigue, while in winter, caloric needs increase even more, as the body expends extra energy to stay warm. An energy imbalance can lead to weakness, dizziness, and constant fatigue. These mechanisms are challenged daily, and continuous exposure can reduce the long-term

adaptive efficiency of the body, leading to exhaustion and health deterioration.

Adaptation to excessive heat during summer, as a preventive measure, can be achieved by implementing periods of lower work intensity and reducing working hours, especially during the first days of exposure to heat. To mitigate the negative effects of climatic factors, modifying the work schedule to avoid the hottest periods of the day may be necessary. An important factor that can support the health of loggers is the existence of a sense of community among colleagues. Working in extreme conditions, especially in isolated areas, can be psychologically challenging; however, social support among workers helps to increase resilience. Encouraging a work environment where employees support each other can reduce stress and create a trustworthy atmosphere. In areas with isolated forestry operations, where access to resources is limited, psychological support for managing stress and extreme conditions is often insufficient. Furthermore, in many physically demanding environments, including forestry operations, mental health is often underestimated. This attitude can lead to the stigmatization of psychological issues such as anxiety and depression, and to workers' reluctance to seek support.

As environmental conditions become more variable due to climate change, innovations in protective equipment and improvements in ergonomics become essential. Today, materials and equipment are being developed that are more resilient to extreme temperature changes, allowing for better air circulation or thermal protection, depending on the season. These improvements can reduce the impact of extreme temperatures on the health of loggers.

In the future, it is anticipated that workplace hazards sensitive to climate change may increase significantly. Periodic monitoring of loggers' health can help identify health issues related to exposure to extreme conditions. Regular medical visits and routine tests to assess cardiac function, respiratory health, and muscular health can prevent the exacerbation of conditions and allow workers to take preventive measures before problems become severe. A deeper understanding of threats to occupational safety and health is necessary to accurately assess and manage risks appropriately. For all preventive measures or action plans, employers must consult their

workers and train them in the implementation of these measures.

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CONCEPTUAL APPROACHES REGARDING THE ENERGY POTENTIAL OF BIOMASS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In Romania, biomass represents a significant untapped potential, with estimates suggesting over 7.5 million tons of oil equivalent per year, which could meet up to 70% of the country's renewable energy targets. Biomass, including wood, agricultural residues, and waste, is primarily used for heating, but inefficiencies in current systems, especially in rural areas, result in excessive consumption. Romania's abundant biomass resources, particularly from forestry and agriculture, provide substantial opportunities for bioenergy production, such as wood pellets, which are being increasingly adopted in energy-efficient systems. Legislative frameworks at both national and EU levels are essential in promoting biomass energy production and ensuring its sustainability. Biomass has been a crucial energy source throughout history and is now experiencing a resurgence as a key renewable energy resource. This paper explores Romania's biomass potential, the challenges of its current use, and the necessary steps to optimize its role in the country's renewable energy transition.

Keywords: Biomass potential, woody biomass, renewable energy sources,

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INTRODUCTION

Biomass includes all the organic matter in an ecosystem and is the most widely used and widespread renewable resource globally. Also, biomass represents a form of renewable energy that can be transformed into solid, liquid or gaseous fuel and can produce both heat through combustion and electricity through various conversion processes.

Biomass is considered the fourth largest energy source after coal, oil, and natural gas and is currently the most significant and widely utilized renewable energy option (Ladanai & Vinterbäck, 2009). Biomass is defined as an organic material of non-fossil origin, including organic waste that can be converted into bioenergy. According to Eurostat data from 2016, over 60% of the EU-28's total primary renewable energy production comes from biomass sources (EUROSTAT, 2016). Biomass has been an important source of energy since ancient times, although in 1870 it was replaced by fossil fuels, nowadays it has again become one of the main sources of renewable energy. Until the 18th century, biomass it was considered an essential resource for cooking

and continues to be one of the most common sources of energy worldwide (Spârchez, et al., 2019; McKendry P., 2002; Antar et al., 2021). Biomass is recognized as a source of renewable energy, suitable for various uses in both the domestic and industrial sectors, being considered an energy carrier with a neutral impact on CO₂ emissions (Huelsmann et al., 2019)

Biomass includes a wide variety of materials collected from nature or biological portions of waste. The most common example is wood (including firewood, wood residues, wood waste, twigs, logs and wood pellets), which is the largest source of biomass energy (Timofte et al., 2016). Biomass represents a significant percentage of the total renewable energy sources, having a weight of 47%. This is followed by hydro with 45%, geothermal with 5%, wind with 2% and solar with 1%. Solid biomass includes a variety of materials from industry, processes, or forestry and agriculture, such as firewood, sawdust, wood chips, and other solid plant residues, and is mainly used for heat and electricity generation (Cheng, 2022). Romania has an unexploited biomass potential estimated at over 7.5 million tons of

oil equivalent per year, and its exploitation could cover approximately 70% of the country's commitments regarding the contribution of renewable sources to total energy consumption (Nenu, 2023).

Romania already has the most important harnessed SRE potential, due to high-power hydroelectric plants. Renewable energy resources represent a viable alternative for replacing fossil fuels, both in Romania and throughout the world. In Romania, the renewable energy resource with the greatest potential in the short and medium term is biomass - woody and agricultural. (Tenchea A., 2008; Spârchez & Lunguleasa, 2023).

At European level, Directive 2018/2001/EC defines biomass as the biodegradable fraction of products, waste and residues of biological origin from agriculture, including plant and animal substances, from forestry and related industries, including fishing and aquaculture, as well as the biodegradable fraction of waste, including industrial and municipal waste of biological origin.

According to the national strategic plan - ROMANIA from June 2022, bioenergy in Romania constitutes over 65% of renewable energy, this percentage being supported by the balanced distribution of hill and plain areas. In the regions from the Carpathian arc towards the center, the biomass is predominantly rich in lignocellulose, and in the areas east, south and west of the Carpathian arc, plains with a significant amount of agricultural biomass predominate. The most used type of biomass is wood from forests, while a significant proportion of biomass potential is represented by agro-biomass, which includes agricultural residues and energy crops.

The global demand for energy and related services is constantly increasing to meet the needs generated by human, social and economic progress, as well as the improvement of well-being and health (Dolf et al., 2019). Worldwide, biomass covered approximately 70% of energy demand and is currently the main fuel used for energy production in developing countries (Spârchez, 2019).

According to the national strategic plan - ROMANIA from June 2022, bioenergy in

Romania constitutes over 65% of renewable energy, this percentage being supported by the balanced distribution of hill and plain areas. In the regions from the Carpathian arc towards the center, the biomass is predominantly rich in lignocellulose, and in the areas east, south and west of the Carpathian arc, plains with a significant amount of agricultural biomass predominate. The most used type of biomass is wood from forests, while a significant proportion of biomass potential is represented by agro-biomass, which includes agricultural residues and energy crops.

Biomass energy (bioenergy) is a versatile and flexible solution that can contribute decisively to the European Commission's objectives of achieving climate neutrality in the 2050 horizon, simultaneously supporting economic growth and creating new jobs. Currently, in Romania between 3.5 and 4 million households depend on bioenergy for home heating, especially through individual systems, wood stoves, with low efficiency.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

A comprehensive literature analysis was carried out to extract official data for the evaluation of biomass potential. Data sources and collection of information were performed through a detailed survey of providers on European, global and national.

The purpose of this paper is to provide an analysis of the current state of biomass research, thus contributing to the understanding of trends in this field. Biomass is the primary and dominant resource among all renewable sources available in Romania.

Romania's average annual availability of agricultural and forest residues for bioenergy is estimated at 228.1 PJ. This includes 137.1 PJ from annual crop residues, 17.3 PJ from permanent crop residues, and 73.7 PJ from forestry residues, firewood, and by-products of wood processing (Scarlat, et al., 2011)

The assessment of renewable sources in Romania (1 TEP = 11.63 MWh) is presented as follows (figure 1):

Figure 1 The energetic potential of Romania (ICEMENERG quoted by Badea et al, 2022)

The share of biomass in Romania's electrical energy balance is as follows: 62% - wind power plants; 28% photovoltaic plants; 7% hydro (figure 2).

Figure 2 The share of biomass in the electrical energy balance of Romania (ICEMENERG quoted by Badea et al, 2022)

According to the study carried out by Badea and his collaborators, biomass is predominantly used to produce thermal energy, known as "wood heating". The biomass used has a weight between 39% - 45% of the total energy consumption of domestic consumers (figure 3).

This large amount of biomass is used inefficiently, with most heating stoves having very low efficiencies (between 10% and 40%), which implies increased biomass consumption to maintain the desired thermal comfort.

Figure 3 Biomass consumption for heating (Mil.Mwh) (EUROSTAT, quoted by Badea et al, 2022)

At present, forest biomass is the primary source, comprising approximately 71.4% of the biomass used for bioenergy, while agricultural biomass and waste biomass contribute 15.3% and 13.3%, respectively (figure 4).

Bioenergy is Europe's most important renewable energy source and in 2021, bioenergy represented 55,7% of all renewable energy. As 22% of the EU's energy mix is renewable, this means that overall, bioenergy represented 10,2% of the gross final energy in 2021.

According to Eurostat, more than 40% of the energy consumption in Romania is produced from renewable sources, being above the European average and in front of countries much more developed from an economic point of view, such as the case of Italy, France or Poland.

Figure 4 Distribution of the various biomass feedstock for energy in 2021 (%) (<https://bioenergyeurope.org/bioenergy/>)

The top of the countries with the highest consumption of energy from renewable sources is led by Austria (76.2%), followed by Sweden (over 75%) and Denmark, being completed by Portugal and Croatia.

More than 40% of the energy consumption in Romania is produced from renewable sources, being above the European average and in front of countries much more developed from an economic point of view, such as the case of Italy, France or Poland.

The top of the countries with the highest consumption of energy from renewable sources is led by Austria (76.2%), followed by Sweden (over 75%) and Denmark, being completed by Portugal and Croatia (figure 5).

Figure 5 Share of energy from renewable sources in gross electricity consumption, Eu, 2021

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In Romania, firewood is the primary biomass used for energy, typically burned in low-efficiency stoves. Roughly one-third of households (about 2.5 million) use natural gas for heating, either through apartment-based central heating or stoves with very low efficiency—at least 500,000 homes fall into the latter category. Approximately 3.5 million homes, predominantly in rural areas, rely on solid fuels, such as wood or coal, burned in similarly inefficient stoves. The remaining homes use liquid fuels (oil, diesel, or LPG) or electricity for heating, and over half of

Romanian households only partially heat their living spaces during winter. To address these issues, a broad reform of heating technology is essential, particularly focused on rural areas.

The current legislative framework addresses biomass in a broad manner, referring to it both as a raw material for generating electricity and heat, alongside firewood—which is the primary product of forestry operations—and as waste, including green residues.

Eurostat data from 2019 indicates that biomass used as fuel is considered carbon neutral, since the carbon emitted during combustion was originally absorbed from the atmosphere during its growth cycle. However, there are several sustainability concerns associated with biomass as

a fuel source. Without a universally accepted definition encompassing all categories of biomass, it will continue to be viewed in a fragmented and incomplete way, and in some cases, may be mistaken for other resources. The Green Energy Association proposes the following classification:

- Natural biomass — sourced directly from ecosystems (wood waste resulting from dressing fruit trees; wood waste from the maintenance of access roads; minor and major beds of temporary and permanent watercourses; meadows, hayfields and pastures; green spaces in localities; bordering areas of uninhabited localities);
- Residual biomass (wood material resulting from wood processing);
- Energy crops (refers to crops intended exclusively to produce biomass for energy purposes);
- Agricultural residues (represent the waste resulting from agricultural activities).

Directive (EU) 2018/2001 on the promotion of energy from renewable sources aims to create a favourable framework for those who want to produce their own energy from clean sources. Biomass from woody and agricultural residues, is considered a significant and promising resource for pellet production due to their high availability, low cost, and potential to contribute to a circular and sustainable economy. Wood pellet production was identified as a rapidly growing sector, offering a sustainable solution with benefits such as compactness, low moisture content, and improved energy efficiency.

According to the Order of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development no. 304 of 2017, amended by Order no. 251 of September 27, 2021, the energy willow and poplar crop was removed from the list of non-agricultural energy crops. The strategy for the development of the agri-food sector in the medium and long term, with a horizon of 2020-2030, approved by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, has as its strategic objective the limitation and reduction of the carbon footprint of agriculture, the promotion of ecological agriculture and climate change resilience, as well as the stimulation efficient water management and renewable energy production. Although, the strategy encourages "the establishment of crops of forest species with a short vegetation cycle on agricultural land for the use of biomass for energy purposes", Order no. 251 of September 27, 2021, issued by the Minister of Agriculture to amend the annex to Order no. 304/2017, excludes the culture of energy willow and poplar from the list of non-agricultural energy crops (Badea et al., 2022).

The energy sector in Romania is booming, moving towards increasing the share of energy

generated from biomass, with a particular focus on woody biomass resources. Currently, only 3% of electricity comes from biomass, both from wood and agricultural sources.

According to Eurostat, electricity production from renewable sources increased by 5% in 2021, while the share of green energy in total consumption at European level reached 37.5%. Regarding the SRE share in the final gross energy consumption, Romania has assumed a share of 41.1% in 2035, respectively 86.1% in 2050.

CONCLUSIONS

Woody biomass has been and will continue to be an essential fuel resource with a long tradition of human use. Over time, it has played and still plays a vital role in the global energy economy. Biomass resources play a significant role in the global economy, although they are often used primarily as raw material in the wood processing industry. However, biomass has great potential as an energy material, being able to generate energy through conversion processes or direct combustion.

Romania is one of the EU countries with the greatest natural potential in terms of renewable energy sources. Biomass is regulated by a series of legislative acts that focus both on the exploitation of natural resources and on the promotion of renewable energy. Current EU legislation currently encourages a considerable expansion of the use of biomass for energy, with the aim of reducing emissions and mitigating the effects of climate change.

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THE TRANSITION TO A SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT AND THE IMPACT ON THE ORGANISATION MARKET BEHAVIOR

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The transition to a sustainable business environment is a critical imperative for organizations seeking to minimize negative environmental and social impacts while creating long-term value. This shift towards sustainability has a profound impact on organizational market behavior, presenting both opportunities and challenges. This abstract explores the challenges that organizations face in transitioning to a sustainable business environment and the subsequent impact on their market behavior. Key challenges include the initial investment required, stakeholder resistance, regulatory compliance, and market competition. These challenges necessitate effective communication, stakeholder engagement, regulatory awareness, and market adaptation to successfully navigate the transition to sustainability. Understanding and addressing these challenges is essential for organizations to leverage sustainability as a strategic advantage and enhance their market position in an increasingly conscious and competitive business landscape.

Keywords: Modern sustainable business environment, transaction, impact, organizational market behavior, challenges, sustainability

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the global business landscape has undergone a significant transformation, driven by an increasing awareness of environmental sustainability and social responsibility. The transition to a sustainable business environment is no longer a choice but a necessity for organizations striving to remain competitive in an ever-evolving market. This article explores the various dimensions of this transition, including the motivations behind it, the methods organizations are employing to implement sustainable practices, the resultant changes in market behavior, and the implications for organizational performance. By examining these aspects, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of how sustainability is reshaping the business environment and influencing market dynamics.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Research Design

This study employs a qualitative research design, utilizing both primary and secondary data sources to analyze the transition to a sustainable business environment. The primary

data was collected through interviews with key stakeholders in various organizations, including sustainability managers, marketing executives, and corporate strategists. Additionally, secondary data was gathered from academic journals, industry reports, and case studies that highlight best practices in sustainability.

Sample Selection

The sample for this study includes organizations from diverse sectors, such as manufacturing, retail, and technology. A total of 20 organizations were selected based on their commitment to sustainability initiatives and their market presence. The selection criteria included the following:

1. Demonstrated commitment to sustainability through certifications (e.g., ISO 14001).
2. Active participation in sustainability-related initiatives or partnerships.
3. Availability of data on market behavior and organizational performance.

Data Collection

Data was collected through semi-structured interviews, which allowed for in-depth exploration of participants' experiences and perspectives regarding the transition to

sustainability. The interviews were conducted over a period of three months and were recorded and transcribed for analysis.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was employed to identify recurring themes and patterns in the qualitative data. This involved coding the data, categorizing it into themes, and interpreting the findings in relation to the research questions. The analysis focused on understanding how sustainability initiatives influence organizational practices and market behavior.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Motivations for Transitioning to Sustainability

Organizations are motivated to transition to a sustainable business environment for several reasons, including regulatory compliance, consumer demand, and competitive advantage. Many stakeholders indicated that increasing regulatory pressures, such as carbon pricing and waste management policies, have compelled organizations to adopt sustainable practices. Moreover, consumers are becoming more conscious of environmental issues, leading to a growing demand for sustainable products and services. This shift in consumer behavior has prompted organizations to rethink their market strategies and invest in sustainability as a means of differentiation.

Implementation of Sustainable Practices

The implementation of sustainable practices varies across organizations, depending on their size, industry, and resources. Common practices include adopting green technologies, reducing waste, and enhancing supply chain sustainability. For instance, many organizations reported investing in renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, to reduce their carbon footprint. Additionally, organizations are increasingly focusing on sustainable sourcing and ethical labor practices to enhance their brand reputation and meet consumer expectations.

Impact on Market Behavior

The transition to a sustainable business environment has significant implications for organizational market behavior. Organizations that prioritize sustainability often experience enhanced brand loyalty and customer satisfaction. Consumers are more likely to support brands that demonstrate a commitment to environmental and social responsibility.

Furthermore, sustainable practices can lead to cost savings through improved operational efficiencies, ultimately affecting pricing strategies and profit margins.

Challenges and Barriers

Despite the positive outcomes associated with sustainability, organizations face several challenges in the transition process. These challenges include the initial costs of implementing sustainable technologies, resistance to change within the organization, and the need for training and education. Additionally, measuring the impact of sustainability initiatives on market behavior can be complex, making it difficult for organizations to justify their investments.

CONCLUSIONS

Transitioning to a sustainable business environment can have a positive impact on an organization's market behavior, but it also comes with its own set of challenges. By addressing these challenges proactively and effectively, organizations can successfully navigate the transition to sustainability and position themselves for long-term success in the market.

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ANALYSIS OF THE LEVEL OF POLLUTION WITH PARTICULATE MATTER PM 10 IN THE AREA OF BIHOR COUNTY IN 2020 – 2022

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In this paper we studied the level of pollution with particulate matter PM 10, in the area of Bihor County in the years 2020 – 2022. The data were processed from the Environmental Protection Agency Bihor Oradea, which is responsible for monitoring air pollution in Bihor County. Four air monitoring stations are located in Bihor County. A station to find inside the premises of the A.P.M. Bihor Oradea BH₁ is an urban station. The second station is located in the Bihor BH₂ Episcopia Bihor and is an industrial station. The third station is in Nufarul near McDonalds-drive BH₃, it is a traffic station, and the fourth station is in Țețchea BH₄ is an industrial station. In the period considered 2020 – 2022, the level of particulate matter pollution is within the normal range and the maximum permissible concentrations of 50 μg/m³ have not been exceeded. However, from daily observations, one can observe exceedances of the maximum permissible concentration, but these overruns lasted for several days.

Keywords: sedimentable particulate matter, monitoring, sampling points, maximum permissible concentration
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INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter PM 10 are formed from a complex mixture of very small particles and droplets of liquid, they are formed in the atmosphere following complex reactions of chemicals.

In the long run, these particles can have negative health effects. The suspended particles PM 10 have a diameter of less than 10 micrometers and are of two natural and artificial kinds.

In some cases, these suspended powders may contain carbon particles, heavy metals, toxic pollutants, etc.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The data used to carry out this study are used from the Environmental Protection Agency Bihor Oradea. For pollution surveillance in Bihor County, four sampling stations are located.

Sampling stations are located in strategic places BH₁ is located in the headquarters of A.P.M. Bihor Oradea, Dacia Boulevard no. 25/A being urban station, BH₂ in Episcopia Bihor, street Matei Corvin no.106/A, industrial station. BH₃ is located in the Nufarul Quarter, near McDonalds-drive and is a traffic station. And value of 7.99 g/m², followed by September 7.75 g/m² and May 7.57 g/m².

In 2022 the highest concentration of sediment particles concentrations were in

BH₄ station is located in Țețchea, being an industrial station (www.apmbh.ro).

In this paper we studied the variations, the level of particulate matter PM 10, between 2020 – 2022. The limit value for particulate matter PM10, according to Law no. 104/2011 on ambient air quality is the daily average value of 50 μg/m³ (STAS 12574/1987).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Annual evolution of particulate matter PM 10

Following the analysis of the particulate matter concentrations PM 10, it follows that in 2020 the highest concentration was determined at the sampling point of Țețchea BH₄ of 25.51 μg/m³ and 19.11 μg/m³ at the point located in Nufarul BH₃, and the lowest value was recorded at APM Oradea BH₁ (17.56 μg/m³).

For 2021 the highest concentration was recorded at APM Oradea BH₁ 19.31 μg/m³, followed by BH₄ Station Țețchea 18.06 μg/m³.

In the last year studied (2022) the highest concentration of PM 10 powders was determined at APM Oradea BH₁ 33.91 μg/m³, followed by 18.06 μg/m³, respectively, the BH₄ Țețchea (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The evolution of suspended particulate matter average concentrations in Bihor county, 2020 – 2022

From the analysis of the multi-annual average concentrations it follows that the highest value was determined at the BH₂ station in Episcopia Bihor, of 23.15 µg/m³, followed by 21.53 µg/m³ at APM BH₁.

Lower values were determined at the sampling points in Țețchea (19.74 µg/m³) and Nufarul (15.43 µg/m³) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Evolution of the multiannual average concentrations (2020– 2022) of suspended particulate matter PM 10 at the 4 monitoring points in Bihor county

2. Monthly evolution of suspended particulate matter PM 10

From the average concentration of sampling points for the period studied (2020 - 2022), it follows that in 2020 the highest concentrations were recorded in January of 29.01 µg/m³, in October of 28.00 µg/m³ and 27.00 µg/m³ in November. At the opposite pole is June with the lowest concentration of 6.60 µg/m³.

The highest values for 2021 were determined in February by 38.13 µg/m³, 27.15 µg/m³ in December and 25.47 µg/m³ in March.

The lowest value was recorded in August of 8.28 µg/m³.

The highest concentrations in 2022 were determined in May 37.51 µg/m³, in January 35.96 µg/m³ and in April 24.21 µg/m³. No samples were taken from July to December due to technical problems (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Monthly pattern of suspended particulate matter in Bihor county (the average of the 4 sampling points)

From the analysis of the multiannual mean concentrations of particulate matter PM 10 for the three years studied, we can conclude that the highest concentrations resulted in December

with a concentration of $25.57 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and in November $24.88 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The lowest values were recorded in June ($10.19 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), July ($12.27 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and August ($13.47 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The evolution of multiannual monthly average concentrations of suspended particulate matter in Bihor (the average of the 4 sampling points)

3 Evolution of particulate matter pollution PM 10 at sampling points

At the sampling point within A.P.M. Bihor BH₁ in 2020 the highest value was recorded in December of $25.76 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, in November of $25.63 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and in October of $19.93 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

During 2021 the highest concentrations were recorded in February of $36.64 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, in December of $34.74 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and in November of $30.13 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

In the last we took into study the highest values were recorded in January of $39.48 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, but this year's 2022 data is incomplete because in July - December for technical reasons no determinations were made (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Monthly evolution of suspended particulate matter at sampling point BH1

Table 1

Valorile depășirilor la stația de prelevare BH₁

Sampling point	Year	Month	Day	The values $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	Sampling point	Year	Month	Day	The values $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
BH ₁	2021	January	10	52.70	BH ₁	2022	January	15	63.25
			16	61.07				16	65.60
		February	8	53.51					
			20	63.41					
			21	73.56					
			22	59.06					
			24	100.71					
			25	80.43					
		March	26	78.51					
			3	58.01					
			4	52.71					
			5	51.99					
		December	26	61.54					
			15	61.56					
			16	58.71					

Following the analysis of the particulate matter PM 10 concentrations per day at the BH1 sampling point in 2020, no exceedances of the maximum permissible concentration of $50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ were recorded. However, in 2021, there were 15 exceedances of the maximum permissible concentration. There were 2 overtakes in 2022 (Table 1).

The highest concentration value of the particulate matter PM 10 at the BH₂ sampling

station in Episcopia Bihor was determined in December 2020 ($27.07 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). In January - March no determinations were made.

In 2021 high value was determined in February of $53.97 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ maximum allowable concentration being exceeded.

In 2022 determinations were made only in January - March, the highest being in January $46.98 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Mersul lunar al pulberilor în suspensie PM 10 la stația de prelevare BH₂

At the BH₂ monitoring point, in 2021, 17 overshootings were observed in 2022, respectively, 12 overshootings of the maximum

permissible concentration of $50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Table 2).

Table 2

Values of overshoots at the sampling station BH₂

Sampling point	Year	Month	Day	The values $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	Sampling point	Year	Month	Day	The values $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	
BH ₂	2021	February	18	52.02	BH ₂	2022	January	8	55.03	
			26	54.05				9	53.75	
		October	27	64.57				13	90.00	
			28	76.05				14	91.34	
			30	65.75				18	62.31	
			31	53.05				19	75.18	
			November	9				55.75	20	56.18
				12				64.57	24	56.20
		13		76.05				25	72.40	
		14		65.75				26	67.41	
		15		76.54				27	57.30	
		16		100.35				26	52.75	
		December	17	70.55						
			18	69.51						
			19	76.54						
			13	54.08						
				14			92.10			

At the BH₃ monitoring station in Nufarul district, the highest level of particulate matter concentration for 2020 was determined in October by 28.58 µg/m³ followed by November of 25.76 µg/m³.

In 2021 the highest concentration level was reached in February by 28.70 µg/m³ and in March by 24.76 µg/m³. For 2022 observations were made only in the first three months of the year (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Monthly evolution of suspended particulate matter at sampling point BH3

At this BH₃ sampling point in the years studied there were no exceedances of the maximum permissible concentration.

The level of PM₁₀ particulate matter concentration in Țețchea, BH₄ for 2020 the highest was determined in January by 47.13 µg/m³ followed by October of 45.70 µg/m³. It is worth mentioning that between February – June for technical reasons no measurements were made.

In 2021 high concentration was determined in February by 33.21 µg/m³, followed by 30.77 µg/m³ in January.

The observations made for 2022 were only on three months January – March, the highest concentration was in January 21.46 µg/m³.

At the BH₃ monitoring point no exceedances of the maximum permissible concentration occurred (Figure 8).

The maximum permissible concentration at the BH₄ station in 2020 was exceeded 12 times, repeatedly in 2021 only once (Table 3).

Figure 8 Monthly evolution of suspended particulate matter at sampling point BH4

Values of exceedances at the sampling station BH₄

Sampling point	Year	Month	Day	The values $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	
BH ₄	2020	January	8	50.30	
			10	67.18	
			11	81.54	
			12	64.69	
			18	78.66	
			19	66.53	
			20	60.04	
			21	53.75	
			October	23	68.51
				24	58.05
				27	51.60
	2022	January	15	64.75	

CONCLUSIONS

Following the analysis of the particulate matter PM 10 pollution over the period considered 2020 to 2022, at the four monitoring points we can conclude that the variations in the mean and multiannual concentrations, annual and multiannual monthly averages The maximum permissible concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ has not been exceeded.

On daily measurements at the 4 sampling stations were signaled overruns in 59 days. These overruns were mostly recorded in the cold season of the year, as homes are heated predominantly with wood and coal, resulting in more particulate matter pollution.

Important factor in the pollution of suspended powders are also weather conditions, and atmospheric calmness, lack of winds can lead to stagnation of dust in the atmosphere.

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ASSESSMENT OF AIR POLLUTION BY SETTLEABLE PARTICULATE MATTER IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF ZALĂU

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The study analyzes the atmospheric air pollution with settleable dust in the area of Zalău, data provided by the Environmental Protection Agency Sălaj. The research covers the period 2017-2023 and includes the monitoring of sedimentable dust concentrations in seven sampling points representative for residential, industrial and heavy traffic areas. The monitoring has been carried out on a monthly basis and the maximum permissible limits (MACs) are stable at 17 g/mp/month according to STAS 12574/1987.

The main findings indicate significant variations in concentrations, frequent exceedances of the maximum permissible values in areas with heavy traffic and near industrial activities. The main factors contributing to pollution include road traffic, industrial activities (manufacturing industry represented by companies such as Tenaris Silcotub and Michelin Romania) and construction activities. In contrast, precipitation plays a crucial role in reducing pollution concentrations.

The results emphasize the need to implement measures to reduce industrial emissions and more efficient traffic management. It is also recommended to promote environmentally friendly transport and to intensify monitoring measures to minimize the impact of pollution on human health and the environment. These conclusions emphasize the importance of integrated management of pollution factors in order to develop air quality in Zalău.

Keywords: sedimentable dust, maximum admissible concentrations, sources of air pollution

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INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is a major problem affecting health and climate, requiring rigorous studies and monitoring (Pereș et al, 2011). In the context of the city of Zalău, the paper analyzes the variations in settleable dust between 2017 and 2023, identifying the main sources of pollution and the influence of environmental factors on pollutant concentrations. Statistical data on air quality at 7 monitoring points were examined, highlighting the frequency of exceedance of maximum allowable concentrations and the impact of meteorological conditions on pollution.

Sedimentable dusts - have a diameter greater than 10 μm , have low stability in the atmosphere and therefore low diffusivity (Moza, 2009). They settle on the earth's surface near pollution sources. Sedimentable dusts originate from the building materials industry, the steel industry, road construction, mechanized

processes, soil erosion, road wear, etc. (Măhăra et al, 2003).

The municipality of Zalău, residence of the county of Sălaj, is located in the north-west of Romania, in Transylvania, in an area of hills and depressions, at the foot of the Meseș Mountains. The city is situated in the Zalău Depression, at an altitude of 275 m above sea level, on the Zalău River, and has an administrative area of 90.09 km².

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Data from the Environmental Protection Agency of Sălaj were used to analyze the atmospheric air pollution with sedimentable dust in the area of Zalău.

Sedimentable dust is determined at 7 sampling points in the city of Zalău with a monthly sampling frequency.

The monitoring points are the following:

- A.P.M. Sălaj - Str. Parcului, nr. 2

- Weather Station - Str. Meteorologiei, nr. 93 - residential area
- Str. 22 Decembrie 1989, nr. 175 - traffic station

- Str. Vânătorilor, nr. 3 A - residential area
- Str. Sărmaş, nr. 4 - conversion from industrial and storage area - to residential area - from 2023

- Station CFR Marfă Zalău Nord, bd. M. Viteazu, nr. 100 - industrial station

- Str. Cascadei, nr. 2 B - residential area

The monitored pollutants are analyzed for a period of 7 years, i.e. for the interval 2017 - 2023.

Maximum permissible concentrations for the pollutant settleable particulate matter MAC = 17 g/mp/month according to STAS 12574/1987.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Sources of air pollution

Industrial sources

Manufacturing industry represents the main industrial branch of the municipality. The main companies operating in Zalău are Tenaris Silcotub and Michelin Romania.

Tenaris Silcotub is the largest producer of small-diameter seamless industrial pipes in Romania. Silcotub exports to international markets products used in the oil and gas industry, the energy industry, the automotive industry, etc.

The *Michelin Group* acquired the Sylvania tire factory in 2001 and has since invested in technological development. The Michelin Zalău factory, with over 1500 employees, produces various types of tires.

Rominserv Valves operated in the manufacturing industry of the Municipality of Zalău until 2022. The company designs, manufactures and commercializes industrial valves for various industries, including petroleum, petrochemical and thermal.

The Romanian companies *Universal Group - Uniconf and Rosko Textil*, specialized in the manufacture of clothing, including underwear and sportswear, are also active in the manufacturing industry in Zalău.

Zalău's industrial sector is diversified, including sub-sectors such as material extraction, food production and preservation, textile and footwear industry, wood processing, packaging, soap and detergent manufacturing, glass and concrete processing, metal products

and machinery manufacturing, and furniture manufacturing.

Mobile sources

Transportation has a profound impact on the environment and is one of the areas with the greatest influence on air quality. This influence is felt not only locally but also globally. According to available data, transport accounts for about a quarter of the world's total energy consumption, making it one of the main sources of greenhouse gas emissions.

The main substances emitted by transport are carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and hydrocarbons. Carbon dioxide is the main greenhouse gas emitted from the combustion of fossil fuels in internal combustion engine vehicles, contributing significantly to global climate change (Pereş et al, 2011; Köteles and Pereş, 2022). Nitrous oxides are responsible for the formation of smog and acid rain, affecting human health and biodiversity. Hydrocarbons also contribute to the formation of smog and fine particulate matter, with negative effects on air quality and public health (Moza, 2009).

Starting in 1990, in the county of Sălaj there has been an upward trend in the contribution of road traffic emissions to total air pollutant emissions. This development was influenced primarily by the shrinking industrial sector, which led to a decrease in emissions from this source. On the other hand, the exponential growth in the car fleet has contributed significantly to the increase in road traffic emissions.

This change in the pollutant emission profile reflects changes in the economy and society of the county of Sălaj during that period. The reduction of industrial activities, possibly due to economic change and modernization, had a direct impact on industrial pollution sources. At the same time, economic growth and urbanization led to an increased demand for road transport, which resulted in a significant increase in the number of motor vehicles in circulation and, consequently, an increase in emissions from this source.

It is important to monitor these trends and adopt appropriate measures to manage and reduce the negative impact of road traffic emissions on air quality and public health in the county of Sălaj. These measures may include promoting public transportation, encouraging the use of less polluting vehicles, and developing infrastructure for alternative transportation, such as bicycle lanes and sidewalks for pedestrians.

Annual and multi-annual evolution of settleable dust

Figure 1. Evolution of the average concentrations of settleable dust in Zalău in 2018

Figure 2. Evolution of annual average concentrations of settleable dust in the municipality of Zalău, in the period 2017-2023

The areas with the highest concentrations include the Consinit concrete plant, the industrial area and areas with heavy traffic. The lowest concentrations were recorded on Cascadei Street, a residential area far from pollution sources.

In Zalău, the multi-annual average of sedimentable dust pollution over the last 7 years indicates the highest levels on Str. 22 Decembrie 1989 (8.3 g/m²) and Str. Sărmaș (5.4 g/m²). Str. Sărmaș, converted from an industrial to a residential area in 2023, is affected by pollution from the Consinit concrete plant and construction sites.

Figure 3. Evolution of the multi-annual average concentrations (2017-2023) of settleable particulate matter in the 7 monitoring points in Zalău

The lowest values were recorded on Str. Cascadei (2.7 g/m²) and at the Weather Station (3.1 g/m²).

Monthly evolution of settleable dust

The monthly trends of settleable dust in the area of Zalău show significant fluctuations in concentration.

According to the data, the highest concentration recorded was in April 2018, with 12.40 g/m², followed by May 2018, with 9.89 g/m². In contrast, the winter months recorded the lowest concentrations, with minimum values in January (ranging from 1.22 g/m² in 2022 to 2.09 g/m² in 2021).

This information emphasizes seasonal variations and highlights the impact of different meteorological and environmental conditions on settleable dust concentrations in the area.

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Figure 4. Monthly trends of settleable dust in the municipality of Zalău (average of 7 points), in the period 2017-20

During the studied period, multiple cases were identified where the maximum permissible concentration of 17 g/m²/month for settleable particulate matter was exceeded in certain areas of the city of Zalău. In particular, the 22 Decembrie 1989 street recorded exceedances due to heavy traffic and the area of Sărmaş street was affected by industrial and construction activities, including a concrete plant.

In May 2017, the concentration reached 29.9 g/m² in the area with heavy traffic on December 22, 1989 street. In 2018, there were three other exceedances of the maximum permissible concentration: two in April and one in November. In the Sărmaş area, exceedances were recorded in November (27.18 g/m²) and April (17.4 g/m²). In the area with heavy traffic on 22 Decembrie 1989, the exceedance was recorded in April, with a value of 18.1 g/m².

These data underline the negative impact of traffic and industrial activities on air quality in these areas.

This information emphasizes seasonal variations and highlights the impact of different meteorological and environmental conditions on settleable dust concentrations in the area.

Figure 5. Monthly trends of settleable dust in Zalău in 2017

Figure 6. Monthly trends of settleable dust in Zalău in 2018

Figure 7. Monthly trends of settleable dust in Zalău in 2019

Figure 8. Monthly trends of settleable dust in Zalău in 2021

In 2019, there were three exceedances of the maximum allowable concentration for settleable particulate matter in the area of December 22, 1989 Street due to heavy traffic. The values ranged from 20.24 g/m² to 23.36 g/m² and were recorded in March, May and August.

In March 2021, a similar exceedance was recorded due to heavy traffic on the same street with a value of 18.45 g/m². This data highlights the continuing negative impact of traffic on air quality in the area.

Data indicate that the highest amount of settleable dust is recorded in the warm period of the year, ranging between 6.08 g/m² and 6.67 g/m², when the amount of precipitation also reaches maximum values (72.2 - 99.1 mm).

This emphasizes the purifying role of precipitation for air quality, as it contributes to the removal of atmospheric impurities by trapping and depositing them on the ground during fall (Sabău, 2014).

In contrast, the lowest amount of settleable dust is recorded during the cold period of the year when precipitation is low. In January, in particular, the concentration is lowest at 1.61 g/m².

Figure 9. Evolution of monthly multiannual mean concentrations of particulate matter in Zalău (average of 7 points), in the period 2017-2023

Figure 10. Variation of the monthly mean concentration of settleable dust and atmospheric precipitation, in Zalău, period 2017-2023

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the analyzed data and information highlight the significant impact of air pollution on the Zalău area. The significant variations in the concentrations of settleable dust, the exceedances of the maximum permissible values in areas with heavy traffic and the proximity of industrial and construction activities, as well as the crucial role of precipitation in air purification, emphasize the importance of monitoring and managing air pollution in this area.

The manufacturing industry, represented by renowned companies such as Tenaris Silcotub and Michelin Romania, is vital to the local economy, but requires strict monitoring and the implementation of effective measures to reduce emissions.

Also, exceedances of the maximum permissible limit values caused by heavy traffic highlight the need for responsible traffic management and the promotion of more environmentally friendly means of transport.

Finally, it is essential that authorities, industry and the community work together to protect the environment and ensure clean and healthy air for all residents of Zalău.

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